

Investigating the creative formations and ideological physiognomies of Greek TV Comedy Series of the 1990s as influenced by the sociocultural principles of their zeitgeist.

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Ethical Approval

This study was filtered out at the pre-screening phase from the requirement of full ethical approval from the Academic Integrity & Ethics Committee (SAIEC) as the study involved the analysis of publicly available secondary data only.

Abstract

During the last decade, Greek Media studies have started to engage with investigations on the Greek television field under the scopes of Entertainment, and Arts and Humanities, deviating from their traditional politico-economical focus. Within a vibrant and rapidly developing environment of scholarly engagement, many recent studies are currently filling in gaps in knowledge related to various Greek television aspects, by producing discourses which usually combine production perspectives with textual analysis on Greek television fiction. Therefore, in order to contribute to covering part of the gap of academic discourse on the field of Greek television, this study investigates, through textual analysis, how eleven popular Greek comedy series produced during the 1990s (a decade considered as the golden era of Greek television comedies) have portrayed Greek national identity, political ideologies and sociocultural beliefs related to the institution of family through their narratives. While previous work has focused on political economy and state-media relations, this research shifts the focus toward the cultural and ideological underpinnings of Greek television fiction, offering a new perspective on how popular media can shape and reflect societal values. By analysing the creative processes behind these comedies, the study uncovers the complex interplay between entertainment, national identity, and cultural norms during a transformative period in Greek broadcasting. Through its examination of these, previously underexplored, areas, the study provides a more nuanced understanding of Greek television's role in shaping collective memory and identity, both in the past and in its contemporary reimagining. This contribution enriches both the academic literature on Greek television and the broader field of media studies, offering valuable insights into how television functions as a cultural and ideological force within society.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

On the 28th of October 2018, MEGA Channel, the first private Greek television channel was shut down. Thousands of Greeks tuned in to watch its last transmission - an episode from the 1990s hit comedy series *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)/Οι Απαράδεκτοι* (MEGA, 1991-1993). Since its foundation in 1989, followed by the launch of many other private television channels [ANTENNA (1989), STAR Channel (1993), SKAI (1993), APLPHA (1999)], MEGA had broadcasted some of the most successful comedy series ever produced in Greece - especially throughout the 1990s and early 2000s, a period frequently characterized as the ‘Golden Era’ of Greek television (Stamatiadi, 2018).

In the 2010s, many comedy series of that ‘Golden Era’ of the 1990s and 2000s were repeatedly rebroadcasted by the private channels that produced them, especially MEGA and ANTENNA, in order cover the gap left by the Greek debt crisis - a crisis, which dramatically decreased the quantity and quality of new productions. Despite the excessive reruns, the old comedies enjoyed very high viewing rates (both on television and online), particularly by young audiences, who have started a cult out of the series, by creating various platforms of ‘fandom’ activity on social media (Stamatiadi, 2018, pp. 629-630). The sentiments of nostalgia that these ‘golden’ series evoked for the Greek audience seemed to spread even more during the years 2016 to 2018 - the last two years before the shutting-down of MEGA. In detail, in 2016, MEGA was disqualified from the second round of the license competition accommodated by the government of the time (SYRIZA/ANEL). Therefore, until its closure in 2018, according to Aitaki and Chairetis (2019), MEGA broadcasted ‘a number of trailers of incredible emotional resonance’ reminding the audience of its contribution to Greek television history, sparking a sense of ‘separation anxiety’ and ‘collective loss’ for its looming farewell (pp. 3-4).

Nevertheless, MEGA was auctioned and bought by Evangelos Marinakis on the 1st of November 2019. It re-launched on the 20th of February 2020, just in time to celebrate its 30th birthday along with one of other major private channels of Greece ANTENNA. As Aitaki and Chairetis (2019) claim, during the period of their celebrations, both private channels ‘strategically’ retreated to historical archives and ‘nostalgically infused compilation of iconic

moments' from their past productions in order to 'convince' the audience about their prominent place in the 'collective memory and identity' (p. 4).

'These celebratory campaigns - centralizing on many occasions the resonance of television fiction - generated a number of reactions/reflections from popular journalistic criticism, activating once again debates around the sociocultural significance of private broadcasting in Greece during the last thirty years' (Aitaki and Chairetis, 2019, p. 4).

All these events - the closure and relaunch of MEGA, the 30-year celebrations of MEGA and ANTENNA, the sentiments of nostalgia, and the prominent place of private channels in the collective memory and identity of the Greek audience - generate a number of 'emotional aftereffects', as Aitaki and Chairetis (2019) call it, which encourage audiences, journalists, and scholars to reflect on Greek television and the many ways it has interacted with the individual television viewers and the Greek society as a whole. Alongside the continuous reruns of old series, followed by the recent restart of investments in new productions, which, once again, are focusing on creating television fiction, a series of questions in regard to the role and status of Greek television and its archive that have yet to be explored are brought to the surface (p. 4-5). After all, according to Aitaki (2018a), the so-far study of domestic programmes, genres and thematic trends that have appeared on Greek television fiction throughout time remains limited, despite the degree of popularity that they locally enjoy (p. 249).

Nevertheless, the conference '50 years of Greek television' (Thessaloniki, 9-11 December 2016), organised by the Laboratory of Cultural and Visual Studies of the Department of Journalism and Media at the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki demonstrated a rising interest towards a better understanding of the role of Greek television and an assessment of its potential in the digital era (Aitaki, 2018, p. 251). The Conference Proceedings, however, confirmed that so far academia lacks substantial research on Greek television studies. They proposed that academic investigation needs to be undertaken in areas such as television fiction genres focusing on their conventions and evolvement; audio-visual aesthetics of Greek television series; and television adaptations of literature or foreign productions. They also highlighted the lack of sociocultural analysis on Greek television series that focuses on issues such as family relationships, gender roles, sexual identities, social bonds and values, depictions of professions, cultural practices, collective and local identities (Vamvakas and Paschalidis, 2018, p. 37).

1.2 Research Aim

The previous section demonstrated the necessity and call for the conducting of essential academic research on the subject of Greek Television in order to help cover the current gaps in academic discourse on various aspects of the medium, such as its programmes, genres, thematic trends, aesthetics, and its portrayal (through television fiction) of sociocultural issues, including representations of family, gender, social bonds and identities. Therefore, in order to contribute to covering part of the gap of academic discourse on the subject, this study aims to investigate and analyse the creative formations and ideological physiognomies of the Greek comedy series of the 1990s as influenced by the sociocultural principles of their zeitgeist. In detail, the term ‘ideological physiognomies’ entails the ‘ideological framework’ incorporated within the Greek comedy series of the 1990s influencing their portrayals of traditional or modernized beliefs, values, and ways of thinking. The term ‘creative formations’ involves discussions around the creative process of Greek comedy-making, focusing on how the creators/scriptwriters of the series selected for analysis formulated and utilized the ‘ideological framework’ met in the Greek society of the 1990s in order to ‘create’ television comedy.

The core aspects investigated throughout the selected series in order to give answers to the research aim - in other words, the main themes that the Analysis chapter of the thesis focuses on, are: 1) Greek National Identity as represented in the Greek comedy series of the 1990s; 2) Political Ideologies as represented in the Greek comedy series of the 1990s; and 3) The Greek Family as represented in the Greek comedy series of the 1990s. This configuration of themes is inspired by: 1) Aitaki and Chairetis’ (2019, p. 4) discourse about the prominent place private channels withhold in the ‘collective memory and identity’, presented in the previous section (1.1); 2) Aitaki’s (2020, pp. 235-236) call for further studies on Greek television fiction, which would investigate whether and/or how political ideologies have infiltrated Greek television fiction/series - an argument presented in the Literature Review chapter of the thesis (section 2.1); and 3) by Vamvakas and Paschalidis’ (2018, p. 37) call for the conducting of academic research on sociocultural issues, such as social bonds, cultural practices, collective and local identities, family relationships, gender roles, and sexual identities as represented through television fiction, mentioned in the previous section (1.1) and in the Literature Review chapter (section 2.2).

The study focuses specifically on comedy series produced in the 1990s, because the 1990s constituted the first decade of private Greek television, which is considered a ‘golden’ decade, with numerous of comedy series produced during that period to be constantly re-broadcasted with high viewing rates and the creation of online ‘fandoms’ especially by younger

audiences, as mentioned in the previous section (1.1). Before presenting, however, the list of the comedy series chosen for this investigation, it is essential to frame out the historical context within which the series selected were produced.

1.3 The first decade of private Greek television: a historical overview

According to Medhurst (2006), after the second World War, the model of broadcasting that most of Europe embraced was the Public Service Broadcasting model (PSB), or else, the Reithian model, named after first Director General of the BBC, John Reith. By adopting PSB, European countries maintained a degree of control over broadcasting, producing a form of programming that was nationally focused but also internationally approved (pp. 117-118). However, in the 1980s, the television industry around the world, having become increasingly competitive, started implementing a Fordist model of operation. Advances in technology as well as an ideological shift away from Public Service Broadcasting (in the form of neo-liberal thinking) led to the abandonment of Reithian (public service) principles and to the adoption of a more market-driven approach to television. The cable and satellite television sector expanded rapidly and began threatening the terrestrial television providers, particularly in terms of attracting large audiences - thereby reducing the viewing figures of core terrestrial television programmes. In the UK, for example, the driving force for the shift to privately owned channels was the Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher (1979-1990), as during her first tenure, two additional private channels (to the already existing private channel ITV) were launched: Channel 4 and the Welsh-language channel Sianel Pedwar Cymru, or else, S4C (pp. 120-121).

In Greece, according to Koukoutsaki-Monnier (2010), when the socialist party PASOK (Panhellenic Socialist Movement) won the 1981 general election, it did not proceed to any discussions on potential launching of private television channels in the country but maintained the already existing 'state monopoly' in regard to national television, according to which Greece could only have state-owned television channels (p. 438). In less than a decade, this situation would change radically, and the 1990s would be known as 'the decade that Greek television was dominated by private channels, while state-owned television was marginalized' (Papathanasopoulos, 2000, p.165). In detail, in 1989, the liberal party New Democracy won the general elections, but not having obtained a majority in the parliament, was unable to form a government of its own. Therefore, it created a national unity government along with PASOK and other parties. In the autumn of the same year, the national unity government led by New Democracy passed legislation legalizing private radio and television broadcasting and provided provisional licenses to private channels (Valoukos, 2018, p. 140). According to Vovou (2010),

the launch of the first two private national-coverage channels, MEGA Channel and ANTENNA TV, signified the beginning of a new era for Greek television. The first official transmission of MEGA took place on the 20th of November 1989, followed by ANTENNA on the 31st of December 1989 (p. 124). In 1993, another two private channels of national-coverage, SKY TV (later renamed SKAI TV) and STAR Channel, started broadcasting. Alongside the national-coverage private channels, more than 160 local-coverage channels were launched by 1995. However, they mainly focused on transmitting foreign films, music videos and talk-shows (Koukoutsaki-Monnier, 2010, p. 426).

According to Papathanasopoulos (2000), the Greek television history of the 1990s can be divided into three periods. The first one is the shortest, lasting from the end of 1989 (when MEGA was founded, followed by ANTENNA) until May 1990. During that period, Greek productions were few, as both private channels were looking to define their identity and role within Greek television. Through the practice of trial-and-error, they tried to shape their profiles, as well as detect what sort of programmes the Greek audience would prefer. During the second period (October 1990 until May 1993), both major private channels dominated the Greek television market attracting audiences and advertisers. This enabled them to invest in Greek productions, and quickly realised that the Greek audience did favour domestic productions. That shift triggered a spectacular evolvement of Greek television production industry, as, due to high demand, dozens of weekly comedy and drama series, daily series and television games were produced. The third period (October 1993 until the end of the decade) was marked by the entrance of many new private channels into the television landscape (especially SKAI and STAR-Channel), which sought to get their own share in the television market and advertisement profits (pp. 165-166).

In the case of the already existing state-owned television channels, then called ET1, ET2 and ET3, after the establishment of the new deregulation (legalization of private broadcasting) and the launch of private channels, their viewing rates declined noticeably (Vovou, 2010, p. 124). According to Paschalidis (2018), there had never been such a massive movement of viewership from national channels to private channels, when legalization of private broadcasting took place in other European countries - mainly, due to the intense state-control and the lack of quality programmes that characterized the Greek state-owned television channels since their launch in 1966 (with the exception of ET3 which launched in 1988) (p. 28). In detail, in 1989, just before the foundation of MEGA, state-owned channels gathered 62% of the average television viewership. In 1990, ET1's average viewing rates dropped to 19.7% and ET2's to 8.7%, whereas MEGA and ANTENNA reached 30.4% and 18%

respectively. In the years that followed, the situation worsened, as in 1996, ET1's viewing rates dropped to 4.8% and ET2's 3.5%. As Vovou (2010) explains, Greek state-owned television, still under the pressure of government control, failed to adapt to the new state of affairs and shape its own strategies. On the other hand, private channels inaugurated a highly commercial and profitable way of function, taking into account viewing rates and advertisement. Content-wise, they contributed to the increase of the production rate of game and, later on, reality shows. However, the area, on which the private channels focused the most, was television series (p. 124). As Koukoutsaki-Monnier (2010) puts it: 'Greek series production flourished, especially until 1994, constituting the main feature in the structure of the programme of the private channels' (p. 442). As she explains, the changes brought to the table after the television sector of Greece passed from the state monopoly to the free market in the 1990s, were radical. Due to private channels' competition to attract viewers and therefore profits from advertisement, new strategies in the production of television series were introduced. In contrast to the previous decades, the private channels were intentionally kept apolitical in order to appear likable to as many viewers as possible (p. 442). As Papathanasopoulos (1997) adds: 'No one can claim that TV channels, abroad and in our country (Greece), do not uphold a certain political character. However, the undisguised alignments with political parties, as happened in the past, do not meet the private-economic criteria of the commercial television' (pp. 213-214).

According to Valoukos (2018), alongside the apolitical character of their series, private channels placed experienced executives in managerial positions who promoted and established a new generation of unknown young writers, giving them freedom to express their creativity and talents. The significance of 'script' for the creation of an efficient programme was recognised in practice, while scriptwriters' salaries raised. Therefore, as Valoukos (2018) puts it, private channels replaced the 'director/creator' tactic followed by the state-owned channels in the 1980s with that of the 'scriptwriter/creator' - a practice prominent in Greece in the decades that followed (p. 155).

In the early 1990s, due to the entertainment policy of the private channels and the technological development of the times - which offered greater creative possibilities to directors regarding special effects - adventure series were brought on Greek television. Some of them, for example *The 13rd Box (To 13^o Kivotio)/To 13^o Κιβώτιο* (ANTENNA, 1992-1993) and *The Anatomy of a Crime (I Anatomia enos Eglimatos)/H Ανατομία ενός Εγκλήματος* (ANTENNA, 1992-1995), constituted ambitious productions that reflected the progress of Greek televisual dramaturgy, especially concerning directing and scriptwriting. However, despite the attempts to enhance the genre, most of the filming of the adventure series did not

take place on location, thus their action scenes lacked authenticity. At the same time, their cost was gradually increased. During 1991-1992, a single episode of an adventure series cost around 4 to 6 million drachmas (\approx 10 to 16 thousand GBP), while few years later, in 1996-1997, its cost reached 14 to 18 million (\approx 37 to 48 thousand GBP). Due to the high cost and challenging technical means, this genre was soon abandoned, only to be replaced by another one, which required a much smaller budget, while attracted a very wide audience. That genre was Comedy (Koukoutsaki-Monnier, 2010, p. 443).

The low budget needed to produce comedy series (3 to 4 million drachmas per episode during 1991-1992, 6 to 8 million during 1996-1997), alongside their studio-based and multi-camera filming, offered a very quick pace of production - two to three days of filming per episode. Particularly popular to all target groups, 1990s Greek comedy series provided private channels with precious content for their prime-time zone - a zone of high importance, right after the evening news, gathering a large number of viewers. As Koukoutsaki-Monnier (2010) notes, as each comedy series was broadcast once a week, they encouraged the creation of 'habit' (loyal, consistent viewership). By structuring their narrative with self-contained stories within a wider storyline that developed throughout the life of a series, they helped viewers emotionally engage with the characters and comprehend the overall plot, while made it easy for newcomers to catch-up quickly. Thus, it is no surprise that both prominent private channels of the time, especially MEGA, greatly promoted this genre to the extent of producing six to eight comedy series per year (which mean, a new episode of a different weekly comedy series was broadcast every day at prime-time). In terms of their aesthetics, the comedy series of the era were mostly multi-camera, studio-based products, as already mentioned. However, in contrast to American comedy series, known as sitcoms (situation comedies), pre-recorded laugh tracks (canned laughter) were not embraced by the Greek audience and were quickly abandoned (pp. 444-445).

According to Petridis (2024), the absence of laugh tracks distanced Greek comedies from the American paradigm in television comedy-making, 'helping them find their own identity'. As he explains, the Greek comedy series did 'borrow' many of the characteristics of their American counterparts. Nevertheless, much of what was 'borrowed' was adapted to better fit the Greek television landscape. The similarities and dissimilarities between the Greek comedy series and the American, established during the first days of private Greek television, continue to define the Greek television comedy genre to this day. Starting on from the similarities, Petridis mentions that the narratives of both the American and Greek comedies revolve around 'situations' which gather the same bunch of characters into specific, repeating

locations, such as ‘the living room’, ‘the kitchen’, ‘the ‘workplace’. Limited within these ‘everyday’ locations, the stories of the episodes (are ‘forced’ to) focus on presenting ‘situations’ related to the domestic/personal and professional lives of the characters. Another characteristic of the Greek comedies ‘inspired’ by the American comedy format is the ‘stereotypically-built’ profiles of characters. As Petridis informs us, the characters are not represented ‘realistically’, as they are built according to character archetypes (the ‘clever’, the ‘idiot’, the ‘funny’, the ‘sexy’, etc.). This way, the personality of each character is easily distinguishable and often incompatible with the personalities of the other main characters of the series.

One of the biggest differences between the Greek and American comedies is that the episode duration of many Greek comedies is around 60 minutes (including the commercial breaks) instead of 30 minutes as it happens in the US. Thus, the longer episodes provide more ‘spare’ time for the main conflict of their narratives to be resolved, which gives Greek scriptwriters enough ‘space’ to unfold the episode stories through a three-act structure and not through the typical two-act structure of the American comedies. Until today, this tactic fulfils the requests of Greek channels for the incorporation of more than one commercial break during the one-hour slot of an episode, unlike the American comedies, which have only one commercial break in the middle of each episode (between act one and two). According to Petridis, changing the format of television comedy, by increasing the duration of episodes and telling three-act structured stories, ‘pushed the genre into new territories and gave a kind of artistic freedom to Greek creators to experiment’ (n.p.). One of their ‘experimentations’, which is still in use to date, is that many Greek comedies do not have story closure/resolution at the end of each episode. They do not just stretch a story over a couple of episodes, as sometime happens in American comedies, but dedicate a whole comedy series to tell one big story. As Petridis states, this is the reason we have two different types of Greek comedy series: ‘the episodic’¹, which tells an autonomous story in each episode, and ‘the serial’², which uses multiple episodes to tell a story. As Petridis highlights, despite this fundamental difference,

¹ Some ‘episodic’ type comedy series are: *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)/Οι Τρεις Χάριτες* (MEGA, 1990-1992), *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadekttoi)/Οι Απαράδεκτοι* (MEGA, 1991-1993), *The Penthouse (To Retire)/Το Πετιπέ* (MEGA, 1990-1992), *Just Us (Emeis ki Emeis)/Εμείς κι Εμείς* (MEGA, 1994-1998), *With Two Mothers (Me Dyo Mamades)/Με δύο Μαμάδες* (MEGA, 1998-1999), *Constantine’s and Helen’s (Konstantinou kai Elenis)/Κωνσταντίνου και Ελένης* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000), *The Bad Vizier (O Kakos Vezyris)/Ο Κακός Βεζύρης* (MEGA, 1997-1998).

² Some ‘serial’ type comedy series are: *Sinning Twice (To dis Eksamartein)/Το Δις Εξαμαρτείν* (MEGA, 1993-1996), *Dolce Vita* (MEGA, 1995-1997), *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)/Δύο Ξένοι* (MEGA, 1997-1999), *Crimes (Eglimata)/Εγκλήματα* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000).

both types of Greek comedy have the three-act episode structure in common - which constitutes the most prominent dissimilarity between the Greek and American television comedy-making.

Continuing with the historical overview, according to Valoukos (2018), comedy series were the major cause for battle between the first two private channels of the early 1990s (MEGA and ANTENNA). MEGA's first comedy series was *The Arbitrarities (Oi Afthairetoi)/Oi Avθαίρετοι* (MEGA, 1989-1990) directed by Nikos Koutelidakis. The series, placed in the microcosm of an apartment building, was inspired by the political conflict between the two major parties of the Greek parliament of the time (New Democracy and PASOK). The characters, living in neighbouring apartments, despite their great animosity decided to work together for a company (something that referred to the 1989's coalition of the two major parties in order to form a national unity government). However, their old habits were never put aside, resulting in catastrophe. MEGA's second comedy series was *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)/Oi Τρεις Χάριτες* (MEGA, 1990-1992), written by the young scriptwriting duo Michalis Reppas and Thanasis Papathanasiou. This 'legendary' series, as Valoukos (2018) calls it, depicted the everyday life of three sisters, named Charitou (plural: Charites), in their forties, sharing a house. For Valoukos (2018), apart from the famous casting (Anna Panayiotopoulou, Mina Adamaki and Nena Menti), the series owed its success to the inventive and imaginative situations, and 'fluently' comical dialogue, rarely seen on Greek television before. The following year, MEGA's *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)/Oi Απαράδεκτοι* (MEGA, 1991-1993) went on air. Alongside well-built characters, the scripts of the 29-year-old actress-writer, Dimitra Papadopoulou, initially rejected by ANTENNA, brought an ingenious, theatrical humour to Greek television (p. 156).

During the same period of time, the state-owned channels tried to 'imitate' the hit series produced by private channels, to no avail. Unable to surpass the competitive production pace and quality of the series of MEGA and ANTENNA, they focused mainly on producing documentaries, with noticeable success. In terms of their series-making, in the early 1990s, the state-owned channels produced soap-operas and drama series, which did not just receive low viewing rates but reconfirmed their unceasing tactic of assigning project to creators selected for meeting political criteria. According to Valoukos (2018), there had been some exceptions to that phenomenon as some creators' (Diagoras Chronopoulos, Errikos Andreou, Antonis Tempos, Vangelis Serntaris) series, under different conditions (better scheduling, advertisement, budget), could have equally competed with series produced by the private channels. Unfortunately, that was not the case, and their viewing rates were disappointing. Nonetheless, the only remarkable series by a state-owned channel (ERT1) in the early 1990s,

was *Black Chrysalis (Mavri Chrisallida)/Μαύρη Χρυσοαλλίδα* (ERT1, 1990-1991), written and performed by Tzeni Karezi, one of the most notable Greek actresses of the 20th century. The series was about a German woman of Greek origin, who worked as a secret agent during the German occupation of Greece (in the second world war). It was the actress's last role as she died a year later (pp. 160-161).

Throughout the second half of the 1990s, MEGA continued to produce hit comedy series, such as *Sinning Twice (To dis Eksamartein)/Το Δις Εξαμαρτείν* (MEGA, 1993-1996), written by the young duo Michalis Reppas and Thanasis Papathanasiou, the writers of *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)*, which preceded. According to Valoukos (2018), *Sinning Twice (To dis Eksamartein)* was a well-performed 'boulevard style' series, with well-built characters and 'curved' plot. Around the same period, another young writing duo, Alexandros Rigas and Lefteris Papapetrou, produced *Dolce Vita* (MEGA, 1995-1997), a remarkably successful series which depicted the secret love affair of a middle-aged mother with her daughter's fiancé (p. 171). The writing duo of *Dolce Vita* would eventually split, and Alexandros Rigas would join forces with Dimitris Apostolou to co-write the most successful romantic comedy in the history of Greek television, called *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)/Δύο Ξένοι* (MEGA, 1997-1999). This series portrayed the love affair between a sophisticated theatre director/drama tutor, and a blond uneducated morning-TV presenter. According to Valoukos (2018), the witty dialogues, the fast pace and the great casting of actors for both first and second roles made the series a classic, successfully re-broadcasted until today (p. 186).

Nevertheless, up until the mid-1990s, the comedy series produced by ANTENNA did not meet the same success as the ones produced by MEGA. The first hit in comedy-making for ANTENNA was the series *Those and the Others (Oi Men...kai Oi Den)/Οι Μεν... και Οι Δεν* (ANT1, 1993-1996) written by yet another duo, Charis Romas and Anna Chatzisoφία, mainly owing its success to the good chemistry amongst the actors (Valoukos, 2018, p. 156). Eventually, towards the end of the decade, ANTENNA managed to produce hit comedy series, which achieved success similar to the series of MEGA. For example, in 1998, ANTENNA produced one of the most prominent black comedies that Greek television ever presented. The series was called *Crimes (Eglimata)/Εγκλήματα* (ANT1, 1998-2000) and was written by one of the two writers of *Dolce Vita* (MEGA, 1995-1997), Lefteris Papapetrou. According to Valoukos, the series is characterised by intelligent punchlines and unexpected plots, featuring nine 'edgy' characters involved in intrigues, and often criminal plans. Finally, the most significant comedy series of the 1990s that ANTENNA produced was *Constantine's and Helen's (Konstantinou kai Elenis)/Κωνσταντίνου και Ελένης* (ANT1, 1998-2000). It was

written by the writing duo Charis Romas and Anna Chatzisofoia, who some years earlier had co-written *Those and the Others (Oi Men...kai Oi Den)* for ANTENNA and *The Bad Vizier (O Kakos Vezyris)/O Kakós Βεζύρης* (1997-1998) for MEGA. The premise of the series revolved around the cohabitation of two incompatible individuals: - a lecturer of Byzantine Studies, Constantine (Charis Romas), and an almost anarchist waitress, Helen (Eleni Rantou). As Valoukos (2018) explains, the series owed its success to the clash of the characters' very different personalities, to the 'staccato prose', and the creative 'boulevard' situations. It is worth mentioning that this series has broken the record for being the most re-broadcast series on Greek television ever, receiving very high viewing rates even to date (p. 187).

1.4 Sample Selection

As noticed in the previous section, in the 1990s there were a number of young writing duos who characterised the era with the comedy series they created. As already mentioned, this came as a result of placing experienced executives in managerial positions who promoted and established a new generation of unknown young writers, giving them freedom to express their creativity and talents (Valoukos, 2018, p.155). As Aitaki (2020) states in the Literature Review chapter (section 2.1), that new generation of writers delivered some of the most 'care-free, quirky and unforced hits' in the history of Greek television fiction (p. 226). Thus, the series selected for investigation are series created by that team of young writers, listed below. In most cases, two series of each writing duo are selected. The only exception comes due to the fact that Dimitra Papadopoulou wrote her second successful series in the 2000s (which is out of the time period this study investigates), therefore, an additional comedy series is selected written and directed by Giannis Dalianidis, who does not belong to that generation of young writers, as he constitutes one of the most prominent writers and cinema directors of the 1960s. The series selected are:

•*The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)/Οι Τρεις Χάριτες* (MEGA, 1990-1992) and •*Sinning Twice (To dis Eksamartein)/Το Δις Εξαμαρτείν* (MEGA, 1993-1996), written by Michalis Reppas and Thanasis Papathanasiou.

•*The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadekttoi)/Οι Απαράδεκτοι* (MEGA, 1991-1993), written by Dimitra Papadopoulou.

•*The Penthouse (To Retire)/Το Πετιπέ* (MEGA, 1990-1992), written by Giannis Dalianidis.

•*Just Us (Emeis ki Emeis)/Εμείς κι Εμείς* (MEGA, 1994-1998) and •*With Two Mothers (Me Dyo Mamades)/Με δύο Μαμάδες* (MEGA, 1998-1999), written by Panos Amarantidis and Spiros Metallinos.

•*Dolce Vita* (MEGA, 1995-1997), written by Alexandros Rigas and Lefteris Papapetrou, •*Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)/Δύο Ξένοι* (MEGA, 1997-1999), written by Alexandros Rigas and Dimitris Apostolou, and •*Crimes (Eglimata)/Εγκλήματα* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000), written by Lefteris Papapetrou.

•*Constantine's and Helen's (Konstantinou kai Elenis)/Κωνσταντίνου και Ελένης* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000) and •*The Bad Vizier (O Kakos Vezyris)/Ο Κακός Βεζύρης* (MEGA, 1997-1998), written by Charis Romas and Anna Chatzisofoia.

1.5 Personal Statement

Before embarking on our journey exploring the realms of Greek comedy, I would like to make a personal statement, giving you some context behind the reasons I chose to conduct this doctoral research on this specific subject. Firstly, I am a Greek national, born in 1994. I was raised in Greece until the age of 18, when I moved to Scotland to study filmmaking and screenwriting, which was my passion since the age of 12. Before commencing my PhD adventure, my engagement with the film and television fields was mostly 'practical' having taken part in international short-film festivals competing with short films I wrote and directed during my undergraduate and postgraduate years. Therefore, I chose to undertake this doctoral study without coming from an academic/theoretical background. There are many reasons behind this decision. An obvious one is that I have been watching Greek comedy series, especially the ones produced during the 1990s, throughout my childhood and teenage years. Yet the turning point, which made me realise how important these series were for me, was during the challenging times I left my country and moved to Scotland to start my undergraduate degree. It was then that I discovered the 'escapist' qualities that these series possessed. Over time I became a 'huge fan' and an active member of various fandom communities devoted to Greek comedy series. These communities started to expand during the early 2010s, thus around the same time period I moved to Scotland. Having first-hand experiences of the powerful bonds formed within these fandom communities, and taking into consideration the great influence that Greek comedy series have been having upon the culture of my country, I decided to self-fund this thesis and 'offer it as a present' to the fellow fans and to the realm of Greek comedy itself - making it a bit more 'visible' for the rest of the world to see.

CHAPTER 2:

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Aitaki, Papadimitriou and Tzioumakis (2021), even though the academic literature on Greek media studies has been developing since the 1980s in both Greek and English languages, its capability to inform research debates at an international level has remained limited. The small size of the country and its marginalized position in the global media economy has constituted the Greek media industry, and consequently its academic media discourse, practically invisible. An additional factor that contributed to Greece's lack of international recognition, in regard to media research, is the prevailing tendency of Greek scholars to focus their discourse on examining the relationship between Greek media and the state (p. 108). This tendency has resulted in the production of an extensive body of academic analysis on news and public affairs programmes, whose main endeavour was to investigate and question the relationship of Greek media with national politics and develop arguments about their influence on democratic processes. As Aitaki, Papadimitriou and Tzioumakis (2020) explain, this 'research tradition' to utilize politico-economical approaches in the conducting of Greek media discourse may have derived as a consequence of the historical link between Greek political parties and the broadcasting and press sectors (p. 17). Nevertheless, while Greek media research, at least until the late 2000s, perpetuated its engagement with topics, approaches and methodologies related to political economy, mass communication and social sciences, that was not the case for other countries. For example, in the US, media research has been expanding its interests (beyond the political perspective) to areas such as Entertainment Studies: examining film and television genres and production circumstances, - and Arts and Humanities: analysing issues such as 'race, gender, equality and inclusivity' as represented through the media industries (2020, p. 23; 2021, pp. 111, 113).

Since the 2010s, however, as Aitaki, Papadimitriou and Tzioumakis (2021) stress, for reasons pertaining both to the media landscape and to the academic environment in Greece, Greek media studies have started to embrace a wider, more pluralistic and interdisciplinary research direction. In the area of Greek Television studies, in particular, there has been a significant shift away from academic publications on politics, news and public affairs, with an increasing number of Greek scholars, based at universities both in Greece and abroad, engaging

with research that tends to investigate Greek television under the scopes of Entertainment, and Arts and Humanities. According to Aitaki, Papadimitriou and Tzioumakis, the newly produced studies, utilizing a variety of methodological frameworks, often focus on issues related to ‘production cultures’, such as ‘creative agency, format localization, casting, and scheduling’, and provide ‘empirically grounded descriptions of the production and dissemination’ of Greek television products (pp. 111-113). Many recent studies also combine production perspectives with textual analysis of Greek television fiction, usually incorporating interviews with television professionals and artists, allowing, this way, for several aspects of production routines, values and practices to become visible (2020, p. 25).

The purpose of this Literature Review chapter, therefore, is to examine and present the findings of recent studies dedicated to Greek television, which fall under the scopes of Entertainment, and Arts and Humanities. Due to the size parameters of a doctoral thesis, however, this review focuses almost entirely on studies related to Greek comedy series broadcasted by private Greek television channels. This way, the chapter is able to provide the appropriate space and necessary attention for this vibrant and rapidly developing field of scholarly engagement to be examined in a manner beneficial both for any reader who wishes to find information on up-to-date academic discourse on Greek comedy series concentrated in one place; and for the thesis itself, as, through this review, the themes of interest, which preoccupy current studies, are thoroughly pointed out, identifying findings, trends and gaps.

Informing the thesis with a review on recently published discourse on the subject is also beneficial, because - as observed in the following two subchapters - academic journal articles, book chapters and doctoral theses, produced during the last decade, have already initiated an extensive engagement in areas, in which the conference ‘50 years of Greek television’ (2016), Vamvakas (2018; 2019), Paschalidis (2018), Aitaki (2019), and Chairetis (2019) have highlighted that academic investigation needs to be undertaken (see section 1.1). Responding to these calls - as is the purpose of this thesis as well - some of the most recent publications tend to revolve around research areas similar to the ones chosen for this thesis. Namely, the literature reviewed below constitutes some of the first attempts to detect and analyse representations on the topics of ‘national identity’, ‘family’, ‘sexuality’ and ‘gender’ as portrayed in Greek comedy series. Apart from inspiration and guidance, the fact that the recently published literature engages with similar subject-matters gives the thesis the advantage to pinpoint and fill in gaps in the existing discourse, and expand on topics, which individual papers and book chapters do not have the space to fully dive into.

The first of the following subchapters is dedicated to presenting studies of scholars that incorporate discourse related to national identity as portrayed in Greek television fiction, usually during turbulent times such as the economic crisis of the 2010s. In recent years, one of the most prominent researchers on the subject is Georgia Aitaki, who in 2018 completed a doctoral thesis which focuses on the role of Greek television fiction in representing historically critical periods that ‘disrupt the normal pace of life’ (2018b, p. 1). Alongside her doctoral thesis, Aitaki has published an extensive number of articles and book chapters on the field of Greek television, which have significantly influenced and guided this study throughout its chapters. Aitaki’s publications (2017; 2018c; 2020), which this review chapter focuses on, emerge specifically from her doctoral thesis and revolve around topics such as: a) the commerciality of Greek television fiction and the potential political influences behind it, and b) the satirical portrayal of the ‘national-self’ in comedy series produced during crucial time periods. The review continues with presenting Stamou’s (2018) work on Greek national identity as portrayed in TV stand-up comedy. With her textual analysis, Stamou enriches the discussion on the topic, as she offers further examples on how ‘Greekness’ is represented - this time, in comparison with representations of the German identity. Additional work on representations of other, non-Greek nationalities is also presented in this subchapter by examining Karakasidis’ (2023) (mostly quantitative) analysis on the presence of foreign characters in Greek series.

The second subchapter presents recent studies on representations of ‘sexuality’, ‘gender’, and ‘family’ as portrayed in Greek television series. It begins with an overview of the findings of a doctoral thesis by Spyridon Chairetis (2020), who conducted a ‘queer reading’ on popular Greek comedy series examining ‘gender, (a)sexuality, family, domesticity, body, and age as a vehicle to create humour’ (p. iii). It continues with reviewing recently published papers by researchers such as Vamvakas, Kaklamanidou, Margaroni, Photiou, Charalambous, Maniou, Gioltzidou F. and Gioltzidou G., which focus on arguments concerning the ‘modernization’ of gender representations in Greek comedy series, as well as the battling relationship between tradition and modernity when it comes to portrayals of the institution of family.

2.1 Influences of political ideologies, satirization of the ‘Greek-self’, and representations of the ‘other’ in Greek television fiction

As mentioned in the previous section, in accordance with the current tendency and call for the conducting of more empirical and production studies on Greek television, one of Aitaki’s (2020) published articles, which constitutes part of her doctoral thesis, focuses on examining ‘widely accepted, yet often empirically obscure’ assumptions concerning the commerciality of

Greek television fiction, drawing answers from interviews she took of Greek television professionals (directors and screenwriters) (p. 220). In detail, by focusing on the first decade of private Greek television, the 1990s, her study makes use of the ‘exclusive’ information she gathered from the interviewees in order to investigate Greek television in relation to specific topics, which are a) the commercialization of broadcasting, b) potential influences of (political) ideologies on television fiction, and c) the multifaced nature of television entertainment.

On the first topic, the interviewed professionals confirmed to Aitaki that the commercialization of broadcasting, caused by the launch of privately owned television channels in the early 1990s, brought many positive changes. For example, the newly launched private channels, ‘appearing more open to taking risks’, gave opportunities to many young creators to gain working experience under conditions of creative freedom. Aitaki describes this tactic as a ‘win-win situation for the practitioners and the channels’, as aspiring artists/creators, such as Dimitra Papadopoulou and others (see chapter 1), had the chance to work and deliver some of the most ‘care-free, quirky and unforced hits’ of Greek television fiction, while, at the same time, the channels met the demands for content. Another positive change that occurred due the commercialization of broadcasting and improved the working routine of practitioners was the minimization of bureaucratic procedures (a negative aspect of the public Greek television channels of the time) and acceleration of production rhythms. Nevertheless, the interviewees reported to Aitaki that, as the 1990s proceeded, they were negatively impacted by the growing power of the advertisers and their increasing tendency for interventions, such as in casting choices and in the number of episodes, usually by ‘forcing’ production of additional material, such as Christmas specials (pp. 226-228). As Aitaki comments, advertisers’ increasing pressure and commercial expectations exemplify the prioritization of profit over any other function of television programming within the capitalist context of the newly-founded Greek private television (p. 235).

For the second topic concerning political ideologies and their influences on private Greek television (fiction), Aitaki notes that, unlike the pre-1990s era during which state-owned television (fiction) was aligned with specific political and governmental agendas, private television did not openly infiltrate specific political ideologies into its fiction productions. At the interviews she conducted with television professionals, such as director Dimitris Sofianopoulos and scriptwriter Elena Solomou, they denied intentional incorporation of any ideological system of (political) beliefs and values into their television creations/series, including any ‘particular ideological influences coming from political agents’. Instead, they characterised their ‘television fiction’ as being in ‘general alignment with dominant norms,

values and versions of the world', fulfilling advertisers' expectation that the series produced were not (politically) 'unpleasant' in order to attract as many viewers as possible (p. 230). However, Aitaki - quoting Gitlin (1994, p. 203) stating that, even though it is not the channels' purpose to 'indoctrinate the helpless masses', they generate or reproduce (political) ideology mostly indirectly and unintentionally - calls for further analyses on Greek television fiction, which would investigate whether and/or how 'particular world-views' have infiltrated Greek television fiction/series (2020, pp. 235-236).

Lastly, on the topic of television entertainment, the variety of viewpoints, expressed at her interviews by the television professionals, helped Aitaki 'unpack entertainment as a multidimensional logic, incorporating distraction, engagement, as well as discomfort' (p. 236). In detail, for scriptwriter Rena Rigga, the entertainment nature of television fiction is correlated with escapism and comforting functions (p. 233). On the other hand, director Manousos Manousakis believes in the utilization of television fiction as a vehicle to address 'broader unresolved social issues pertinent to Greek society' (p. 234). On a similar note, scriptwriter and actor Giorgos Kapoutzidis expresses that television fiction should 'respond to contemporary anxieties and to have a constructive impact on its viewers' (p. 234). Lastly, scriptwriter and director Eleni Mavili describes television as a medium of mass communication, and therefore she believes that television fiction needs to attract and engage with large audiences and not be used as a means for creators to exhibit their own 'personal repressed desires' or 'imaginary, existential or philosophical problems', as this might pose financial risk to the channels (p. 233).

Through the examination of the three topics in the above article, it becomes clear that the second topic, which questions whether influences of political ideologies have infiltrated into Greek entertainment programmes, is the one that necessitates further investigation. The professionals that Aitaki interviewed denied that they deliberately 'passed' political beliefs into their scriptwriting. However, as Gitlin and Aitaki express, ideologies may be indirectly, unnoticeably and unintentionally reproduced in television programmes. Therefore, Aitaki invites for further investigations on potential political ideologies influencing Greek television fiction, stating that 'there is evidence of political interference and ideologically inflected texts' (2020, p. 222). Thus, one of the subchapters of the Analysis chapter of this thesis is entirely dedicated to detecting and analysing moments, found within the narratives and dialogues of the comedy series selected, which portray elements related to political ideologies, influences and practices.

As mentioned in the previous section, representations of the Greek-self in comedy series produced during historically critical times is another subject matter which Aitaki

extensively engages with in her doctoral thesis. One of the published articles (2017) that emerged from her thesis examines the ways through which the Greek comedy series *The Arbitraries (Oi Afthairetoi)/Οι Αυθαίρετοι* (MEGA, 1989-1990) manages to both construct and satirise a specific version of the Greek-self, the ‘Neoellinas’ (literal translation: New Greek) - a term which attributes to modern Greeks a number of negative characteristics. The story of *The Arbitraries (Oi Afthairetoi)* revolves around two families who are bitter enemies, competing with each other on all levels. They reside on different floors of the same apartment building and, by coincidence, share the same last name, Chatzigiorgis. For Aitaki, what mainly characterizes the series is an anxiety as to how the Greek-self can coexist with the European-self. As she explains, in many of its episodes, the series references the major changes taking place in Greece, during the period it was produced, caused by the transition processes towards the upcoming establishment of the European single market in 1992. She argues that the series responds to this existential anxiety with a humorous portrayal of negative Greek traits and a self-disparaging rhetoric which ‘not only undercuts optimism about European integration, but also renders the national-self worthy of ridicule and lays the foundation for the notion of the ‘Neoellinas’ to evolve into a recognizable identity marker’ (pp. 5-6).

As Aitaki explains, in the series, ‘the national-self emerges as the butt of the joke through the satirical tool of hyperbole’ (exaggerating) and ‘by means of generalizing’. In the first case, the comedic effect derives from presenting the national-self as ‘knowing no limits’ when it comes to the intensity of the families’ antagonistic behaviour. In one of the scenes, which Aitaki references in order to exemplify the satirical tool of ‘hyperbole’ when presenting the national-self, we see one of the characters, Kostas (Christos Valavanidis), saying to his Spanish housemaid, Dolores (Isavella Vlasiadou): ‘My dear girl, if your neighbour buys a new car and parks it outside your front door to show off, what will you do? [...] Here in Greece, you go and buy a better car than him. And you go and park it in his bedroom if possible, understand?’

In regard to the second case, in which the national-self is satirised ‘by means of generalizing’, Aitaki highlights another part of the dialogue of the same scene, where Kostas states: ‘Here in Greece people are envious of each other, they hate each other. We live with passions, understand?’ As she points out, such a statement demonstrates that the blame for the problematic situation portrayed in the series (through the rivalry between neighbours) is ‘lifted’ from the individual and is bestowed upon Greek society in general. Hostility, therefore, as a characteristic of Greek identity is explained as ‘an inherent feature of everyday interactions in the country’ on a cultural level (pp. 8-9).

Besides analysing the national-self as portrayed through the antagonistic social interactions of the characters, Aitaki also examines portrayals of their professional lives, which she describes as ‘equally problematic’. In detail, she indicates that the characters show a general disregard for the law and tend to fixate on getting rich through fraudulent methods. ‘Illegal importation of goods, setting up of uncertified gambling sites, investment frauds and receiving bank loans with forged documents are only some of the activities the protagonists become involved with’. As she comments, such behaviour presents an image of a nation which constantly utilises deceitful and individualistic strategies to accomplish its ambitions and is indifferent towards ‘collaboration and collective achievement’ (p. 9).

Despite all the negative traits of the characters, the series does not end with them being transformed into better versions of themselves, having matured through the consequences of their actions. Instead, the series invites the audience to assume that a perpetuation of their negative aspects in their personalities and ways of living is ‘to be expected in the future’. Nevertheless, even though the characters are ‘never punished’ and transformed, they manage to become sympathetic to the audience. Our sympathy towards them, according to Aitaki, derives from the fact that, since there is no other alternative resolution to their problematic condition, all we can do is to ‘somehow accept it and laugh with it’. She concludes that *The Arbitraries (Oi Afthairetoi)* left a significant legacy in terms of what Greek television comedy identifies as funny. From then on, the term ‘Neollinas’ is considered a ‘staple’ in Greek comedy-making - a standard character-type ingredient utilised in many popular series, epitomizing familiar ‘Greek’ problematic behaviours but, at the same time, portraying them in a positive light as sympathetic and even genuinely amusing (pp. 12-13).

Another relevant published paper (2018c), part of Aitaki’s doctoral thesis, is dedicated to examining how the Eurozone crisis of the early 2010s is negotiated in Greek television fiction - a medium, which, as Aitaki states, can work as an ‘accommodator and shaper of *hot moments*’. Specifically, she investigates the ways in which the family comedy series *Back Home (Piso sto Spiti)/Πίσω στο Σπίτι* (MEGA, 2011-2013) offers cultural insights on Greek identity by associating the Eurozone crisis as a consequence of the flawed personality of the Greek-self (p. 958). Her analysis is conducted by close-examining the 34 episodes of the series, emphasizing on scenes that demonstrate a ‘heightened social reality relevance’, namely moments in which plots and conversations amongst characters reference current affairs of the Greek reality of the era (p. 962).

In detail, the premise of *Back Home (Piso sto Spiti)* revolves around a Greek family that deals with financial difficulties due to the general situation of the Greek economy of the

early 2010s, and their own bad management of personal economic matters. A significant part of the narrative has to do with the efforts of the family members to manage to pay back the money they borrowed from a German woman, Angela (Jenny Theona), who is the partner, and, later on, the wife of the family's second son Kostis (Thanasis Tsaltabasis). Angela, hoping that someday she will get her money back, is always eager to convince them to leave their problematic 'Greek habits' behind, and endorse the efficient 'German model' of living and thinking (pp. 962-963).

By examining conversations taken from various scenes, Aitaki summarises some of the characters' 'problematic' profiles, commenting that some of them show serious (while others show lighter) 'symptoms of defectiveness'. For example, Ilias (Thodoris Atheridis), the father of the family, is portrayed as 'an almost pathologically self-sabotaging' man, striving to find ways to pay back their debt but without sticking to the original agreements with Angela. Katerina (Maria Kavoyianni), the mother of the family, does not demonstrate heavy 'symptoms of pathology', as she is mostly portrayed as the voice of reason. Nevertheless, she has gotten an early retirement from her job at the bank, and that places her, as Aitaki puts it, 'within the array of wrong-doings that were highlighted as factors that led to Greece's downfall'. The family's daughter-in-law Anna (Anna Menenakou), wife of the first son Dimitris (Apostolis Totsikas) is presented as a naïve 'nouveau riche' character. Unable to realize the severity of their situation, she consumes and over-spends, embodying, therefore, 'the popular stereotype of Greeks living beyond their means' (pp. 963-964).

Aitaki suggests that if we consider *Back Home (Piso sto Spiti)* as depicting the crisis as a merely 'domestic problem', actualized through the characters' problematic personalities, it is insinuated that it must be them who have to bear the whole responsibility (for the crisis) and find a solution for their 'financial headaches'. If that is the case, then this piece of 'prime-time television fiction' portrays (once again) the national self as 'negatively attired', 'in line with popular stereotypes that were simultaneously circulating in other types of media', such (international) TV news and printed press. In other words, the series in question could be read as following in the footsteps of the mainstream information media, which depicted the crisis as being 'rooted in a certain nation and a certain culture'. Thus, as Aitaki puts it, the series contributes to the processes of 'culturalization' of the crisis, re-presenting 'a pathologized image of Greek society caused by inherent cultural flaws and national deficiencies'. By 'naturalizing' the crisis as a cultural problem, therefore, *Back Home (Piso sto Spiti)* excludes any alternative viewpoints on the subject, solely bestowing 'self-responsibility and blame' on

individuals without incorporating moment of systemic criticism and other types of external interventions (pp. 969-970).

Alongside Aitaki's research on Greek identity as portrayed in television fiction produced amid the economic crisis, Stamou's (2018) article on the TV stand-up comedy show *Burn the Script (Kapse to Senario)/Κάψε το Σενάριο* (MEGA, 2012-2013) offers additional moments of Greek identity representations by comparing, once again, Greek identity aspects with German [as was often the case with the German woman Angela in the series *Back Home (Piso sto Spiti)*]. In detail, Stamou analyses two short sketches, called 'Restaurant' and 'When Children Move out of their Parents' House', taken from the stand-up comedy show in question. As she explains, each of these two sketches is filmed twice: once with Greek characters in order to portray how Greeks behave in a restaurant, and once with German characters (played by the same Greek actors) in order to demonstrate the differences in the behaviour of Germans in a similar environment/situation. The same principles apply for the second sketch ('When Children Move out of their Parents' House') (p. 379).

In her analysis, besides the straightforward differences between 'Greekness' and 'Germanness' in language, music and other cultural elements (such as food), Stamou stresses that the sketches deliberately portray the mentalities of these two nations as complete opposites. By doing so, they attempt to 'define' the Greek and German identities by comparing 'Greekness' traits in juxtaposition with 'Germanness' traits, and vice versa. Examining the behaviour of the German characters, she summarizes that 'Germanness' connotes strictness, discipline, order, and, at the same time, lack of generosity, coldness with family members and friends, and insinuations of a Nazi past. On the other hand, 'Greekness', as represented in the sketches with the Greek characters, signifies good cuisine, directness, affection with family and friends, as well as greediness, thoughtlessness, disorder and 'pathological attachment to family' (p. 393).

In general terms, Stamou concludes that the depictions of Greeks and Germans in these sketches echo well established ideological preconceptions about 'Southern Europeanness' and 'Northern Europeanness'. She suggests that, since her analysis is limited to two sketches from a single show, 'it would be interesting' for researchers to conduct interpretative examinations of 'Greekness' as portrayed in a variety of Greek public discourses, such as films, television series and commercials, where 'ideologies pass more unnoticed' (pp. 393-394).

Lastly, another recent study related to the topic of national identity as portrayed through Greek television fiction comes from Karakasidis (2023), who investigates how immigrants - or, in his words, 'the other' - are represented in Greek television series produced between 1989

and 2019. In detail, out of the 143 Greek series of this timeframe which feature non-Greek characters, he examines the ones (50 in total) that incorporate the non-Greek characters as members of their regular cast. His analysis is divided into three main sections: a) the 1990s, b) the 2000s, and c) the 2010s. In each section, he presents extensive quantitative data related to various attributes of the non-Greek characters he studies, such as their country of origin, occupation, educational level, etc., followed by a summarised qualitative analysis on how they are portrayed in the series throughout the decades.

Starting with the first section, Karakasidis states that, in the 1990s, the regular characters portrayed to be of a non-Greek nationality are 17, appearing in 13 series, 11 of which are comedy series. Thus, out of the 251 series produced in Greece during the 1990s, only the 6.66% of them have a foreign character as member of the main cast. He informs us that 82.4% of them appear as legal immigrants coming to Greece from places such as: Northern and Western Europe (29.4%), the Filipins (23.5%), Africa (17.6%), Eastern Europe (11.8%), Spain/Latin America (5.9%), Albania (5.9%), and China (5.9%). 53% are portrayed as educated, while their occupations are: housemaids (53%), business employers/employees (11.8%), and priests and freelancers (5.9%) (pp. 329-330).

In terms of how the non-Greek characters are portrayed in the 1990s series, Karakasidis notes that negative references and comical incidents involving foreigners are common phenomena in the plots and dialogues, reflecting the 'general' attitude that Greeks held on the subject during that decade. He also mentions that non-Greek nationalities are often negatively characterized and parodied through 'misunderstandings and other humorous situations' even in series that do not include foreign characters in their cast. He claims that such moments are usually motivated by socio-political developments (e.g., immigration and military conflicts in the Balkans) of the era or are based purely on Greeks' stereotypical perceptions of other nationalities (p. 331).

In the 2000s, he points out that the regular characters portrayed to be of a non-Greek nationality are significantly increased to 38, appearing in 22 series, 14 of which are comedy series. So, out of the 274 series produced in Greece during the 2000s, the 13.9% of them have a foreign character as part of the main cast. 84.2% of them appear as legal immigrants coming to Greece from places such as: Turkey (39.5%), Albania (15.8%), Northern and Western Europe (13.2%), Africa (13.2%), former Eastern Bloc (10.5%), Middle East (5.3%), and Latin America (2.6%). 36.9% are portrayed as educated, while their professions are: employees (31.6%), students (13.2%), freelancers (7.9%), and fashion models (5.3%) (pp. 332-334).

For the 2000s era, Karakasidis stresses that the fact that more non-Greek characters managed to get leading roles in drama series led to fewer cliché portrayals of immigrants. However, that was not the case for the comedy series as they continued to perpetuate racist stereotypes - namely, presenting immigrants as impoverished and inclined to crime (p. 333).

Lastly, according to Karakasidis, in the 2010s, there are 27 regular characters portrayed to be of a non-Greek nationality, appearing in 15 series, 12 of which are comedy series. Hence, out of the 95 series produced in Greece during the 2010s, the 15.8% of them have a foreign character as part of the main cast. 81.5% of them appear as legal immigrants coming to Greece from places such as: Eastern Europe (25.9%), Turkey (18.5%), Africa (18.5%), Western Europe (11.1%), China (11.1%), the Middle East (7.4 %), Latin America (3.7%), and Canada (3.7%). 26% are portrayed as educated, while their occupations are: employees (29.6%), freelancers (22.2%), students (11%), and unemployed (14.8%) (pp. 337-338).

As Karakasidis comments, the third decade of private television (the 2010s) coincided with the outbreak of the economic crisis, and therefore the total number of series produced was dramatically decreased. Despite that, the significance of foreign characters in series increased, as they acquired more leading parts, which dealt with serious and sensitive sociocultural issues. He gives the examples of the series *Tamam* (literal translation: *Okay*)/*Ταμάμ* (ANTENNA, 2014-2017) and *Ethniki Ellados* (literal translation: *National team of Greece*)/*Εθνική Ελλάδα* (MEGA, 2015), which incorporate five and four foreign characters in leading roles respectively. In short, *Tamam*, adapted from the German series *Türkisch für Anfänger/Turkish for Beginners* (DAS ERSTE, 2006-2008), portrays the complexities, mostly religion-related, deriving from the marriage of a Turkish man and father of two children, Metin (Manolis Mavromatakis), with a Greek woman, also mother of two children, Myrto (Maria Lekaki). On the other hand, *Ethniki Ellados*, by merging the genres of comedy and drama, extensively depicts images of racism, xenophobia, social violence, disability, homosexuality, and domestic violence (p. 335).

Summarizing the main points of the literature on representations of Geek identity presented above, one of the first observations is that the majority of the existing studies strictly focus on examining 'Greekness' portrayed during periods of historical turbulences (such as the transitioning period towards entering the European single market in the early 1990s, and the economic crisis of the early 2010s). Secondly, the satirization of the Greek-self, through self-stereotyping, self-disparaging, hyperbole, generalizing, and comparisons with other nationalities, is considered, throughout the studies, as seemingly the most important tool utilized by Greek comedy creators for the generation of laughter. As a consequence, the

researchers who have examined these television texts could not avoid but focus their discourse on detecting and analysing mostly negative aspects of the Greek-self, portraying it as being in a constant state of ‘defectiveness’.

Nevertheless, an aspect of the Greek-self, which has barely been investigated to date, is its portrayal in moments in which its positive traits and value are presented as facing dangers of potential alterations or even ‘elimination’. In other words, while there has been substantial discourse on the ‘faultiness’ of the Greek-self, no attention has been given to analysing moments in comedy series which portray the Greek national identity and its positive attributes being in crisis. As observed in section 4.1.2 of the Analysis chapter, Aitaki (2015) argues that national identity crisis can occur during periods of geopolitical conflicts. Yet the examination of the episodes selected for this thesis has detected many moments in which characters bring up the issue in their conversations, expressing additional reasons (apart from geopolitical conflicts) as to why the Greek identity is in danger. An entire section (4.1.2) of the Analysis chapter, therefore, is dedicated to presenting and analysing scenes from the series, which portray the Greek identity being in crisis and the ‘measures’ taken by the characters to ‘fix’ this problem. Reviewing the characters’ reasons why crisis in national identity occurs, as well as how they attempt to ‘fix’ it, provides us with first-hand material, which 1) showcases the various ‘ideologies’ on the subject that circulated in Greece during the period the selected series were produced, and most importantly, 2) demonstrates how these ‘ideologies’ were creatively utilised by the scriptwriters to generate comedy.

Satire by ‘stereotyping’ the national-self is, of course, a very useful tool in comedy-making, as discussed throughout the discourse. Hence, the Analysis chapter incorporates two sections (4.1.3 and 4.1.4), one dedicated to how the Greeks ‘stereotype’ foreigners, and one on how Greeks ‘stereotype’ themselves. In the second case, the investigation on ‘stereotyping’ the Greek-self does not focus on detecting scenes in series, which portray ‘Greekness’ in association with periods of historical disturbances. Contrary to the existing literature, this thesis attempts to explore how the Greeks are ‘stereotyped’ when they ‘just’ experience their everyday life, undisturbed by the various politico-economic stimuli - namely, in ‘peaceful’ moments in which national identity is able to infiltrate more ‘unnoticed’. This way we can detect additional aspects and attributes of the Greek identity and its ‘actualization’ through everyday behaviour, hidden in the ‘mundane’. Besides, it is through the observation of the everyday life and behaviour that we can gain understandings about the culture of a nation. Taking into account the importance of culture in the shaping of the national-self, one of the sections (4.1.5) of the Analysis on Greek identity representations is fully focused on examining scenes in which

characters verbally reference cultural practices or physically perform cultural practices - for instance, through singing and dancing. Examining ‘culture’ and ‘cultural practises’ is an area which researchers who have been investigating national identity in Greek television fiction have so far ignored, despite the fact that creators/scriptwriters extensively incorporate ‘culture’ and ‘cultural practises’ when depicting ‘Greekness’ in their series-making.

2.2 Greek television fiction and the modernization of tradition in gender, sexuality, and family representations

The previous subchapter reviewed academic discourses related to representations of Greek national identity in Greek television fiction, pointing out the gaps in existing research which constitute the focus of the first part of the Analysis chapter of the thesis. The second part of the Analysis chapter investigates potential infiltrations of political ideologies into the Greek comedy series selected for the study, while the third part is dedicated to examining representations of the institution of family in the series in question, incorporating discourses on gender and sexuality. Therefore, the purpose of this second subchapter of the Literature Review is to present existing studies that focus on representations of gender, sexuality, and family as portrayed in Greek television fiction.

Similarly to the previous subchapter, this section also starts with a presentation of a recently completed doctoral thesis. The thesis examined here comes from Spyridon Chairetis (2020), who, through the prism of feminist and queer methodological frameworks, close-analyses in his discourse four popular Greek comedy series of the 1990s and 2000s: *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)/Οι Απαράδεκτοι* (MEGA, 1991-1993), *Dolce Vita* (MEGA, 1995-1997), *In the Nick of Time (Sto Para Pente)/Στο Παρά Πέντε* (MEGA, 2005-2007), and *Chara's Café (To Kafé Tis Charas)/Το Καφέ Της Χαράς* (ANTENNA, 2003-2006/2019-2021). As he explains, these series, utilizing in their narratives images of ‘gender, (a)sexuality, family, domesticity, body, and age’ in order to generate humour, have been dividing opinions and interpretations of viewers and critics since their first broadcast. While for some audiences these series are considered ‘conservative, homophobic, misogynist, or nothing but funny’, Chairetis manages to trace alternative access points into their narratives and give to some their characters the opportunity to be viewed in new, ‘resistant’ and ‘agentic’ ways (p. 12).

For example, he argues that, when the series *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)* first aired, the character Giannis (Giannis Bezos) may have been decoded as an always single and sexually inactive gay man, with his life and attitude significantly differing from the life and attitude of the rest of the male characters of the series. However, this may not have been the

case if Giannis' profile was examined according to more contemporary discourses of queerness representations. Similarly, his straight flatmate Vlassis (Vlassis Bonatsos), whose heterosexuality and attraction to women seemed, at first glance, unquestionable, may have indirectly exhibited heteroflexible traits, experimented with identities and flirted with 'non-hegemonic gender scripts' (p. 245).

For the series *In the Nick of Time (Sto Para Pente)*, Chairetis points out that some of its protagonists perform roles and behaviours that 'challenge' both their gender and the comedy genre. He claims that this series offers representations of characters who refrain from the social conventions of 'proper' femininity and masculinity, which 'require' of (in this case, seemingly straight) young individuals to have active sexual lives, and present and 'perform their bodies' in ways considered attractive by dominant social norms. As he puts it, the 'gender-bending' moments in this series, if examined through a queer methodological approach, indicate that the comedy genre, when surpassing its conventions, can constitute 'a queer space for harbouring ostensibly heterosexual characters who live inside the queer closet' (pp. 247-248).

Chairetis underlines that the series he examined do contain 'scenes of patriarchal domination', but these scenes become continuously contested through episodes of 'surprising' scripts and narratives that are 'anything but monolithic and linear'. In short, all these series provide a wide range of character profiles, such as 'widows, queers, spinsters, asexual, infertile, celibate, and fools', who, with their alternativeness, eccentricity and 'ambivalent' relation to societal norms, 'often contest heteronormative order and dominant ways of living'. Nevertheless, he notes that, besides the showcasing of 'resistance' (performed through these characters), there are, at times, 'narrow articulations of feminism and queerness', which 'do not upset the very foundations of patriarchy'. For example, while two of the 'black sheep' female characters in *Chara's Café (To Kafe Tis Charas)*, Chara (Renia Louizidou) and her daughter Valia (Efi Rassia), escape patriarchal oppression by leaving the village where the series takes place, choosing for a new though uncertain future, this might not be the case for Christina (Anna Panagiotopoulou) in the series *Dolce Vita*. In a nutshell, the premise of *Dolce Vita* revolves around a middle-aged widow, Christina, who, despite her conservative personality, gets into a secret love affair with her daughter's boyfriend, 25-year-old Antonis (Thanassis Efthimiadis). Consequently, throughout its narrative, the series exemplifies Christina's 'resistance' against 'the normalizing forces exerted upon her as an aging female and widow' for being in such a transgressive relationship. In the last scene of the last episode, however, as her love story with Antonis has come to an end, she meets another handsome young man. Even though the effortless with which she engages with him during their first

conversation demonstrates a breaking-free from ageist stereotypes (with which she dealt in the past) and opens up a new era of gender and sexual emancipation for her, she wants to make sure that this new man is not anyhow related to her daughter. According to Chairetis, this worry of hers indicates that ‘her sexual transgression may be stigmatized from an internalized fear to not fail again as a mother’ (pp. 245-247).

He suggests that instead of considering moments like the above as problematic and sabotaging of the queer potential of the series examined, it will be beneficial to investigate the ways in which narratives of ‘widowhood, domestic womanhood, and male queerness are both enabling and restraining simultaneously’. He stresses that ‘the small gaps and petty victories’ within the series provide us with unexpected opportunities to study the portrayal of feminist, postfeminist, and queer discourses in the Greek television of the 1990s and 2000s, and review how the depiction of characters who ‘lived’ during a different spatiotemporal context can be understood and read today. Altogether, he claims that these series, which ‘have been known as funny, yet frivolous and simplistic, can become sites for reappropriation in the name of queer experience and disclose different meanings and concerns’ (p. 247).

Besides his doctoral thesis, Chairetis has conducted additional research on Greek comedy series in relation to LGBT representations. For example, in a subsequent study (2021), in order to help construct an archive of lesbian presence on Greek television, he examines a different set of comedy series of the same era [*Crimes (Eglimata)/Εγκλήματα* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000), *Constantine’s and Helen’s (Konstantinou kai Elenis)/Κωνσταντίνου και Ελένης* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000), *The Stables of Erieta Zaimi (Oi Stavloi tis Erietas Zaimi)/ Οι Στάβλοι της Εριέτας Ζαϊμη* (ANTENNA, 2002-2004), and *Talk Dirty to Me (Mila Mou Vromika)/Μίλα Μου Βρώμικα* (MEGA, 2009-2010)], which feature lesbian characters (as guest appearances or regular cast), and maps out prevailing ideologies and imagery that arise from the ‘lesbian moments’ portrayed (pp. 2-3). By exploring the ‘dialectic’ of these moments with the heteronormative rules and conventions of television, he draws the conclusion that the comedy series listed above ‘predominantly reify heteronormativity in regard to the representation of lesbian characters and minimize the queer potentialities of these characters’ (p. 8).

In detail, in one of the scenes of episode 18 in the series *Crimes (Eglimata)*, an unnamed lesbian character (played by Vicky Stavropoulou) makes a short appearance behaving in a way which, according to Chairetis, ‘emulates the male gender role of the popular imagination’. Namely, she constitutes a dressed-in-black ‘stereotypical butch lesbian’, who is ‘violently animated’ with exaggerated and aggressive mannerisms. As he explains, this appearance, apart

from serving as a source of laughter, ‘educates’ the audience about ‘a specific type of masculine lesbianism associated with gender inversion’ (pp. 4-5).

In the case of *Constantine’s and Helen’s* (*Konstantinou kai Elenis*), the premise of episode 42 revolves around a lesbian guest character, Marina (Dimitra Papadima), whose sexuality is only revealed towards the end. Thus, throughout the episode, Marina ‘passes’ as a straight woman admired for her looks and personality, which make other women jealous and ‘upset’ the men. When she announces, however, that she isn’t single, everyone assumes that she has a male partner. For Chairetis, such an assumption demonstrates ‘the centrality of the heterosexual rule’ in people’s way of thinking. In fact, in the scene in which Marina’s female partner makes her appearance, the ‘comedic effect’ is generated by focusing mainly on the male characters’ reaction to the knowledge of lesbianism, while, at the same time, the lesbian couple becomes peripheral to the camera and, therefore, to the audience. This way, as Chairetis puts it, the series renders ‘lesbianism palpable only through the eyes of confused heterosexual men who struggle with their own reactions and feelings of uneasiness’ (pp. 5-6).

As opposed to the previous two examples, the series *The Stables of Erieta Zaimi* (*Oi Stavloi tis Erietas Zaimi*), which takes place within the walls of a female prison, has a lesbian character, Pigi (Vicky Protogeraki), as part of its main cast. As Chairetis describes, it takes until episode 10 for Pigi to start expressing desire and making her sexuality visible to the other prisoners. Her multiple endeavours, however, to achieve intimacy with any other female prisoner are all unsuccessful. Her confinement within the heterosexual contexts of prison leads to the portrayal of a version of lesbianism that is ‘harmless’ yet ‘policed’ by the rest of the characters when necessary. Thus, Pigi is presented as a lesbian character trapped within a heterosexual community, deprived of her ‘queer possibilities’ and networking (p. 6).

Lastly, in episode 20 of the series *Talk Dirty to Me* (*Mila Mou Vromika*), a female main character, Rita (Klelia Renesi), who is seemingly straight, has a romantic encounter with a female colleague, Teri (Vasiliki Kakosaïou). According to Rita, this comes as a result of the fact that she has gotten tired of men and wants to turn a new page in her life. Nevertheless, towards the end of the series, we find the two women to have entered into heterosexual relationships. For Chairetis, such a finale makes lesbianism seem like a ‘rest stop’, a sexuality that can be consumed and then discarded, a sexual adventure that ‘prepares women for their future relationships with men’. He also argues that Rita and Teri’s case might be the outcome of queerbaiting - strategy, according to which, creators attempt to gain the attention of queer viewers by showcasing queer ‘moments’ and elements, and then shake them off (pp. 6-7).

As far as lesbian representation is concerned, therefore, according to Chairetis, even though Greek comedy series of the 1990s and 2000s seem eager to engage with provocative themes and transgressive characters, they end up (re)producing social stereotypes regarding lesbian identity, demonstrate ‘queerbaiting’ elements, and downplay transgressive features and ‘possibilities’ of the lesbian characters, in order to become more palatable to the general audience.

Nevertheless, this does not seem to be case when it comes to representations of heterosexual women and their sexual life in Greek comedy series. For instance, Kaklamanidou (2017) argues that the series *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)/Οι Τρεις Χάριτες* (MEGA, 1990-1992), created by the novice scriptwriting duo Michalis Reppas and Thanasis Papathanasiou, alongside its strong cast and intelligent script, portrays progressive gender politics regarding female representation (pp. 139-140). Its progressiveness, however, is unrelated to American paradigms of the era, as, when interviewing Michalis Reppas, Kaklamanidou found out that ‘before the show he didn’t even own a television set and the only television person he knew and admired was Lucille Ball’. Instead, the dynamic portrayal of the three female protagonists of the series is influenced by the political shifts that occurred in Greece during the 1980s implemented by the socialist party PASOK. As she explains, the sociopolitical changes, such as the legalization of civil marriage, the simplification of the process for obtaining a divorce, abolition of the dowry system and the decriminalization of adultery, started altering the traditional views on gender equality (p. 148).

In detail, *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)* depicts the cohabitation of three sisters, Olga (Anna Panagiotopoulou), Maria (Nena Menti) and Irimi (Mina Adamaki) - all in their early to mid-forties. As Kaklamanidou puts it, ‘thematically, the show foregrounds everyday life (portrayals) and does not insist on the three sisters’ need of a man to find happiness and/or fulfilment’, as only 5 out of the 22 episodes of the first season revolve around the sisters’ love life. She points out that such a narrative choice contradicts US comedy series of the era, such as *The Golden Girls* (NBC, 1985-1992) and *Designing Women* (CBS, 1986-1993), in which finding the right man (or the right man ‘for now’) is the primary narrative objective at least for one of the female protagonists (in most episodes). Instead, the three sisters ‘seem quite content living their life without men’ (p. 148).

As an example on this matter, Kaklamanidou mentions an incident that takes place at the end of episode 6, when Olga and Maria discover that the two men they have been dating for a few days were dishonest about their ‘single status’ - unfortunate news, which bring their love affairs to an end. What demonstrates the women’s ‘progressiveness’ on this subject is their

reaction to the news, as they do not seem to consider this unlucky encounter as a decisive event. Neither do they try to dissect the reasons why the two men lied to them - as is often the case in the American series *Sex and the City* (HBO, 1998-2004), which tends to scrutinize the failed love affairs of its female protagonists. As Kaklamanidou explains, in *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)*, the writers deliberately opted for a more empowering mindset on such issues, having the sisters 'firmly acknowledge the men's hypocrisy and discard them without having to even momentarily be upset, thus commenting on their autonomy and strength' (p. 149).

Additional examples that exemplify, according to Kaklamanidou, moments of female empowerment can be found in episodes 7 and 8, in which Maria has an intense relationship with Stavros (Andreas Andreopoulos), a man in his early twenties. Kaklamanidou highlights that, at her interview with the writer Repas, he mentioned that he and his writing partner Papathanasiou struggled to come up with a way to terminate Maria's relationship, as they were strongly against treating it as 'another failed romance because the woman was older than the man'. Ultimately, they decided that the affair will end due to an external factor, namely Stavros' obligation to fulfil his military duties (an obligation still present in Greece). They also showed Maria, at the finale of episode 8, going out on a new date with another younger man 'underlining (once more) that female age is not a factor in a sexual relationship' (pp. 149-150).

Another article that examines gender representations in sexual/romantic relationships comes from Photiou, Charalambous and Maniou (2019) who conducted a study on the Greek and the Greek-Cypriot adaptations of the Canadian comedy series *Un Gars, Une Fille/A Guy, A Girl* (1997-2003, Radio-Canada), which focuses entirely on depicting the everyday life and conflicts of one heterosexual couple. The Greek version of the show, named *I Love You, You Love Me (S' Agapo, M' Agapas)/Σ' Αγαπώ, Μ' Αγαπάς* (2000-2002, MEGA), was adapted by Dimitra Papadopoulou, scriptwriter (and actress) of *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)*. Alongside adapting the Canadian script to 'match' the 'Greek reality', she played the female protagonist, Dimitra, accompanied by the actor Thodoris Atheridis, who played the male counterpart, Thodoris. The Greek-Cypriot version, adapted by Christina Artemiou, Nikolas Kouroumtzis and Tasos Tryfonos, is called *Me and You (Ego Kai Esi)/ Εγώ και Εσύ* (2010-2013, RIK 1) and the couple, Photis and Danae, is played by the actors Photis Georgidis and Danae Christou. In their study of these two versions of the show, Photiou, Charalambous and Maniou examine how gender stereotypes are portrayed in both adaptations, how the portrayal of gender stereotypes differs between the adaptations, and how gender as presented in the series reflects the cultural 'realities' in the Greek-Cypriot and Greek societies. Interviews with

production personnel from the Greek-Cypriot adaptation were also conducted to gain understandings into the creative process and cultural influences (p. 91).

In detail, the analysis of the shows focuses on investigating representations on two topics (frames): on moments that portray how the couples deal with finances, and on moments that offer an insight into the characters' beliefs concerning emotional and social settling down, namely marriage, family and childbearing. In regard to the first topic (financial management), in both adaptations, the male characters are depicted as frugal and cautious with money, while the female characters are portrayed as extravagant spenders. As Photiou, Charalambous and Maniou explain, this dichotomy utilizes traditional gender stereotypes, according to which excessive spending is considered a feminine trait and frugality a male one, in order to generate humour through the depiction of male-female conflicts, or else 'the battle of the sexes'. Nevertheless, they identify a significant difference between the Greek male character and the Greek-Cypriot on the issue of money management. On the one hand, Photis, in the Greek-Cypriot version, is depicted as excessively stingy, embodying the cultural stereotype of a 'hillbilly', while the Greek character, Thodoris, is still portrayed as frugal yet through the 'gendered stereotype' of the wise male financial manager. The creators of the Greek-Cypriot version verified to Photiou, Charalambous and Maniou that 'this was by design', aiming to make Photis appear 'boorish' in order to satirize the stereotypical Greek-Cypriot man (p. 99).

On the second topic (views on marriage and family), both female characters express a strong desire to settle down, looking forward to what they perceive to be the next 'natural' step in their relationships. On the other hand, the male characters seem content to just cohabit with their partners, reflecting the stereotype of men being reluctant to commit to marriage. Despite the similarities between the male characters on the subject, Photiou, Charalambous and Maniou point out that, in the Greek-Cypriot version of the series, Photis' reluctance to settle down has to do with his undecidedness to marry Danae, while, in the Greek version, Thodoris' hesitance derives from his unwillingness to become a father. For the female characters, despite their common ground, there are dissimilarities to how they perceive settling down, as well. For Danae, in the Greek-Cypriot version, marriage is important and entails emotional stability, whereas for Dimitra, in the Greek version, settling down means becoming a mother - which constitutes her main worry throughout the series. Interestingly, Dimitra does not bring up the subject of marriage as a prerequisite to have a child. She seemingly conveys that it is considered acceptable in Greece to form a family out of marriage, which, according to Photiou, Charalambous and Maniou, illustrates a possible cultural divergence between the Greek and the Greek-Cypriot societies (pp. 106-107).

The study concludes that both adaptations exploit ‘the battle of the sexes’ trope for comedic effect, drawing from and reinforcing traditional gender stereotypes. The Greek-Cypriot version amplifies these stereotypes to create more ‘caustic humour’, while the Greek version maintains a more balanced portrayal. Overall, as Photiou, Charalambous and Maniou suggest, while the adaptations share similarities in their portrayal of gender stereotypes, which seem deeply rooted in the cultural contexts of both communities, they also exhibit significant differences that reflect their unique cultural backgrounds (p. 108).

Another study on Greek television fiction with substantial focus on representations of romantic relationships and family formations comes from Vamvakas’ (2019) thematically summarised cultural analysis on series produced from 1993 to 2018 by the two most prominent private Greek channel, MEGA and ANTENNA. Through the examination of the 30 most successful series, selected according to their viewing rates, one of Vamvakas’ first observations is that the series often blend traditional and modern elements, reflecting the constant negotiation between these two aspects in contemporary Greek society. He also notices that four specific frames of interest, or else four thematic categories, persistently arise in the narratives of the series. He names these thematic categories as: a) paradoxical love, b) multifunctional friendship, c) old and new family crisis, and d) conflicts and overlaps between city and countryside life (urban vs rural life) (p. 23).

He explains that the series that thematically belong to the first category, ‘paradoxical love’, revolve around stories which aim to bridge social and cultural differences. In other words, they portray the love affair of two people who belong to ‘two different worlds’. He notices that, in drama series, the differences between the lovers are related to class, religion, national characteristics, even health condition, while in comedy series, the differences in the lovers’ profiles are mainly ‘aesthetic’. Two of the comedy series he offers as examples are: *Love Sorry* (MEGA, 1994-1995) and *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)/Δύο Ξένοι* (MEGA, 1997-1999). The first one portrays the love affair between a disciplined doctor, Lili (Konstantina Michail), and a laid-back plumber, Sakis (Tasos Chalkias); and the second one, the stormy love between a bubbly television star, Marina (Evelina Papoulia), and a ‘grave’ theatre teacher/director, Konstantinos (Nikos Seryanopoulos) (pp. 24-25).

Vamvakas points out that one of the peculiarities of Greek television fiction is that the series which fall into the second category, ‘multifunctional friendship’, such as *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)/Οι Απαράδεκτοι* (MEGA, 1991-1993) and *Even Married Men Have Soul (Kai oi Pantremenoi Echoun Psychi)/Και οι Παντρεμένοι Έχουν Ψυχή* (ANTENNA, 1997-2000), depict friendship as a ‘long-lasting, almost perpetual matter’, even transforming

it into ‘brotherly’ or ‘sisterly’ relationships. An exception to this trend is the series *In the Nick of Time (Sto Para Pente)/Στο Παρά Πέντε* (MEGA, 2005-2007), in which friendship operates in a ‘revealing and liberating way between unfamiliar and diverse (in cultural and generational terms) persons’, as the formation of their relationship is a matter of the present and not of the past (and the traumas it carries) (pp. 26-27).

On the third category, ‘family crisis’, Vamvakas notes that over the last three decades, series, especially comedies, which portray, or reference, non-nuclear family models have become more frequent. For example, the series *Hi Rock* (MEGA, 1992-1994), *Happy Together (Eftihismenoi Mazi)/Ευτυχισμένοι Μαζί* (MEGA, 2007-2009), and *All the Best (I Ora i Kali)/H Ώρα η Καλή* (MEGA, 2004-2007) depict relationships between divorced parents and their children, as well as complexities created by the introduction of modernized family roles and obligations, associated with ‘less patriarchal connotations’. Therefore, the dynamics that derive from the relationship between tradition (i.e., traditional family paradigms and values) and modernity (i.e. modernized ideologies, for example, on parental roles) seem to highly influence comedy series that focus on the family theme (p. 27).

Lastly, the fourth category, ‘urban vs rural life’, is exemplified in comedy series such as *Chara’s Café (To Kafe Tis Charas)/Το Καφέ Της Χαράς* (ANTENNA, 2003-2006/2019-2021) and *Clinical Case (Kliniki Periptosi)/Κλινική Περίπτωση* (MEGA, 2011-2012), which portray the challenges - and the comedic moments these challenges generate - caused by the clash between modern urbanites and traditional rural communities. An interesting feature of *Chara’s Café (To Kafe Tis Charas)*, in particular, is that the old Greek cinema motif of the countryman, who relocates to the city, is reversed in this series. Namely, *Chara’s Café (To Kafe Tis Charas)* chronicles that life of a divorced woman, Chara (Renia Louizidou), that used to live in a city but has decided to move to a village in the countryside, along with her little daughter, Valia (Efi Rassia). The basic premise of the series revolves around the struggles of Chara and Valia in their attempts to get accepted by the people of the village they just moved to - people, who are ‘probably unrealistically depicted as being far away from modern behavioural and moral evolution’. Thus, similarly to the ‘family crisis’ category, the ‘urban vs rural life’ category is also profoundly influenced, even defined, by the battle between tradition and modernization (p. 28).

Vamvakas concludes that traditional patterns of identification are always present in Greek series, serving as a backdrop for their modern narratives. Therefore, what is interesting is not so much the insistence of tradition in Greek series, but the existence of moments in which the depiction of the past prevails over and destabilizes modernized beliefs and roles. Especially

in the comedy genre, he points out that it is the topic of ‘family’ that the satirical confrontation of the normative and legitimation aspect of tradition is mainly linked to. He notes, nevertheless, that ‘there is a lot of work to be done in order to confirm the existence of such connection’, which will entail the examination of prominent Greek comedy series of the last 30 years (pp. 34-35).

One of the earliest overviews on family representations in Greek series comes from Margaroni (2017), who examines fifteen popular comedy series³ of private Greek television in relation to sociocultural characteristics and changing perceptions met within Greek society, especially during the economic crisis of the 2010s. In particular, Margaroni lists in her article the different forms of families depicted in her sample of series, the educational level, and occupations of the family members portrayed. She also introduces brief discourses on how kinship relations are represented, as well as attitudes towards homosexuality, unmarried and/or childless family formations, and extramarital and non-traditional affairs (p. 233).

In detail, Margaroni points out that ‘family’ constitutes a central theme in Greek comedy series, with the most-depicted family household being ‘the extended type’ - which often consists of three generations of family members living under the same roof, children from previous marriages, or even married adult children who bring their spouses to live in their parents household. She notes, however, that in the more recent series, cohabitation of many generations in the same household is a consequence of the economic crisis, representing the practical difficulties with which Greek families had to deal during the 2010s. In terms of the

³ Based on their viewing rates, the comedy series chosen by Margaroni for her study are: *Dolce Vita* (MEGA, 1995-1997), *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)/Δύο Ξένοι* (MEGA, 1997-1999), *Constantine’s and Helen’s (Konstantinou kai Elenis)/Κωνσταντίνου και Ελένης* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000), *Crimes (Eglimata)/Εγκλήματα* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000), *Ten Minute Sermon (Deka Lepta Kirygma)/Δέκα Λεπτά Κήρυγμα* (MEGA, 2000-2003), *You’re My Mate (Eisai To Tairi Mou)/Είσαι Το Ταίρι Μου* (MEGA, 2001-2002), *Strictly in the Family (Akros Oikogeneiakon)/Άκρως Οικογενειακόν* (ANTENNA, 2001-2003), *Born Lucky (Savvatogennimenes)/Σαββατογεννημένες* (MEGA, 2003-2004), *In the Nick of Time (Sto Para Pente)/Στο Παρά Πέντε* (MEGA, 2005-2007), *Chara’s Café (To Kafé Tis Charas)/Το Καφέ Της Χαράς* (ANTENNA, 2003-2006/2019-2021), *Happy Together (Eftihismenoi Mazi)/Ευτυχισμένοι Μαζί* (MEGA, 2007-2009), *My Lovely Neighbours (Latremenoi mou Geitones)/Λατρεμένοι μου Γείτονες* (MEGA, 2007-2009), *Fifty-Fifty (Peninta-Peninta)/Πενήντα-Πενήντα* (MEGA, 2005-2007/2010-2011), *The Family Damages (I Oikogeneia Vlaptei)/Η Οικογένεια Βλάπτει* (MEGA, 2009-2010), and *Don’t Start Nagging (Min Archizeis Ti Mourmoura)/Μην Αρχίζεις Τη Μουρμούρα* (ALPHA, 2013-2024).

educational and professional status depicted, there is an excessive number of characters who have well-paid, high-status occupations. For Margaroni, this comes in contrast to the reality of Greek society, constituting the series less realistic. When it comes to working female family members, the stereotype which requires them to simultaneously be ‘good’ wives, housekeepers and mothers is broadly reproduced. Lastly, she stresses that the series in question permeate negative stereotypes about homosexual, unmarried and/or childless characters, while any references to disabled people and their role in the family are almost entirely absent. Therefore, she states that, despite some exceptions, these series reproduce social stereotypes and ridicule marginalised groups of Greek society. She concludes her study highlighting that the family in Greek comedy series is portrayed as a network of protection for its members - a network, which can sometimes be redemptive, sometimes oppressive, and sometimes destructive (pp. 254-257).

Another more recent case study on representations of the Greek family, conducted by Gioltzidou F. and Gioltzidou G. (2023), offers a close analysis on conventional and unconventional characteristics observed within the family units portrayed in three popular comedy series - one from the 1990s: *Dolce Vita* (MEGA, 1995-1997), one from the 2000s: *Happy Together (Eftihismenoi Mazi)/Ευτυχισμένοι Μαζί* (MEGA, 2007-2009) adapted from the Spanish series *Los Serrano* (TELECINCO, 2003-2008), and one from the 2010s: *Your Kin (To Soi Sou)/Το Σόι Σου* (ALPHA, 2014-2019) adapted from the Israeli series *Savri Maranan/סברי מרנן* (CHANNEL 2; KESHET 12, 2011-present) (p. 285).

As Gioltzidou F. and Gioltzidou G. describe, the series that comes from the 1990s, *Dolce Vita*, revolves around the everyday struggles caused by the ‘forbidden’ love affair between Christina (Anna Panagiotopoulou) and her daughter’s, Dorita (Katerina Ziogou), boyfriend Antonis (Thanassis Efthimiadis). The family unit depicted in this series, at least initially, consists of three women (and a female housemaid) of three different generations living together: a widowed elderly woman, Olga (Maria Foka), a middle-aged woman, Christina, who is the widow of Olga’s son, and Dorita, Christina’s daughter, who is in her early 20s. According to Gioltzidou F. and Gioltzidou G., *Dolce Vita* satirizes the matriarch family model, extensively ‘celebrated’ in the series, through the matriarch-type character Olga, a dynamic leader of the household with very conservative mindset, eager to sustain her control over all intrafamilial and extrafamilial matters despite her old age. What is also satirized is the ‘decency’ and conservatism that Olga (and society by extension) forces upon Christina concerning how she should think and behave as a widowed, middle-aged, middle-class woman. The satire on this matter becomes even more intense, as Christina’s best friend, Sasa (Katiana Balanika), is the

exact opposite of Christina - namely, she is unconservative, 'flamboyant' and of 'weak moral principles' (p. 295). Yet even though the series does not satirize the role of men within a family, the male characters that manage to enter the family as (potential) grooms for Dorita - Antonis in the beginning of the series, and Charis (Christoforos Papakaliatis) later on, who does marry Dorita and becomes a permanent male member of the family - are portrayed as 'deconstructed' versions of the traditional husband/father figure (p. 291).

The family unit portrayed in the 2000s series *Happy Together (Eftihismenoi Mazi)* is formed by the marriage of Dionisis (Giannis Bezos), a widower and father of two sons, with a divorced woman and mother of two daughters, Eleni (Katerina Lehou). According to Gioltzidou F. and Gioltzidou G., satire, in this series, is generated by the portrayal of the indirect conflicts between 'modernized parenthood' and the ineffective attempts of Dionisis to apply 'conventional family rules' to an 'unconventional' family formation. The 'unconventionality' of the family is also understood through the portrayal of 'non-traditional' gender-related characteristics. On the one hand, the male members of the family are mostly portrayed as spontaneous and emotional. On the other, the female members are presented as (more) intelligent, dynamic and decisive (than the male ones), while, at the same time, pretending to maintain an outwardly humble attitude in order not to 'offend' and bring down the 'men' of the family (p. 295).

Lastly, the 2010s series *Your Kin (To Soi Sou)* focuses on portraying the everyday interactions taking place within the extended unit of relatives that surrounds the main family of the show. The relating families presented consist of married heterosexual couples with children - a scriptwriting choice, which reveals a clear disposition towards promoting the conventional family model. According to Gioltzidou F. and Gioltzidou G., this disposition can be also observed through the tendency of older family members to consistently urge their offsprings to appreciate the conventional family model, support Greek customs and traditions (including religious traditions) and encourage them to consider that 'the traditional family structure is the key to happiness'. Therefore, in *Your Kin (To Soi Sou)*, the comedic effect does not derive from satirizing issues related to the traditional roles of the family members (as is the case in the previous two examples), but from satirizing aspects of their personalities. For instance, sources of satire are the stinginess of Savvas (Ilias Meletis), the irony of Alexandra (Mirka Papakonstantinou), as well as Bella-Pelagia's (Vivian Kontomari) constant search for love. As Gioltzidou F. and Gioltzidou G. stress, 'the institution of the conventional nuclear family remains intact and uncommented (in this series), while the comical conflicts of its members rather strengthen the belief in it than disrupt its cohesion'. Despite the focus on only

including representations of conventional family formations, the high viewership rates of the series indicate that *Your Kin (To Soi Sou)* was and still is loved by the Greek audience. As Gioltzidou F. and Gioltzidou G. put it, ‘this could initiate a big debate’ regarding whether the Greek society of the 2010s could be considered conservative (returning to old values), and/or whether (and to what degree) it could be capable to ultimately accept and approve innovative ideas and elements of modernism (pp. 294-296).

Overall, Gioltzidou F. and Gioltzidou G. identify that all three series have as a common feature the battle between conventional and unconventional family models. In the first two cases, *Dolce Vita* and *Happy Together (Eftihismenoi Mazi)*, it seems that the unconventional elements prevail, while in the most recent series, *Your Kin (To Soi Sou)*, ‘conventionality’ returns. Ultimately, they conclude that these comedy series try to ideologically balance the portrayals of conventional and unconventional aspects of the Greek family. Yet the traditional family model ends up always being protected as the only stable, strong and legitimate version, despite its (depicted) potentialities for flexibility and adaptability actualized through ‘rebellious’ characters (p. 296).

Having now examined the existing literature on representations of gender, sexuality and family in Greek comedy series, we can deduce that the main characteristic met in all the studies investigated in this section and, by extension, in all the series referenced, is the battle between tradition and modernization. This battle seems to be the driving force behind the shaping of character profiles, the forming of plots, even the premise focusing of entire series. According to what Vamvakas (2019) mentioned earlier, ‘the satirical confrontation of the normative and legitimation aspect of tradition is linked to the topic of family’ (p. 35). In other words, it is the ‘family theme’ that is able to concentrate the most dynamic portrayals of the battle between tradition and modernization in Greek television fiction. Therefore, in order to investigate how competing ideologies circulating in Greece during the 1990s influenced the comedy-making of the era, the third part of the Analysis focuses specifically on examining representations of the institution of family in the series selected - through the prism, of course, of the battle between tradition and modernization.

CHAPTER 3: **RESEARCH DESIGN**

3.1 Research Paradigm

According to McKee (2003), we make sense of the reality that we live in through our culture, therefore different cultures can have very different experiences of reality from one another. ‘No single representation of reality can be the only true one, or the only accurate one, or the only one that reflects reality because other cultures will always have alternative, and equally valid ways of representing and making sense of that part of reality’ (pp. 10-11). This approach to reality sense making is called (cultural) Relativism, an ontological stance according to which ‘there is no single shared social reality, only a series of alternative social constructions’ (Snape and Spencer, 2003, p.16). According to Relativism, reality is only knowable through socially constructed meanings. This constitutes Relativism a variant of Idealism, which asserts that, alongside socially constructed meanings, reality is knowable through the human mind, its beliefs and understanding. Therefore, the ontological position of this research study, in other words, the perception of Greek ‘reality’, as represented in the Greek comedy series of the 1990s, is executed through a relativist and idealist approach to reality sense-making. This means that this work does not claim that the ideological and sociocultural physiognomies as (re)presented in Greek comedy series accurately reflect Greek ‘reality’, neither considers Greek ‘reality’ as the one and only true reality, nor ‘compares’ Greek ‘reality’ with other possible cultural ‘realities’ (i.e. British or American). On the contrary, it deems ‘reality’ as constructed by the human way of thinking, social beliefs, values and experiences - elements which can vary among different societies and cultures. Thus, ‘reality’ is not just open for interpretation, but it is through interpretation that we can make sense of the social world.

The epistemological stance that stresses the significance of interpretation and observation in understanding the social world is called Interpretivism - an integral part of the qualitative tradition (Snape and Spencer, 2003, p. 7). The social world, as Snape and Spencer put it, is ‘not governed by law-like regularities but is mediated through meaning and human agency’ (p. 17). Therefore, its understanding is shaped by interpreting the interrelated psychological, social, historical and cultural aspects of people’s lives (p. 7). Hence, Interpretivism is a suitable research paradigm as the aim of this study is to investigate and

analyse the creative formations and ideological physiognomies of the Greek comedy series of the 1990s as influenced by the sociocultural ‘reality’ of the era. However, due to the prominent human agency in social research, Interpretivism supports the idea that truth and knowledge, being culturally and historically situated, are subjective. As researchers are part of the social reality, they can never be totally separate from certain social values and beliefs themselves. This factor unavoidably informs the way in which data are collected and interpreted (Ryan, 2018, p.8). Yet, even though the findings are influenced by the researchers’ perspective affecting the objectivity of their study, it is important they remain transparent about their assumptions (Snape and Spencer, 2003, p. 17).

According to Bryman (2012), the researchers, who apply the interpretivist model to a study, focus on these intellectual interpretivist traditions: hermeneutics, Weber’s notion of Verstehen, phenomenology and symbolic interactionism (p. 31). Briefly, (1) hermeneutics, a term imported into the social sciences from theology, is concerned with the theory and method of understanding human action by interpreting the deeper meaning of texts and documents (Bryman, 2012, p. 28; Ryan, 2018, p. 8); (2) Weber’s Verstehen (which means ‘understanding’ in German) focuses on the exploration of understanding and perception from the point of view of research participants and attempts to explain the cause and effect of social actions (Ryan, 2018, p. 9). Such ‘causal explanation’ is conducted in relation to the ‘interpretive understanding of social action’ rather than to external forces which have no meaning for those involved in that social action (Weber et al., 1947, p. 88); (3) phenomenology is a philosophy questioning how individuals experience and make sense of the world around them and how the researcher can bracket out preconceptions in his or her comprehension of the world (Bryman, 2012, p. 30); (4) finally, according to symbolic interactionism, social interaction takes place in such a way that people are continually interpreting the symbolic meaning of their environment (which includes the actions of others) and act in relation to this imputed meaning (Bryman, 2012, p. 31). However, due to the nature of the chosen research method, explained below, which does not incorporate reception investigations with the help of audience participants, the interpretivist tradition mainly used in this study is hermeneutics, since our ‘understanding’ of the Greek ‘reality’ takes place by interpreting the deeper meaning of the ‘text’ - with that ‘text’ being the comedy series examined, as analysed in the following section.

3.2 Research Method

For McKee (2003), cultural Relativism is directly linked with the term ‘post-structuralism’, a methodological perspective which aims to interpret the various elements of society which ‘produce’ culture, such as books, films, magazines, television programmes, etc. (p. 12). According to cultural studies, any such cultural practice, product or content is referred to as ‘text’. In its broader, poststructural sense, ‘text’ is understood as an object that can be ‘read’, and thus, analysing media content, for example, can be considered a ‘reading’ (and not an objective examination or collection of data) (Fürsich, 2009, p. 240). This interpretivist method of ‘reading’ a text to conduct a study is called textual analysis and its purpose is to ‘make an educated guess at some of the most likely interpretations that might be made of that text’ (McKee, 2003, p. 1). According to McKee (2003), there are three perspectives/types of textual analysis that a researcher may choose to use, depending on what approach he or she may take to judging different cultures’ sense making practices. These perspectives are: the realist, the structuralist and the post-structuralist perspective (p. 9). The textual analysis type most suitable this study is the post-structuralist one, as the interpretations of the Greek culture derived from the investigated text (Greek comedy series) is not considered as representing reality most accurately (realist perspective), nor is it compared with equivalent cultural products of other cultures or countries (e.g. British or American comedy series) in order to establish similarities and differences (structuralist perspective) (p. 12). Rather, through a post-structuralist perspective, the textual investigation analysis of Greek comedy series of the 1990s seeks to shape an understanding about the ways through which representations of Greek sociocultural ideologies take place, the assumptions behind them and what kinds of sense making about Greek society they reveal (p. 17).

Textual analysis is considered by Fürsich (2009) a viable method for such media investigations as the ‘texts’ in question (television products) constitute ‘a distinctive discursive moment between encoding and decoding that justifies special scholarly engagement’ (p. 238). By using this method, the researcher is able to detect underlying meaning, implicit patterns, ideological and cultural assumptions and omissions of a text - even by strategic selection and presentation of fragments of the text, operating as evidence for an overall argument (p. 241). This sort of qualitative analysis involves a ‘long preliminary soak’ (prolonged engagement) of the chosen text undertaking narrative, genre, semiotic or rhetorical strategies (Hall, 1975, p. 15), executed through an interpretive analysis approach. As Fürsich (2009) puts it, ‘the narrative character of media content, its potential as a site of ideological negotiation and its impact as mediated ‘reality’ necessities interpretation in its own right’ (p. 238). Such a

statement acknowledges the autonomy of cultural studies and research practices in the analysis of text, which can be evaluated and interpreted independently from the intentions of their authors and producers or their reception by the audience (p. 240).

Philo (2007), on the other hand, claims that it is impossible to analyse text effectively without integrating an examination of the wider systems of ideologies which inform the production process of the text. He stresses the importance of taking into account the dynamics between the produced text and its sources - in other words, the intentions of the producers. In addition to that, he considers necessary to simultaneously study the audience reception of the text before making conclusions about its ideological meaning and its impact on the public. Therefore, according to Philo, the basis of textual analysis should consist of interlinked production, content (text), and reception investigations. If that is not the case and the analysis remains text-based, he warns that the study will not show: '(1) the origins of competing discourses and how they relate to different social interests; (2) the diversity of social accounts compared to what is present (and absent) in a specific text; (3) the impact of external factors such as professional ideologies on the manner in which the discourses are represented; and (4) what the text actually means to different parts of the audience' (pp. 184-185). Thus, for Philo, the communication of meanings from their inception in contested perspectives, through the structures by which they are provided to and processed by the media, to their subsequent distribution as text and lastly to their reception by the public should be considered a total circulating system and get investigated in its entirety when textual analysis is conducted (p. 192). Consequently, by diverging from a 'text-only' analysis, the representations derived from the text are more accurate, its significance to the audience is more noticeable, while the social and political structures which underpin its content are more effectively detectible (pp. 185-186).

However, the circulation of meaning through the key interacting dimensions of production, content and reception is not the only reliable option for conducting textual analysis. As mentioned earlier, Fürsich (2009) believes in the autonomy of the text, as an integral basis for the researcher to depend on in undertaking an interpretive analysis.

'I ultimately argue that despite many advantages of large-scale research projects that integrate moments of production, content and reception, only independent textual analysis can elucidate the narrative structure, symbolic arrangements and ideological potential of media content' (Fürsich, 2009, p. 243).

In practice, according to Fürsich, if the researcher decides to investigate moments of production by interviewing producers, journalists, writers, etc. of a text, there is a possibility they may

reflect a momentary situation only relying on psychological and individual attitudes, and lack long-term evaluations and applications. Another problem that occurs is that the relationship between the personal convictions of media workers and media content is not one-dimensional. It would be unwise to argue that if a majority of news journalists, for example, are conservative, media content would be conservative as well. 'Such an account overlooks powerful structural, economic and professional constraints on media production' (pp. 242-243). Furthermore, attempting to find and interview a media content 'auteur' is highly challenging due to the collective creative process underlying most television productions. When it comes to reception investigations, on the other hand, audiences' input is often gathered in focus groups long after the actual text has been distributed/aired, while the amount of text used in the focus groups is fragmented, short and cannot cover the whole range of content that the researcher is able to analyse during a years-long study. Moreover, in research methodology approaches similar to Philo's, 'selective use of audience reactions' are merely used to 'authenticate' a specific reading of the researcher as the dominant reading'. Therefore, audiences' voice constitutes just a stimulus to generate feedback to support the researcher's interpretations - a mixed-method approach of little value (p. 243).

Due to all these problematic issues, the research method of this study does not include interviews with Greek comedy creators, nor does it incorporate audience reception investigations, but remains entirely focused on interpreting 'the text'. Besides, the lack of sufficient primary academic analysis on Greek comedy series by scholars highlights the need for conducting a fundamental text-only investigation, which can then work as a basis for further production and reception studies. Furthermore, in order to take on some of Philo's criticism against textual analysis which does not include production and reception investigations, the research method of this investigation affiliates with some of Carvalho's views and propositions on the subject. According to Carvalho (2008), a pragmatic set of research strategies should be embarked by critical discourse analysts, which integrate contextual factors, such as the historic contingencies of the text, the investigation of social actors associated with the text, and the impact of the text on various constituencies. This approach of analysing historical and social context is largely incorporated throughout the main analysis of the 'text' of this study, while the Introduction chapter, also attempts to offer an initial presentation and understanding of relative contextual information around the history of Greek television as influenced by the political framework of the late 20th century Greece. As Carvalho suggests, such methodological decisions constitute a way to overcome some limitations of critical discourse analysis which

remain too close to the text and highlight contextual ideological constraints and effects of the text under investigation (p. 172).

On a similar note with Fürsich and Carvalho's views on text-only analysis, Vande Berg et al. (1998) advise that textual critics should 'start with the text and/or textualizations and see where they take them, rather than starting with some judgments and then searching out evidence to support them' (p. 299). For Johnson (1986-7), 'the text' is no longer studied for its own sake, nor even for the social effect it may be thought to produce, but rather for the subjective or cultural forms which it realizes and makes available' (p. 62). Therefore, text, such as media content, can be seen not as the passive or reflective 'crop' of media production, but rather as the momentarily fixed form of an ongoing negotiation, even struggle, over meaning and common sense (Fürsich, 2009, p. 247). Yet, through Fürsich and Philo's conflicting approaches to textual analysis, it can be concluded that there is a constant debate about which site is more efficient in the construction of textual meaning: the variety of interpretations of the active/passive audience (reception investigation) or the hegemonic/polysemic reading of the text executed by the researcher through a post-structuralist perspective? (Fürsich, 2009, p. 243). According to Dow (1996), neither can provide 'better' evidence, as in both situations it is the researchers' effective manipulation of the method they choose - it is their 'act of interpretation and argument' which 'is paramount' (p. 15). Consequently, we could summarize in Fürsich words that:

'The measure for a well-executed textual interpretation cannot be to explain how closely the text represent the producers' intentions nor does it mean how close does the textual analyst come to the actually prevalent audience interpretation of the text. Instead, the textual analyst needs to establish the ideological potential of the text between production and consumption. The question is not how accurately the text reflect reality but what version of reality is normalized and as a consequence, how emancipatory or hegemonic is the text' (Fürsich, 2009, p. 249).

Having now examined many parameters of the textual analysis method, along with the most prominent arguments about its advantages and disadvantages in relation to the positionality of the researcher undertaking this methodological approach, it is time to demonstrate in practice how textual analysis has been utilized in this thesis. Repeating Hall (1975), since the research method chosen here is textual analysis, the coding process had to start with a 'long preliminary soak' into the chosen 'text' (p. 15). Namely, the first stage of coding involved watching all 755 episodes of the eleven Greek comedy series, which were selected according to the rationale presented in the Introduction chapter (refer to section 1.4). Out of the 755 episodes, the ones

that were chosen to undergo interpretivist/hermeneutical analysis, were the episodes which provided ‘moments’ related to the three main topics of the main Analysis chapter - that is ‘moments’ that portrayed conversations among characters talking about 1) national identity, 2) political ideologies/practices and 3) family-related issues/beliefs. Then, a list was created stating the name of the series and number of the episode in which a specific character expressed his/her opinion about one of the topics mentioned above. The ‘nature’ of his/her opinion/comment was also recorded on the list. For example, when a character made a self-deprecating comment about his/her nationality that meant that the ‘moment’ in question was related to the national identity topic and thus it was listed as such. The fact that that specific ‘moment’ had to do with a self-deprecating comment (‘nature’) meant that it was marked as an incident which would be presented and analysed in section 4.1.4, which is dedicated to discourse on ‘stereotyping the Greeks’, which, in turn, is part of the National Identity subchapter (4.1) of the main Analysis chapter (4). Similarly, when a character would make a ‘racist’ joke (‘nature’) about a foreigner, that ‘moment’ would be marked as a national identity ‘moment’ and would be presented and analysed in section 4.1.3, which focuses on representations of ‘racism’ and, in turn, is part of the National Identity subchapter of the main Analysis chapter. In this fashion, the characters’ views on the rest of the topics (e.g. their views on politics and family issues/beliefs), expressed through the dialogues of the scenes, would be marked and listed accordingly, and then analysed in the relevant section of the Analysis chapter.

Consequently, in this thesis, the decision regarding what part of the ‘text’ would be chosen and analysed is taken by the ‘text’ itself! Or in other words, it is the characters of the series, who by ‘speaking their minds’ on various issues related to national identity, politics and beliefs on the institution of family offer ‘the first-hand material’ needed for the analysis. My role is to mediate and place the ‘the first-hand material’ into appropriate groups and then interpret it in the Analysis chapter having provided first the full dialogues in which the characters express their opinions (namely, ‘the first-hand material’). As Fürsich (2009) puts it, with such a ‘strategic’ selection and presentation of fragments, the ‘text’ itself is able to operate as ‘evidence’ for the overall argument, as a means for the detection of underlying meaning, implicit patterns, ideological and cultural assumptions (p. 241).

CHAPTER 4: ANALYSIS

4.1 THE GREEK COMEDY SERIES OF THE 1990s AND NATIONAL IDENTITY

4.1.1 The early years of the American Sitcom and the complexities in representing the US identity

According to Morreale (2003), in the summer of 1951, the American television channel CBS introduced *The Amos 'n' Andy Show* (CBS, 1951-1953), adapted from a popular radio sitcom that had been on the air since 1928. Even though, the protagonists in the radio version were played by two white actors, CBS decided to launch the television version with an all-black cast. In a similar fashion to other sitcoms of that period, *The Amos 'n' Andy Show* fell into the category of 'the screwball comedy' (a fast-paced, farcical comedy style with witty dialogues and often romantic storylines that involve a battle of the sexes) portraying the everyday adventures of a conventional, middle-class black man Amos (Alvin Childress), his sidekick Andy (Spencer Williams), and their devious friend George 'Kingfish' (Tim Moore). Similarly to *The Beulah Show* (ABC, 1950-1953), which was the first sitcom to feature a black female protagonist, *The Amos 'n' Andy Show* perpetuated negative stereotypes about African-Americans. While sitcoms of the era that revolved around white families usually portrayed black people as 'hard-working and restrained', *The Amos 'n' Andy Show* presented its black characters as 'lazy and ignorant'. Its insistence on negative portrayals of black Americans led the civil rights organization National Association for the Advancement of Coloured People (NAACP) to threaten to coordinate a boycott of the show's sponsor, Blatz Beer, if the show was not taken off the air. Despite the pressure, CBS refused to end the series, but when during the second season *The Amos 'n' Andy Show* fell from place thirteen to twenty-five in the Nielsen ratings, it was discontinued - a decision seemingly taken based 'only' on poor ratings. As expected, the controversy the show caused pushed American television channels to 'concentrate on safe, nondescript, white middle-class suburban families'. Thus 'after the furore over *The Amos 'n' Andy Show*, sitcoms starring black performers virtually disappeared from the airwaves' (p. 3).

By the fall of 1951, the West and East Coasts were linked by coaxial cable, establishing a coast-to-coast television coverage. That meant that, unlike previously, audiences across the US could now watch the same program simultaneously. Coast-to-coast coverage, however, brought many (in)direct changes in the ways television series represented ‘the Americans’. Before the introduction of the ‘coaxial cable’, sitcoms usually revolved around ‘urban, ethnic, working-class families dealing with life in America’, such as *The Goldbergs* (NBC, 1949-1955), a long running series about a Jewish immigrant family living in New York, and *Mama* (CBS, 1949-1956), which featured a Norwegian family at the turn of the century living in San Francisco. After the introduction of the ‘coaxial cable’, the television channels stopped focusing on urban, ethnic sitcoms, which used to be aimed mostly at audiences clustered in coast cities, and started producing sitcoms that featured ‘white, middle-class suburban families of indistinct nationality’. Hence, the ‘coaxial cable’, as Morreale puts it, led to the homogenization of representations in American series, while ‘the experiences of working-class or ethnic families were simply not represented in television’ anymore (pp. 2-4).

After the second world war, the ‘loss’ of ethnic identities was a common phenomenon throughout the US, as the expansion of the economy moved many (white) working-class Americans into the middle-class suburbs. Television played its part in that process as, through its portrayals of the suburbs, it idealized images of the white middle-class American ‘who had the means to buy the appropriate consumer goods’. Domestic comedies, such as *The Adventures of Ozzie and Harriet* (ABC, 1952-1966), which exemplified the ‘ideal’ suburban nuclear families, characterized the American television of the 1950s, portraying humorous, trivial situations of everyday life, ‘where problems were easily resolved, and on-screen lives were dominated by leisure rather than work’ (p. 4).

Nevertheless, a sitcom which managed to merge the old ‘urban, ethnic, working-class sitcom’ and the new ‘domestic suburban family sitcom’ was *I Love Lucy* (CBS, 1951-1957). As Morreale informs us, when CBS encouraged actress Lucille Ball to produce a sitcom, she agreed only if her real-life husband, the Cuban actor Desi Arnaz, was allowed to play her on-screen husband. At first, the channel hesitated to portray ‘what was then considered a mixed marriage’ but greenlit the show after Ball and Arnaz agreed to ‘take a pay cut in exchange for complete production control of the series’. Succinctly, *I Love Lucy* depicted both professional and domestic situations and mixed the ‘physical’ and ‘screwball’ humour of sitcoms such as *The Amos 'n' Andy Show* with some degree of character realism as in *Mama* (p. 4).

During the 1960’s, according to Tredy (2013), the American television did not echo the unrest social troubles of the era, such as the race and student riots and assassinations of

politicians, or the sociopolitical ideological changes in civil rights activism and feminism. Instead, the television programming of the 1960s, especially in terms of sitcoms, was characterized by two comedy subgenres that appeared to ‘in no way reflect what was often going on right outside the viewers’ living rooms’. Those two subgenres were the rural sitcom and the supernatural sitcom, both utilized as a means of ‘soothing escapism’. Some of the most popular rural sitcoms were *The Andy Griffith Show* (CBS, 1960-1968), *The Beverly Hillbillies* (CBS, 1962-1971), *Green Acres* (CBS, 1965-1971), *Petticoat Junction* (CBS, 1963-1970) and *Hee-Haw* (CBS, 1969-1971). As Tredy puts it, through those shows the American identity was presented as ‘lulling reassured by the grassroots wisdom and old-fashioned horse-sense of heroes like Andy Griffith or of the shenanigans of country bumpkins striking it rich and/or of rich socialites moving out to the sticks’. The other popular subgenre, the supernatural sitcom, included shows such as *Mister Ed* (CBS, 1961-1965), *My Mother the Car* (NBC, 1964-1966), *Bewitched* (ABC, 1963-1972), *I Dream of Jeannie* (NBC, 1964-1970), *My Favourite Martian* (CBS, 1963-1966), *The Addams Family* (ABC, 1964-1966), *The Munsters* (CBS, 1964-1966) and *The Ghost and Mrs. Muir* (NBC, 1967-1970). They all told the stories of ‘how witches, genies, aliens, ghosts, grandfatherly vampires, cuddly werewolves and other assorted monsters and side-show freaks all somehow coped with living a ‘normal’ life in the small towns and quiet suburbs of America’ (pp. 9-10).

As Tredy explains, by the end of the 1960’s, the American viewers could no longer remain disconnected from current harsh realities. As a response to much criticism by minority action groups and feminist organizations, claiming that minorities and women were either unrepresented or too stereotypically represented in American sitcoms, ABC, CBS and NBC attempted to ‘bring the changing face of America to the small screen’. NBC, in particular, tried to overturn the traditional representations of black people by giving to two popular African-American actors - Diahann Carroll and Bill Cosby - a sitcom each, adding, this way, *Julia* (NBC, 1968-1971) and *The Bill Cosby Show* (NBC, 1969-1971) to its line-up (p. 10).

Nonetheless, despite televisions executives’ strategies to ‘counter charges of racism and racial insensitivity’, by producing shows such as *Julia* and *The Bill Cosby Show*, they ended up employing the ‘logic of colour-blindness’. Namely, they incorporated multicultural castings ‘without acknowledging or addressing cultural and social differences’ (Nilsen and Turner, 2014, p. 5). As Tredy (2013) puts it, those series attempted to portray ‘blacks living like (or as) whites’, leaving racial tensions out of the picture. For example, the black protagonist Chet (Bill Cosby) in *The Bill Cosby Show* was an ordinary gym teacher at a primarily ‘black high school’ (p. 12). Yet his household was represented as ‘an upper-middle class family’, who just

happened to be African-American, virtually intact by any financial difficulties and racial prejudices (Means Coleman, 1998, p. 199). Similarly, the series *Julia* portrayed its black female lead, Julia (Diahann Carroll), as a widowed single mother totally distanced from any references to Black American culture. Therefore, both series depicted their African-American protagonists in a multicultural assimilationist fashion, presenting a generally colour-blind America that seemed generations away, if ever achievable (Martens and Povoia, 2017, p. 119; Trendy, 2013, p. 12).

According to Brook (2003), it took until the 1990s for the American television channels to consciously get rid of 'assimilationist' strategies that denied racial differences, and come up with rejuvenated sitcoms featuring black characters, such as *The Fresh Prince of Bel-Air* (NBC, 1990-1996), *In Living Colour* (FOX, 1990-1994), *Family Matters* (ABC, 1989-1997; CBS, 1997-1998), and *Living Single* (FOX, 1993-1998). Those sitcoms were presented to the American public as 'separate but equal programs' portraying 'a self-sufficient ethno-racial world' that existed parallel to the 'white world' (p. 85). As Martens and Povoia (2017) explain, by the late 1990s and early 2000s, as the 'black' sitcoms started to decrease in number, a group of minority media advocacy institutions asked for more racial diversity in the programming of the main channels. Due to the pressures, the channels did not only start incorporating more people of colour in the casts of shows, but also twisted the 'stereotypical' hierarchy of 'white superiors' and 'black subordinates' by featuring more black characters in professional and managerial positions, usually in drama series such as *ER* (NBC, 1994-2009) and *NYPD Blue* (ABC, 1993-2005) (p. 120). In doing so, a new mode of racial representation was established, which Entman and Rojecki (2001) call 'utopian reversal' (p. 152).

Summarizing the main points of this overview on the history of the American sitcoms of the 20th century, it is clear that the portrayal of the US identity in those programmes had been undergoing constant changes. Its continuous forming and reshaping throughout turbulent times and peaceful periods exemplifies the multifacetedness in the nature of the American national identity. The relationship between this multifacetedness - represented through portrayals of ethnic groups (in the early sitcoms), African-Americans, white Americans, east and west coasters, and citizens of 'indistinct nationalities' living in wealthy suburbs - and the various strategies taken by American television channels over the decades, concerning the ways those 'multifaceted' groups of 'Americans' were depicted, perpetuated a state of constant 'crisis' in relation to US identity representation in American sitcoms. That crisis faced a lot of criticisms by the American viewers and activist groups, as mentioned throughout this section,

either because the various representations incorporated racists/stereotypical elements or promoted cultural assimilation logics.

As stated in the Literature Review chapter (section 2.1), an aspect of Greek television fiction which academia has not investigated yet is how Greek identity is represented in Greek comedy series when being in crisis. Of course, the Greek television does not face the complexities (related to issues of colour, for example) that the American television has been dealing with when portraying US identity in series. However, it would be interesting to explore how the subject of national identity, especially when being in crisis, has been utilized in Greek series-making, mostly in regard to its ‘creative’ aspect - namely, how it has been used by creators of Greek comedy series within narratives and dialogues in order to generate laughter.

4.1.2 Representing the Greek national identity... in crisis

As mentioned in the Introduction and Literature Review chapters, one of the aims of the thesis is to investigate the Greek national identity as represented through the Greek television comedies of the 1990s. As observed throughout this section, by examining episodes of the series selected that, directly or indirectly, reference the subject of national identity, it becomes apparent that the characters tend to bring up conversations around national identity mostly in relation to the various dangers that, according to their views, threaten it. This comes as no surprise as, according to Woodward (1997, p. 15), ‘identity’ and ‘identity crisis’ are popular terms and notions that characterise our contemporary societies. For Mercer (1990, p. 43), however, identity only becomes an issue when it is actually in crisis: ‘when something assumed to be fixed, coherent and stable is displaced by the experience of doubt and uncertainty.’ Giddens (1990) argues that one of the dangers that lead to such crises in traditional types of social order, and by extension in national identities, is ‘modernity’. As he puts it, the effects of modernity on national identity makes sense in the context of the transformations that are defining contemporary life as a result of globalization, which ‘alters some of the most intimate and personal features of our day-to-day existence’ (p. 4).

This altering of our most intimate and personal features of our day-to-day experience caused by modernity and globalization constitutes the topic of a conversation between three characters, Charoula (Elda Panopoulou), Kostas (Giannis Nezis) and Fivos (Tasos Kostis), in episodes 8 of the series *The Penthouse (To Retire)/To Petipé* (MEGA, 1990-1992). In detail, in the first scene of the episode, we see Charoula (Elda Panopoulou) getting informed by her colleague, Kostas (Giannis Nezis), that he has just become the new owner of a little shop that sells shirts. He plans to rename it ‘Oxford Street’, claiming that foreign names are in fashion.

Charoula most emphatically does not approve of its new foreign name, especially due to the fact that the shop is located at a remote, commercially insignificant suburb of Athens (Ano Liosia). She would later comment to her friend, Fivos (Tasos Kostis), that: 'I'm a Greek, a Balkan, an 'undeveloped', living in Greece, and I see foreign signboards everywhere! Malls, restaurants, patisseries, bars - all with foreign signboards! I've even seen a funeral home called *The Happy Silence* (in English) and its owner's name underneath written in the English/Latin alphabet. He thinks he's become a European this way, the idiot.' Fivos replies that this phenomenon is here to promote tourism and to indicate to consumers that the shops also provide foreign stock, as to his opinion: 'the foreign products are better than the Greek.' Charoula disagrees and states that Greeks have adopted a very 'unhealthy' tendency for xenomania. In fact, a situation which portrays Greek characters adopting an 'unhealthy' tendency for xenomania, as Charoula describes it, takes place in the final scene of episode 19 of the same series, when a couple of female guests arrive at Katerina's (Katerina Gioulaki) home and introduce themselves using the French and English version of their Greek names. For the entire scene, they insist on using English and French words and phrases throughout their talking as a sign of 'elegance' and 'chicness', driving Katerina crazy with their pretentious behaviour.

According to Robins (1997), the 'transnationalization of economic and cultural life', which is taking over due to the phenomenon of globalization, has triggered the 'dissolution' of the old institutions of national states and communities. Since our 'familiar structures and orientations are weakening, we are increasingly exposed to new and disorientating horizons of possibility.' The new possibilities that emerge due to globalization, however, comes hand in hand with new uncertainties and anxieties (p. 12). Indeed, in the examples taken from episodes 8 and 19 of *The Penthouse (To Retire)*, we see characters commend upon the new features, or else, the 'new possibilities' that emerged within the Greek society of the 1990s due to the transnationalization of economic and cultural life as a result of globalization. According to their words, within their day-to-day experience, the newly brought features of globalization come in the form of malls, foreign stock, the use of the English language instead of the Greek for the naming of shops and services, as well as the use of English or French phrases in their everyday communication. As already stated by Robins (1997), these new 'horizons' come hand in hand with uncertainty, anxiety and disorientation - consequences of globalization that occur due to the 'dissolution' of our 'familiar structures'. These negative aspects of globalization are represented through the character Charoula, who, in the scene analysed above, appears frustrated due to the 'altering' of her 'familiar' everyday experience. In other words, what

seems to constitute Charoula's main concern, when it comes to the effects of globalization within the Greek society, is 'cultural convergence' (Robins, 1991, p. 28), according to which distinct characteristics of the Greek identity, such as the language, culture and lifestyles would gradually disappear as globalization spreads and strengthens. This eventually leads to a national identity in crisis, and its people losing touch with their culture, history and sense of self.

Moments which directly reference aspects related to Greeks experiencing a crisis when it comes to their national identity occur in the series *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)/Oi Aparáδεκτοι* (MEGA, 1991-1993). In detail, in the second scene of episode 27, Vlassis (Vlassis Bonatsos) reads an article to Giannis (Giannis Bezos), his flatmate, which states that: 'The Greeks have lost their national identity, and, therefore, they are more vulnerable than nations which are more aware of their national origin and roots.' Giannis agrees with the statement saying: 'We have indeed lost our roots' and advises Vlassis that he should stop going to bars to listen to 'that barking' (referring to commercial music). Instead, he recommends that he listens to traditional Greek songs like *Yerakina* and *Menousis* (see section 4.1.5) in order to reconnect with his roots. At the flat next door, a married couple, Spiros (Spiros Papadopoulos) and Dimitra (Dimitra Papadopoulou), discuss the same subject, having just read another article about the controversy around the Greekness of the ancient history of Macedonia - an issue which irritates them. Therefore, throughout the following scenes, the characters endeavour to reconnect with their roots and history by asking relatives where their ancestors came from. They are proud to find out that they originate from various places around Greece, while some of their ancestors were 'heroic historical figures' of the 19th and early 20th century. Yet, highly annoyed by the fact that other countries are not very familiar with the history of Greece, which results, according to their words, in the creations of controversies, for example around the Greekness of the ancient history of Macedonia, they decide to dress up in national costumes, perform a song and 'send it to Europe' to propagate their national history. Some of the lyrics of the 'patriotic' song they write are: 'What is our country?/ Isn't it the plains?/ It is our history/ A page that glows/ Paok, Aris, Iraklis (football teams)!/ Goals they score all these three!/ What makes the Greek?/ It's his cunningness/ His proud boorishness within his nobility.'

As we notice, unlike the previous example taken from the series *The Penthouse (To Retire)*, the characters in *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)* do not refer, directly or indirectly, to globalization as the cause of losing touch with their history and roots, and by extension with their national identity. Instead, they attempt to 'fix' a crisis in their national identity, which, according to Aitaki (2015), came to be as a result of a geopolitical conflict (the

Macedonian name dispute⁴) with a neighbouring country, inflicted during the period this series was produced. As she explains, the characters, in this episode, in order to restore their sense of self as Greeks ‘resort to history, both in terms of national history and their personal family history in an attempt to construct a historicized version of their national identity’. Through this process, they attempt to rediscover some sort of continuity between the ‘glorious’ past and the present that would help them defend their ‘vulnerable’ national identity, which they deem is in danger due to contemporary international geopolitical affairs. In other words, they believe that reconnecting with the past would ‘equip them with the necessary arguments’ to defend Greece’s historical heritage and culture - and, thus, their national identity (p. 43).

On a similar note, in episode 35 of the same series, the characters are worried, once again, about the fact that other countries are not very familiar with the history of Greece - a matter, which, according to them, indirectly threatens Hellenism (Greekness), as Greece’s views and interests on international geopolitical affairs, such as the Macedonian name dispute, are overlooked. They decide, therefore, to make a play about the history of the country and perform it on a cruise ship for foreign tourists. The play they come up with consists of sketches that tell the history of Greece from the era of the Trojan War (13th-12th century B.C.) until the Greek War of Independence (1821-1832). Throughout the play, many historical figures of different eras intermingle and discuss about the constant threats that Hellenism undergoes over the centuries, which lead to its continuous diminishing. The play maintains a satirical, sarcastic, and self-deprecating tone, portraying the Greeks as unfortunate, disorientated, and vulnerable over the course of history - implying that contemporary Greeks do not remember who they really are, and they should at last ‘wake up!’ as Dimitra shouts, dressed as Laskarina Bouboulina (a female naval commander, heroine of the Greek War of Independence of 1821) at the end of the play.

This episode constitutes, therefore, an additional example which portrays contemporary Greeks coping with their national identity being in crisis by seeking to return to a lost past - a past, which Daniels (1993) describes as ‘coordinated by legends and landscapes, by stories of golden ages, enduring traditions, heroic deeds and dramatic destinies located in promised

⁴With the disintegration of Yugoslavia in 1991, one of the new countries that emerged, now known as North Macedonia, declared its independence under the name Republic of Macedonia. For Greece, the use of such a name was unwelcome, and therefore, it responded strongly against the newly formed state’s attempts to construct its national image by adopting historical and cultural aspects that Greece identifies as fundamentally Greek (Mavromatidis, 2010, p. 48; Aitaki, 2015, p. 39).

homelands with hallowed sites and scenery' (p. 5). According to Guibernau (2007), connecting with the historic past does not just legitimize a nation and its culture, but contributes to the (re)discovery and maintenance of 'the continuity' of its collective self. As she notes, recognizing, documenting, and studying antiquity is a modern practice that supplies contemporary nations with a distinguished pedigree, so that when its members look back at history, they are not confronted with a meaningless vacuum regarding their own collective origin, but are reassured by the actions of their ancestors. Therefore, exploring the past nurtures the subjective belief in a kinship relation at the heart of the nation, whereas constitutes the culture of each nation its signature to the rest of the world (pp. 14-15).

As investigated through the examples analysed from the series *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)*, the concept of continuity, as Guibernau (2007) puts it, stems from the idea of the country as a historically anchored entity that projects into the future. As she explains, its individuals can sense the continuity of their national identity through a set of experiences that transcend across time and are linked by a collective meaning that only 'insiders' can understand. The fact, however, that 'only insiders' can understand collective meanings, which derive for a distinct community's shared culture, past, symbols and customs, especially when bound to a specific location, entails the notion of 'differentiation from other'. Consequently, according to Guibernau (2007), the defining criteria of national identity are continuity across time, on the one hand, and differentiation from others, on the other. As she states, the dynamics emerged when these two notions are put together result to the creation of the distinction between 'members' (those who belong) and, on the opposite side, the 'strangers', 'the rest', 'the different' and, occasionally, 'the enemy' (p. 10). Thus, in the following section, the study focuses on analysing scenes from the Greek comedy series selected that portray moments in which characters, directly or indirectly, refer to their national identity in relation to other national identities, or else, in relation to the 'other'.

4.1.3 The Greek national identity and the 'Other': Racism and Xenophobia in the Greek comedy series of the 1990s

According to Hodkinson (2011), the sense of shared experience and belonging, necessary for meaningful nationalist expression, entails boundaries that are 'inevitable' between 'insiders' and 'outsiders.' Identities are, after all, relational, which means that every 'us' is reliant for its meaning and significance on its differentiation from one or more 'thems' (p. 199). Similarly, in Woodward's (1997) words, identities are 'forged through the marking of difference.' This marking of difference occurs both through the symbolic systems of representation and through

forms of social exclusion. 'Identity, then, is not the opposite of, but depends on, difference' (p. 29). Hence, 'what we think of our identity is dependent on what we think we are not' (Barker, 2012, p. 256). As Barth (1969) argues, it is often 'the ethnic boundary that defines the group rather than the cultural stuff that it encloses' (p. 15). What are, therefore, those boundaries seen as national identity markers that allow for the distinction of groups?

According to Rovisco (2008), people, in order to understand their collective identity as distinct from the identities of other collectives, rely on the highly prominent and largely unchanging set of symbolic boundaries, which are: language, religion and ethnicity. As she describes, the media constantly circulate stories, images and symbols of 'us' that originate from a variety of sources, including the state apparatus, cultural producers and institutions, operating both within and outside the state level. These stories, images and symbols of 'us' reinvent and negotiate the content of these symbolic boundaries or identity markers. Of course, symbolic boundaries differ from political and physical boundaries in that they are not always linked to a particular region. They may, instead, be associated with 'ideas' of a homeland or other spaces of cultural belonging that are related to an ethnic understanding of the nation. Nonetheless, despite any shifting social and historical conditions (for instance, a change or a dispute over a political/physical boundary), symbolic boundaries can continue to be mostly stable and unaffected. Thus, the symbolic boundaries that people employ to divide 'us' and 'them' are meaningful expressions of collective identities (p. 145).

However, as Rovisco (2008) notes, the crossing of boundaries, physical or symbolic, is associated with notions of challenge, danger, and transgression. Kuechler (1994, p. 51) identifies these negative consequences of crossing physical or symbolic boundaries - that is the co-presence of different ethnic groups often within the same space - as racism, xenophobia, and self-defence. For Woodward (1997), oppositions among different groups can indeed be seen negatively, as they may lead to the marginalisation and exclusion of individuals, who are deemed to belong to the 'other' group - the 'outsiders.' On the other hand, oppositions may also be embraced as a source of diversity, heterogeneity, and hybridity, where acceptance of change and distinction are viewed as enriching. In any case, she argues that, in order to maintain some social order, there must be a degree of consensus between the members of a group on how positively or negatively to classify difference and opposition. She concludes that each community has each own ways of classifying the world and its differences to the 'other' according to the community's culture, standardized ideas and values (pp. 30, 35).

Therefore, the following scenes analysed offer an insight on how the 1990s Greeks saw themselves by classifying the 'other', as mentioned earlier, and what these classifications can

imply for the cultural values and ideologies that shaped the ‘Greek’ way of thinking of the era. The first example is taken from the black-comedy series *Crimes (Eglimata)/Εγκλήματα* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000), episode 14. In detail, Korina (Maria Kavoyianni), who works as a prostitute, but has lied to her boyfriend, Pavlos (Vasilis Eftaxopoulos), that she is a primary school teacher, asks a friend of hers, who is a real teacher, to ‘lend’ her her classroom and students, so she (Korina) could give the students a mock lesson. This way, she attempts to convince Pavlos that she is a teacher by inviting him to come and observe her teaching. At the lesson, she decides to teach Geography, though due to her lack of knowledge on the subject, she starts comparing the African country Burkina Faso with Greece saying: ‘We don’t care with which countries Burkina shares borders with. We’ll never go there, anyway. Why would we ever care about Burkina? We live in the most beautiful country in the world! It would be bad to lie! The day we had the grand opening of Acropolis, those poor ones had tails and were jumping from branch to branch! Of course, it wasn’t their fault! They are humans too! But look at the map and tell me: Is there any other country similar to beautiful, tired, poor but honourable *grand-Greece* of ours! LONG LIVE GREECE!’ The lesson ends with the students and her boyfriend clapping touched by her ‘patriotic’ speech, while she takes a bow. With this scene, the scriptwriter of *Crimes*, Lefteris Papapetrou, attempts to portray Greek characters that celebrate their national identity by bestowing pride and value upon it - a value, which, in this case, comes into being by having the characters compare their ancient history to an African country and its people. Therefore, in this example, the differentiation from ‘the other’ leads to the creation of a shared sense of superiority, as far as Greek national identity is concerned. This sense of superiority is then what is satirized by the scriptwriter in order to create comedy (comedic effect). As seen in the following examples, satirizing a shared sense of identity superiority does not only work as a means for offering comedic effect/entertainment, but also as a tool used by scriptwriters to build the plots of episodes.

A couple of examples that showcase the building of plots of episodes through the utilization of the sense of superiority derived from differentiating the Greek national identity from other national identities can be met in the series *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)/Οι Τρεις Χάριτες* (MEGA, 1990-1992), episodes 4 and 27. In detail, in the beginning of episode 4, we see the three sisters, Olga (Anna Panagiotopoulou), Maria (Nena Menti) and Iriini (Mina Adamaki) getting ready to welcome Olga’s daughter, Teti (Anna Kouri), who is visiting them from London, where she studies. Before her arrival, Teti informs them that she is coming over with her new boyfriend, John. Once they hear that his name is John, they take it for granted that he is an English man, and probably a royal! They are very proud of Teti’s choice of a

boyfriend and excited to meet him. However, it turns out that John is a Japanese man studying in England along with Teti. From that point on, the plot of the episode revolves around Olga's negative reaction to her daughter's relationship, and her expression of xenophobic and racist views against Asians, as an attempt to convince her daughter to break up with John due to his 'exotic' origin. In a similar tone, in the first half of episode 27 of the same series, the three sisters anxiously wait for the arrival of a Filipino, whom they hired through a maid agency to work as their servant. While waiting, Irini advises them: 'Composure! We'll pretend not to see the fact that she is yellow, okay?' to which Maria responds: 'Of course, we'll behave to her as if she is like us.' Olga agrees and emphatically adds: 'We are not uncultured to accentuate the flaw of the other (referring to the colour of the Filipino's skin).' The fact that the Filipino servant who arrives is a male and not a female, as they were expecting, complicates things even more for the sisters in their struggle to 'teach' the 'exotic' servant the 'Greek' ways of maintaining a household - which are actually the 'proper' ways, especially when it comes to cooking!

Despite the racist comment about the skin colour of the Filipino servant made in that episode - a problematic line put in place to satirize Olga's racist way of thinking, and, by extension, to work as a representation of racist ideologies circulating within the Greek society of the era - the more recent forms of racist discourse, according to Hodkinson (2011), the so-called 'new racism', have drifted away from notions of biological racial inferiority/superiority and towards the notion of essential differences of culture. As he argues, different ethnic communities have naturally different and incompatible collective values, priorities, allegiances, and ways of living. This constitutes the co-presence of different communities within the same space a threat to each of their identities, and a cause of natural hostility and conflict (p. 198). In Taguieff's (1994, p. 120) opinion, racism towards foreign groups is caused by the fact that a foreigner is assumed to be unassimilable without inciting a destruction of community identity. For Guibernau (2007), the dread of the unknown and the eagerness to preserve the community identity and culture are indeed contributing factors to racism. Yet, she points out that the preservation of the current political and economic status quo are some additional justifications given by individuals who subscribe to racism. In practice, racist behaviours may include avoiding 'the other', isolating and segregating oneself, as well as engaging in various forms of physical and verbal abuse, and threatening or attacking property. She concludes that racism constantly invokes a distinction that elevates one group over another and encourages the development of hostile feelings toward those who belong to the 'other'

group. At the same time, any negative assessments towards the ‘other’ group require active censorship of any inclination to see the ‘other’ group as an equal (pp. 147-148).

As observed in the examples above and in the examples that follow, Greek superiority, on the one hand, and negative assessments, stereotypes and racist overgeneralizations against immigrants living in Greece, on the other, are features constantly met in Greek comedy series of the 1990s. Another example depicting such a problematic way of thinking against foreign groups can be found in episode 13 of *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)/Οι Απαράδεκτοι* (MEGA, 1991-1993), in a scene where the characters have a meeting to decide what housekeeper they would hire. They consider hiring either a Filipino, an Albanian, a Polish or a black person. They ‘conclude’ that the Filipino would be rude, the Albanian would be so poor that ‘he’d never seen food in his life, therefore, he wouldn’t know how to cook for them’, and the Polish would be educated, so in that case they could have just hired a Greek instead. An additional case, in which negative stereotypes against foreigners take place, occurs in episode 7 of *With Two Mothers (Me Dyo Mamades)/Με Δύο Μαμάδες* (MEGA, 1998-1999). In detail, Annoula (Chara Kefala), having failed to make it into a Greek university for the third time, decides to go study gastronomy in Albania. Her decision infuriates her two mothers, Dora (Nena Menti) and Koula (Chryssa Ropa), who characteristically say: ‘What gastronomy? Those in Albania don’t even have food to eat!’ [...] ‘The whole Albania has come here (Greece), and my very child wants to go there!’ [...] ‘Why don’t you pick one more normal country, like Greece?’ With these ‘arguments’, they eventually convince Annoula not to choose Albania for her studies, but Germany. Nevertheless, the ‘joke’ in this case does not derive so much from the ‘arguments’ themselves, but mostly from the fact that the scriptwriters of the series, Panos Amarantidis and Spiros Metallinos, associated, in this scene, Albania with gastronomy - an association which in the eyes of the Greek audience of the 1990s would seem oxymoronic due to socio-economic factors discussed later in this section. Similarly, in episode 67 of *Just Us (Emeis ki emeis)/Εμείς κι Εμείς* (MEGA, 1994-1998), Maria (Maria Filippou) asks a beautician to fix her husband, Stelios (Stelios Pavlou), up, as, because of his causal choice of clothes and lack of good skincare, he looks like an ‘Albano-Bosnian’ (according to Maria’s words).

Apart from these racist representations of Balkans and Asians, there are also instances of negative portrayal of the Arab world in the series examined. In this case, however, the racist attitude of Greek characters towards Arab characters derives mostly from the stereotypical fear of terrorism. In detail, in episode 63 of *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)*, Olga (Anna Panagiotopoulou), dressed as a cleaner, spies on her daughter Teti (Anna Kouri) by watching

who gets in and out of the apartment building where the latter dwells. She does that because she heard that her daughter has some sort of connection with a man named Omar. Due to his middle-eastern name - which, for Olga's mindset, is associated with terrorism and danger - and along with a series of suspicious events that occur during the episode, Olga has drawn the conclusion that her daughter is associating with dangerous people. Therefore, by watching who gets in and out of Teti's apartment building, she hopes to solve the mystery and protect her daughter. So, while spying, she comes across an unknown to her Arab man named Mohammed (Nikos Papakonstantinou). Assuming that his name is Omar, and not Mohammed as he claims, she prevents him from entering the building, asks for his passport and interrogates him. The situation becomes highly distressing for Mohammed, who, in the end, decides not to enter as he gets annoyed by her unnecessarily authoritative and disrespectful behaviour. Another instance that portrays racist presumptions against Arabs, which, once again, derive from the stereotypical fear of terrorism, takes place in episodes 80 and 81 of *Just Us (Emeis ki Emeis)*. Telis (Konstantinos Katselis), a dentistry student is heard to be talking on the phone with a man called Abdul-Nasser, who subsequently turns out to be a fellow student. Yet, the rest of the characters, and especially Ermioni (Maria Martika), get paranoid and assume that since the man on the phone is an Arab, he must be a terrorist, and therefore Telis is a terrorist too.

On this subject, Woodward (1997) notes that, in the 1990s, western interpretations of the Orient tended to revolve mostly around Islamic extremism, which was seen - even demonised - as the primary new challenge to western, liberal values (p. 18). According to Guibernau (2007), particularly in the aftermath of the 9/11 terrorist attacks in New York and Washington, Muslims were singled out as the most severe threat to western civilisation, and they were frequently presented as the most alien and difficult to assimilate. As she explains, that was because they were deemed to contribute to the increase of violence and crime, while their cultures, languages, traditions and ways of life were perceived as 'strange' by western populations - constituting, therefore, a threat to national identity (p. 150). This might be interpreted as a new type of Orientalism, as defined by Edward Said back in 1978, where western societies establish a set of assumptions and representations about 'the East' that construct it as a place of fascination and danger, as both exotic and menacing. Nonetheless, according to Said, western understanding of the East reveals more about western concerns and anxieties than it does about the reality of living in those places, as was the case with Olga and Mohammed in episode 63 of *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)* mentioned above.

Even so, it is important to stress that, during the time of production of the comedy series examined in the study, prejudice, hostility and fear toward foreigners were growing rapidly in

western societies due to the large influx of immigration from eastern Europe and Africa - sparking rhetoric of an 'invasion of the poor', as well as phrases such as 'storming Europe' (Guibernau, 2007, p. 150). Betz (1994) points out that 'more than twice as high a percentage of the French population agreed in 1991 with the Front National's extremist position on immigration than generally voted for the party in regional or national elections.' For Betz, that indicated that in the 1990s xenophobia had become the most significant response in western Europe toward the challenges associated with the transition to post-industrial individualized capitalism - namely the coming of a multi-ethnic and multicultural world (p. 172). Guibernau (2007) argues that ideological factors, such as the perception of a cultural threat capable of damaging national identity, are accountable for creating fears within the 'dominant' group. However, a significant contributor that may also favour racism is an unstable economy. For her, racism gains recruits during times of crisis, which leads to minorities facing harsher treatment and being blamed for the misfortunes of the whole community. On the one hand, they are held responsible because of their assumed 'inefficiency', 'laziness', 'lack of culture', 'propensity to crime and arrogance', or even their 'economic success' - a success which has supposedly deprived the indigenous majority from financial prosperity. On the other, they are deemed to negatively impact the labour market by providing inexpensive, often 'black market' labour, which contributes to increased native working-class unemployment. Nevertheless, she points out that it is easier to tolerate a cheap, unproblematic labour force that is eager to do any type of work and apathetically accepts submission. Yet, when the 'majority' perceives it as 'natural' to be able to decide the status of the minority and believes that its authority derives from its undeniable 'superiority', any excuse seems appropriate to pinpoint the 'difference' and charge it negatively (pp. 149-150).

A strong example that illustrates the discourse above can be found in episode 89 of *Just Us* (*Emeis ki emeis*), when Maria (Maria Filippou), upset because of some robberies that recently took place in their neighbourhood, says to Smaragda (Smaragda Diamandidou) and Natasa (Natasa Manisali): 'Those Albanians are to blame for everything, for sure! [...] It's not that they are the ones that do the stealing, but they are responsible for the general situation.' She justifies the reasoning of such statement by saying that 'as foreigners move to Greece, salaries go down (because foreigners provide cheaper labour than Greeks), therefore the rates of unemployed Greeks increase, which contributes to the increase of the criminality rates.' Therefore, Maria presents, in her own way, what Guibernau (2007) describes above in relation to the negative mindset against immigrants caused by the fact that they provide cheap labour, which is deemed by the indigenous population as the reason of the increased native working-

class unemployment. As far as statistics are concerned, the majority of immigrants that lived in Greece, as of 2001, were Albanians standing at 56%. As Iosifides et al. (2007) explain, the most important reasons Albanians migrated to Greece was for work or for reuniting with a family member that had already migrated. The main employment sectors that the majority of the Albanian immigrants worked at were the primary sector, construction, the food/restaurant sector, or personal services. The key factors that led Albanians to choose Greece over other countries, briefly summarized by Iosifides et al., were: the ease of entry, the socio-economic and political changes in Albania during the 1990s, the geographical proximity to Greece, and the demand for an inexpensive and flexible labour force in various sectors of the Greek economy, such as in construction and agriculture (p. 1344).

However, despite Maria's efforts to convince Smaragda and Natasa that 'those Albanians are to blame for everything', both of them discard her theory and do not express a negative opinion against immigrants, and by extension Albanians. They may not present a reasoning as to why they do not agree with Maria, but their friendly, or at least not hostile, mindset towards immigrants, indicates a dichotomy when it comes the attitude of the 1990s Greeks to foreigners. This dichotomy can be also observed in *Constantine's and Helen's (Konstantinou kai Elenis)/Κωνσταντίνου και Ελένης* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000), episodes 10 and 13, in which a number of characters do not present hostility towards immigrants, while others think negatively against. In detail, a substantial part of episode 10 revolves around the endeavours of a Romanian woman, Tatiana (Katerina Sazli), as she tries to get accepted and make a living in Greece. Once she gets hired at the bar where Helen (Eleni Rantou) and Peggy (Maria Lekaki) work, due to her appearance (tall, blonde and slim) and negative stereotypes around her nationality, the characters initially assume that Tatiana's original profession was prostitution. They soon find out that she used to work as a social worker (marriage consultant) back in Romania. As already mentioned, there is an apparent contrast in the ways some of the characters think and behave towards her, as opposed to others. On the one hand, Helen, Nikolas (Stergios Nenes) and Peggy, who are low-paid employees at the bar, try to help her out - Helen even accepts to take her in, as Tatiana was homeless for a brief period of time. On the other, Constantine (Charis Romas), Helen's housemate, a university lecturer of Byzantine studies and descendant of a wealthy family, does not approve of Tatiana. The same situation takes place in episode 13, when Helen befriends an illegal Albanian immigrant, Pirro (Tasos Palatzidis), and hides him from the police, who is after him because he stole some salami from a supermarket. Constantine, on the other hand, insists that Pirro gets handed in to the police, while his behaviour towards him is sarcastic and diminishing throughout the episode.

Nevertheless, despite portrayals of Greek characters who hold a positive attitude towards foreigners, - such as Teti in *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)* who gets into a relationship with a Japanese man; Smaragda and Natasa in *Just Us (Emeis ki Emeis)* who do not agree with Maria's negative mindset towards immigrants; Helen, Peggy and Nikolas in *Constantine's and Helen's (Konstantinou kai Elenis)* who are friendly and accommodating towards Tatiana and Pirro - the majority of the examples analysed in this section indicate that racism and xenophobia were prominent characteristics within the Greek society of the 1990s. Through the investigation of moments where Greek characters, directly or indirectly, differentiate themselves from the 'other', a sense of superiority in regard to their national identity seems to emerge. This sense of superiority is then utilized by the creators of the series to produce comedic effect, by satirizing the Greeks' fears and anxieties towards foreigners (such as in episode 63 of *The Three Charites*, where Olga interrogates Mohamed), on the one hand, or exemplifying their pride towards their Greek identity (such as Korina in episode 14 of *Crimes*, who compares Greece with Burkina Faso), on the other. The countries or individuals who receive racism from the Greek characters in the series come from places such as eastern Europe, the Balkans, Asia, Afrika and the Arabic world. Yet, there are a couple of instances (in episode 4 of *The Three Charites* and episode 7 of *With Two Mothers*) that Greek characters indirectly show admiration towards England and Germany - western places, financially and politically stronger than Greece. This might indicate an underlying sense of inferiority when it comes to Greece's endeavours to establish itself, culturally and financially, within the western world. This sense of inferiority can be observed in some of the examples analysed in the following section, which focuses on presenting stereotypes that, in this case, 'describe' the Greeks and not the foreigners. In other words, the following examples explore moments within the comedy series examined in which Greek characters commend on how they see themselves.

4.1.4 Stereotyping 'the Greeks'

According to Guibernau (2007, pp. 10-11), 'stereotypes' have an origin and can refer to a collection of characteristics that are thought to be shared by individuals who belong to specific nationalities. 'Stereotyping', on the other hand, is the practice of picking and frequently exaggerating the distinctive features of certain nationals. For Hodgkinson (2011, p. 201), the ways in which ethnic minorities have been represented in media texts have tended to be stereotyped, as observed by the examples above, producing a restricted and generalised image of such populations' lives and identities. As for Pickering (2001, p. 4), if these stereotypes are repeated often enough, they end up liable to render uniform everyone associated with a

particular feature. ‘Stereotyping reduces, essentializes, naturalizes and fixes ‘difference’’, argues Hall (1997) and ‘tends to occur when there are gross inequalities of power’ (pp. 257-258). Thus, as shown in the previous section, it is subordinate and minority groups who tend to be affected the most, both in terms of the pervasiveness of the stereotypes and the depth of their impact. However, according to Hodgkinson (2011, p. 201), ‘media stereotypes of powerful groups undoubtedly exist’ as well. The following examples, therefore, consist of scenes in which Greek characters ‘stereotype’ themselves, by expressing mostly negative insights about their nationality and shared behavioural characteristics.

In episode 20 of *The Unacceptable (Oi Aparadektoi)/Οι Απαράδεκτοι* (MEGA, 1991-1993), the characters decide to compose a song and perform it at the Eurovision Song Contest representing Greece. However, they struggle to come up with an appropriate song that they can identify themselves with. During a brainstorming meeting, Dimitra (Dimitra Papadopoulou) claims that the Greeks have always been characterised by infighting and discord. Spiros (Spiros Papadopoulos) adds upon that stating that the Greeks are also massive *know-it-alls*. Therefore, the only way to achieve writing a song for Eurovision is to become good team players and collaborate effectively, as according to Vlassis (Vlassis Bonatsos): ‘People united, never defeated!’ The song they finally submit, which they rehearse dressed in togas, consist of various lines which describe how Greeks see themselves. Some of its lyrics are: ‘We are a team, Greece is our country / We are nice and historically *fatal* / We gave the lights (we enlightened the others) / Greece is not a chicken (coward) / Long live the teams! / Once a *high* team built the Parthenon / We *made* Aristotle and barrel wine.’ Nevertheless, the episode ends with the national broadcaster announcing that Greece will not compete at Eurovision that year due to the low quality of the candidate songs.

Continuing with *Crimes (Eglimata)/Εγκλήματα* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000), episode 57 contains sequences of flashbacks and projections into the future. During a projection-into-the-future part, Soso (Keti Konstantinou) and Alekos’ (Kostas Koklas) yet unborn child is a teenager and studies history with his dad. Alekos examines his son’s, Telis (Nikos Poursanidis), knowledge on the Battle of Alamana (a battle between Greeks and Ottomans that took place on the 23rd of April 1821, in which Greeks were defeated) and Telis recounts: ‘Look, generally speaking, the battle of Alamana took place in April 1821. It was an unfortunate moment in the history of both Greeks and Turks, because the two nations, instead of choosing a diplomatic route to solve their differences, preferred the use of raw violence.’ Hearing this moderate point of view about that particular historical event, which constitutes a significant part of the Greek revolution of the early 19th century contributing to the demolition of the Ottoman empire and

the creation of Greece and other nations, Alekos asks infuriated: ‘What’s all these? What idiot teaches you these things?’ Telis answers calmly: ‘It says so in the book. The books have changed, they’re not as you remember them.’ Alekos, fuming, goes on asking his son how Athanasios Diakos (a Greek commander) was executed after that battle: ‘How did Athanasios Diakos die?’ to which Telis answers: ‘I don’t know, maybe from old age.’ Alekos replies even more angrily: ‘Old age? Is this what they teach you? Athanasios Diakos was impaled by the antichrists (meaning the Turks).’ Telis, with an ‘innocent’ look wonders: ‘Maybe it was an accident?’ driving his dad crazy: ‘Telis, I’m going to beat you up!’ Telis, however, repels the threat by saying: ‘Alekos, you are very unprogressive! You cultivate intolerance and fanaticism!’ At that moment, Soso, who is Telis’ mother and Alekos’ wife, enters the room and adds: ‘That’s right! All your life, this is what you’ve been cultivating, instead of cultivating tomatoes!’ Alekos desperately exclaims: ‘I am Greek!’ to which Soso sarcastically answers: ‘Get lost from here, you Turk-seed! If you’re Greek, then what are we? Mongols?’

In this scene, we see Alekos, who represents the ‘patriotic’ Greek, being accused by his son for being unprogressive, intolerant, and fanatic, while his wife calls him a ‘Turk-seed’ - a characterization through which she implies that since the Greeks lived for around four hundred years under the Ottoman empire, his ‘Greek genetics’ must have been affected by the ‘Turkish.’ Telis may have indeed misrepresented historical events and their national and political significance, but his action is an opportunity for the scriptwriter, Lefteris Papapetrou, to bring to the surface and satirize some negative stereotypes around the personality of Greeks of the 1990s, such as unprogressiveness, intolerance, patriotic fanaticism. Such a negative stereotyping can be also found in episode 25 of *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)/Δύο Ξένοι* (MEGA, 1997-1999), when Flora (Chryssoula Diavati), while speaking on the phone with Konstantinos (Nikos Seryanopoulos), who has lied that he is currently in London, says to him: ‘English people are honest people! We, Greeks, are the only crooks left in the European union.’ Even though Greeks, in this example, are stereotyped as crooks, there is an underlying suggestion in Flora’s tone that such a negative characterization is unfair, as ‘crookedness’ can be met in other nationalities as well.

Apart from the stereotypes around the ‘character’ of the Greeks, there are instances that reference stereotypes on their mannerisms, habits, and everyday-life behaviours. For example, in episode 14 of *The Penthouse (To Retire)/Το Πετιπέ* (MEGA, 1990-1992), during a normal day working at the office, Katerina (Katerina Gioulaki) points out to her colleagues, Kostas (Giannis Nezis) and Eleni (Kleri Katsantoni), that she has noticed that people around her constantly complain and nag. In particular, she says to Eleni: ‘The other day, when you returned

from your sick-leave and found all the documents that we sent out to be wrong, didn't you grumble?' and Eleni answers: 'But they were indeed the wrong ones!' Katerina, however, disagrees: 'No, they weren't, but you, as an original Greek, like to grumble! Because all Greeks grumble! Because all Greeks find wrong what the others do (meaning their fellow Greeks) and right only what they personally do! Because all Greeks are never satisfied with anything!' Eleni, not convinced, asks Katerina to stop exaggerating, yet Katerina insists on her opinion: 'No exaggeration here! If you ask a Greek *how are you?* are you under the impression that he's going to reply *fine thank you, all great, thank goodness, fantastic?* No! He'll say he's doing very badly. For example: How are you?' to which Eleni answers: 'I'm so and so.' Katerina, proud to have proven her point, continues: 'You see! The one *so* means well and the other one bad!' Eleni, in order to make Katerina realize that she does the same thing, asks her: 'How are you doing then?' Taken by surprise, Katerina replies: 'I? Badly, icily and topsy-turvy! My situation doesn't count in this case! I wasn't talking about my nagging; I was talking about other people's nagging. Well, after all I'm not a Congolese! I'm a Greek too!' Taking into account Guibernau (2007), Hodkinson (2011), and Pickering's (2001) theories on stereotyping presented earlier in this section, picking and exaggerating the distinctive features of certain nationals. producing a restricted and generalised image of such populations' lives and identities. If these stereotypes are repeated often enough, they end up liable to render uniform everyone associated with a particular feature.

Additional behavioural characteristics of the 'everyday' Greek can be pointed out in episode 107 of *Just Us (Emeis ki emeis)*. In detail, Champos (Tasos Perzikianidis) finds out through a TV-show that he has a 'lost' sister, who, when she was born, was given for adoption in the USA. Once they reunite, his new 'American' sister, Booboo de Havilland (Vana Partheniadou), spends some days at his place and gets acquainted with some of his relatives and friends. She receives a warm welcome from all, while feasts and dinners are organised in her honour. Her 'new' cousin, Antonia (Maria Kanellopoulou), spends a whole day cooking various traditional dishes, while the rest try their best to 'please' her - including forcing a tulumba (a syrupy dessert) into her mouth without her consent. Once she manages to swallow the tulumba, Booboo (who, when finding out of her Greek descent from her dying foster mother, learns Greek at an institution in the US, before searching for her biological family) says: 'Champos, next time, please, let me choose what I want to eat and when to eat it, okay?' Apart from this incident, which indicates an override of personal boundaries when it comes to 'taking care' of other people, she points out that Greeks overdo it with eating meat and fried food. She screams when some of them start smoking in the living room and threatens to call

the police. The episode continues with a sequence of instances that depict Booboo's 'suffocation' in her new environment and her struggle to adapt to the Greek way of life. For example, she gets frustrated when characters pay her visits without prior notice, when they just enter Champos' flat (where she resides) without ringing the doorbell first, or when they touch her (e.g. on the arm) as a sign of rapport from their side. According to her words, such things are 'very annoying and very primitive.' Yet, Antonia expresses quite a different opinion on the matter saying that: 'If for you touching between two people is primitive and annoying, for us is very warm and very humane'; while on the issue of visiting without prior notice and entering houses without knocking first, Natasa (Natasa Manisali) says: 'We don't do such things here (prior notices and ringing doorbells)! We just open the door and enter because we have nothing to hide from one another! We're a nice bunch/company!' The episode ends with the characters getting notified by the TV-show, which brought Booboo and Champos together, that Champos is not her brother. She is happy to find out that her actual brother 'thankfully' belongs to a rich and high-class family. She uses the word 'thankfully', not only for the financial wealth her 'new' family possesses, but to imply that she does not expect to experience the same behaviours she did with the 'everyday' Greeks.

Among the numerous and diverse 'positive' and 'negative' stereotypical characteristics demonstrated in the example above, we can detect that Greeks are 'stereotypically' portrayed to have a special relationship with food and cooking, as well. Throughout the series examined, Greek cuisine is presented as an integral part of Greek culture, playing a significant role not only in the 'everyday experience' of the characters, but in their 'image' as a nation to the rest of the world. An example on this subject can be found in episode 2 of *The Penthouse (To Retire)*. In detail, Katerina (Katerina Gioulaki), who works as a talk-show presenter, hosts a politician at that day's show, who expresses his interest in marrying an American woman, since her nationality is associated with the White House and the Pentagon - places of significant political 'importance' according to his words. Katerina, however, advises him to marry a 'typical' Greek brunet woman, especially if she is a good cook, as 'dolmadakia' (a delicacy made of vine leaves) make a significant contribution to local politics. She brings as an example Marika Mitsotakis (wife of the then-prime minister, Konstantinos Mitsotakis), who was famous within the political party, New Democracy, for her dolmadakia (according to Katerina). The indirect sarcasm, in this scene, derives from the fact that, while the global 'reputation' of countries, like the US, is shaped around their financial, military and political power, what 'humble', 'inferior' Greece can offer to the world is its cuisine.

Another example, which indicates that Greek cuisine may constitute the ‘signature’ of Greece and its culture to foreigners, takes place in episode 50 of *Crimes (Eglimata)*, when Korina (Maria Kavoyianni) briefly comes across an English woman. She very excitedly introduces herself in English, unsuccessfully imitating the British accent, by saying: ‘Oh hello! My name is Korina! Welcome to our country! This is the country of moussaka, choriatiiki (Greek salad) and feta!’ As we can see, the first thing Korina does to introduce her country is exemplifying its cuisine. In the next second, however, her warm welcoming changes into aggressiveness. She grabs the English woman by the collar and shouts: ‘GIVE US BACK THE PARTHENON MARBLES!’ This second intense moment, apart from satirizing the stereotypical ‘fiery temperament’ of Greeks, which very quickly can change from ‘overly’ welcoming to hostile, attempts to pass a political message about the unsolved issue of the return of the Parthenon marbles from the British Museum to Athens.

Besides the ‘stereotypical’ relationship of Greeks with food and cooking, the comedy series of the 1990s also offer a plethora of examples that portray the impact of Greek music on all aspects of the ‘everyday’ life and, by extension, on the ‘stereotypical’ character of Greeks. For example, in episode 57 of *Crimes (Eglimata)*, Korina (Maria Kavoyianni) is about to marry someone against her will. The day before the wedding she dances at home along with a friend, Michalis (Stavros Nikolaidis), to express her pain. They dance holding each other’s hand, with the help of a white handkerchief, to an old, sad but upbeat *rebetiko* song [*rebetiko* being an urban Greek music genre that emerged in the late 19th century and flourished after the 1950s (Holst-Warhaft, 2002)] called *Εύχομαι και στα δικά σου/Efhome ke sta dika sou* [loosely translated as *I wish the best for your wedding/marriage, too* (by Marika Ninou, 1954)]. Similarly, in episode 58 of *Dolce Vita/Ντόλτσε Βίτα* (MEGA, 1995-1997), Loukas (Pavlos Orkopoulos) finds out that Christina (Anna Panagiotopoulou), the woman that he was in love with for years, though they had never been together, has an affair with a man half her age - her ex-son-in-law Antonis (Thanassis Efthimiadis). He is drunk and devastated at a Greek tavern along with a couple of friends, Aspasia (Maria Kavoyianni) and Manolis (Isidoros Stamoulis). At some point, a *rebetiko* song called *Βρέχει φωτιά στη στράτα μου/Vrehi fotia sti strata mou* (*It’s raining fire on my way*), by Stratos Dionisiou (1970), is heard on the radio and Aspasia urges him: ‘Come on Loukas! Dance to forget! Bring wine, the man is in pain!’ Loukas gets up and dances *zeibekiko* [a solo dance based on improvised steps, mostly performed by men (Economou, 2018)] to express his pain, while his friends, kneeled on the floor, support him by clapping their hands to the music. These two scenes, which exemplify the importance of popular music in the everyday life of Greeks and the shaping of their national identity, indicate

the necessity to explore and analyse further how Greek music and other cultural practices have been represented in Greek comedy series of the 1990s.

4.1.5 The Greek national identity and ‘Popular Culture’

‘Popular culture’ has been defined as the culture that is prominent among the ‘people’ and is particularly relevant to the construction of national identity (Edensor, 2002, p. 14). According to Storey (1993, p. 7), the term ‘popular culture’ represents a broad spectrum of meanings - from that which is ‘widely favoured or well-liked by many people’ to those ‘inferior’ cultural forms and practices that are left over by ‘high culture.’ It is a term often synonymous to ‘mass culture’ - a culture inherently commercial and homogeneous, with elements of dangerous, hypnotic, and addictive tendencies (Edensor, 2002, p. 13). The term ‘high culture’, on the other hand, encompasses whatever art form or cultural practice is considered worthy of study. In Arnold’s (1993, p. 79) words: ‘to make the best that has been known and thought in the world current everywhere’ - an intention inspired by the ‘study of perfection.’ ‘Mass or popular culture’ may not only constitute the opposite of ‘high culture’, but it is often set apart from the term ‘folk culture’ - a term that embodies whatever cultural expression encourages a sense of belonging, of knowing one’s place in an organic world, a pre-urban *gemeinschaft* where one’s identity is a part of a deeply embedded and unquestioning way of living, anchored in time and space (Edensor, 2002, p. 13). The examination of examples that reference the subjects of ‘high’, ‘popular’ and ‘folk culture’ can offer us the opportunity to understand the complexities of the various and often contradictory stimuli that have influenced and shaped contemporary Greek culture - and by extension, contemporary Greek national identity. The following section, therefore, presents and analyses scenes in which characters physically perform some sort of cultural practice - such as singing, dancing, playing theatre - or verbally express their views around cultural practices.

Starting with episode 17 of *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)/Δύο Ξένοι* (MEGA, 1997-1999), we see Konstantinos (Nikos Seryanopoulos), a drama-school teacher and theatre director, sitting at his desk listening to Beethoven’s *Ode to Joy*, while his housekeeper, Flora (Chryssoula Diavati), a middle aged, uneducated and ‘unfortunate’ woman enters the room shouting: ‘Konstantinos! Konstantinos! Turn this thing off, my boy! The neighbours will come out to ask who died!’ Konstantinos, finding her reaction amusing, says: ‘Flora, what you’re listening to is a legend of classical music! [...] Ludwig van Beethoven’ to which Flora answers: ‘Yes, right, I know him. He is that guy from Eurovision. [...] Come on now, turn it off, I can’t stand this thing in my ears!’ Konstantinos, laughing, enlightens her by saying: ‘This, which

you cannot stand in your ears, is a hymn to joy. It's a music that praises the human emotions. It's a music that makes you feel to the greatest level the pain, the joy, the love!' However, Flora with a calm, emotional tone contradicts him: 'My boy, if there is no taqsim [a melodic musical improvisation that precedes the main song (Racy, 2000)], strumming and baglamas (the Greek version of a plucked string instrument used in Turkish, Arabesque, Armenian and other ethnic music) you cannot feel to the greatest level the pain, the joy, the love, because 'longing/pain' needs D major [a semitone used in Greek songs of the 20th century 'popular culture' with instruments like bouzouki and baglamas (Ordoulidis, 2011)].' In this scene, we observe that the characters are in the middle of two very different forces of musical influences that coexist in modern Greek society. On the one hand, these influences derive from Europe (classical music), in Konstantinos' case with his deep appreciation of Beethoven's work, and on the other, from Eastern cultures that greatly impacted Greek popular music, as we can see in Flora's case. Yet, it should be noted that Flora, as a character, represents the 'uneducated mass', the 'everyday' person, while Konstantinos, a drama-teacher, theatre director and son of an upper-class family, represents the 'intellectual', the 'elitist', the 'artist.' Therefore, in this scene, there is an indirect, yet apparent reference to Edensor (2002), Storey (1993), and Arnold's (1993) theories on the dichotomy between 'high culture' (represented by Konstantinos) and 'popular culture' (represented by Flora).

This dichotomy becomes even more obvious in episode 49 of the same series, when Konstantinos' team of drama students is invited by the Greek Air Force to perform for some aircraftmen the ancient Greek tragedy *The Trojan Women*, produced by Euripides in 425 BC. Throughout the play, empty paper cups and other rubbish are thrown at the actors on stage, who, despite that, are eager to continue performing their parts. The aircraftmen bored, uninterested and unfamiliar with the play, demand Charoula (Despina Vandis), the singer that was entertaining them a moment ago with popular contemporary Greek songs, to come back on stage. The warrant officer (Giannis Bostantzoglou), who is not educated on this kind of theatre art either, tries to convince the aircraftmen that: 'Art is needed!', though he does not know why that is the case. Konstantinos, in an attempt to enlighten them, says that: 'Art is the purgatory of our soul that can help us win in the battle against the mass alienation from the self.' Yet, despite the actors' endeavours to complete the performance, they end up, later in the episode, grabbing some Greek music instruments, like bouzouki, and start playing popular songs to entertain the aircraftmen. The aircraftmen, having ridiculed Greek 'high' art, get up to dance to 'cheap' contemporary Greek music. Therefore, in this example, 'popular culture' is not only presented as 'widely favoured', 'well-liked by many people' (Storey, 1993) and

commercial, as described earlier in the section, but also as stimulating addictive tendencies (Edensor, 2002). In this case, the addictive tendencies evoked by ‘popular/mass culture’ are portrayed by the aircraftmen’s disrespectful, dismissive, even violent, reaction to what was presented to them as ‘high’ art, followed by their passionate demand for commercial music, and peaked by their euphoric ‘release’ when commercial music finally starts playing and they party.

This battle between ‘popular’ and ‘high culture’ might have been repeatedly portrayed, as observed throughout this section. However, ‘folk culture’, and its relationship with ‘popular’ and ‘high culture’, has also been showcased, as seen in the following examples, adding yet another layer of complexity when it comes to the representation of contemporary Greek culture in the 1990s comedy series examined. For instance, in episode 24 of *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)*, Konstantinos, while being at a hotel in the island of Spetses along with his secret lover, Marina (Evelina Papoulia), who is a morning TV-show host, a song by Greek singer Haris Alexiou is heard on the radio, and the couple starts a conversation about music. In detail, Marina asks Konstantinos: ‘What sort of music did you use to listen to when you were younger?’ He answers passionately: ‘Music! Opera, classical music - not pre-classical, everyone says that - Byzantine hymns, traditional music of African tribes, symphonic rock.’ Sarcastically she responds: ‘Wow, you were indeed dancing on the tables! No Greek music then?’, but Konstantinos corrects her: ‘No, I used to listen to Greek music too, I’m not a snob. I listened to Chatzidakis and Theodorakis [two of the most prominent Greek composers of the 20th century (Orfanos, 1999; Holst-Warhaft, 2002)] when I wanted to approach the *logic of the masses*. I don’t dare asking what you used to listen to. I can imagine.’ Yet, she very proudly answers: ‘I knew by heart all the *demotic* songs of my area [the term *demotic* refers to the traditional/folklore Greek songs dated back to the medieval era (Kallimopoulou, 2016)]. I also listened to *laiko* [a term which translates as ‘the song of the people’, a popular Greek music genre that flourished in the mid-20th century (Economou, 2018)], I went to fairs and concerts.’ On the subject of concerts, Konstantinos confesses that his mother never permitted him to attend, because she believed left-wing elements (ideologies) had started to infiltrate into those kinds of events (see section 4.2.2). Finding out that he did not use to go to fairs and concert, Marina presumes: ‘So, this mean, bouzouki, baglamas (musical instruments that feature in *laiko*/popular songs) and clarinets (musical instrument that features in *demotic*/traditional songs) were out of the question for you!’ Through the dialogue of these characters, we can detect that what represents ‘high culture’ (e.g., classical music, Byzantine hymns) does not just collide with ‘popular culture’ (*laiko*) but with ‘folk culture’ (*demotic*) as well. Alongside that,

this scene explicitly presents us with the terms *laiko* and *demotic*, two Greek music genres further analysed later in this section. The term *laiko*, which means ‘song of the people’, refers to contemporary Greek ‘popular’ music (from the 20th century onwards) - thus, ‘popular culture’. On the other hand, the term *demotic*, which refers to traditional Greek songs and dances deriving from centuries of musical practice, represents the Greek ‘folk culture’.

As observed in *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)*, ‘high’, ‘popular’ and ‘folk culture’ are presented as opposing forces that characterize modern Greek culture highlighting its non-homogeneity in the field of music and other art forms. An example from another series that provides a similar lens into the cultural complexity of Greece exploring its non-homogeneity, especially in regard to ‘high’ and ‘popular culture’, can be found in episode 11 of *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)/Οι Απαράδεκτοι* (MEGA, 1991-1993). In detail, the episode starts with Dimitra (Dimitra Papadopoulou) taking her morning coffee listening and dancing to a *laiko* song by the singer Litsa Diamanti, called *Λέει-λέει/Leei-leei* (*He says-he says*, 1990). The song has clear eastern elements and is considered a product of light entertainment. Dimitra turns the volume of the stereo system all the way up upsetting their neighbours, Vlassis (Vlassis Bonatsos) and Giannis (Giannis Bezos). Soon, her husband, Spiros (Spiros Papadopoulos), enters the room and demands that she turns that song off. However, Dimitra shouts back at him: ‘Stop oppressing me! This is how I have fun! [...] These are the songs that I like!’ to which Spiros responds: ‘You like these songs because you are stupid!’ and turns the music off himself, while Dimitra calls him: ‘Fascist!’ Later in the episode, Spiros, after a fight he has with his boss (Alexandros Koliopoulos) at the advertising company where he works, decides to invite him over for dinner to make up. Before the gathering, Spiros buys a replica of an ancient amphora (type of container) in order to offer it as a present to his boss. Once Dimitra sees the present, she disapproves as she thinks it is a carafe: ‘Why did you bring this disgusting thing in the house?’ to which Spiros answers: ‘This is no carafe! It is a replica of an amphora that was found in Troezen (in Peloponnese), dated from 1500 BC.’ Dimitra, considering the artefact junk due to its old age, says: ‘That old! We’re out of our minds! Take this out of here. We can’t have people seeing this junk in the house!’ Spiros infuriated asks: ‘You dare to say that you don’t like this gorgeous piece of art?’ and Dimitra proudly answers: ‘Yes sir! I do dare to say that I don’t like it, because you exist when you express your opinion without being ashamed of your choice!’ - a statement that leaves Spiros speechless. The episode finishes with Spiros’ boss getting tired of listening to Norma’s *Casta Diva* by Bellini, performed by Nana Mouskouri (1989), during the dinner - an aria that Spiros was informed was his favourite. Instead, he (the boss) and Dimitra end up having great fun singing *laika* (plural) songs for the rest of the

evening. This incident demonstrates that the dynamics of Greek ‘popular culture’ have ‘prevailed’ over ‘high culture’ in the hearts of most of the characters in their everyday experience. Comedy (comedic effect) is created, here, by depicting the ‘battle’ between ‘high’ and ‘popular culture’; in particular, by mocking, on the one hand, the resistance ‘high culture’ holds as it endeavours to maintain its significance, and on the other, by satirizing the rebellious, revolutionary ‘nature’ of ‘popular culture’ in its attempt to gain more ground.

A similar situation takes place in episode 130 of *Just Us (Emeis ki emeis)/Εμείς κι Εμείς* (MEGA, 1994-1998). However, in this case, it is not ‘high culture’ that gets ‘replaced’ by ‘popular culture’, but ‘folk culture.’ In detail, episode 130 is an Easter special, which portrays many Greek customs of the season. For example, the characters prepare a big feast in their neighbourhood, with some of the traditional delicacies being a whole roasted lamb on a spit, red dyed eggs, tsoureki (traditional Greek Easter bread) etc. After they have eaten, they dance in a circle to some traditional Pontian dances (see section 4.1.6) accompanied by a group of professional Pontian dancers and musicians, who are dressed in the traditional Pontian costumes. However, after the dancers leave, a number of popular singers of the 1990s turn up. The characters, then, start to entrain themselves with contemporary, highly commercial Greek songs of the era, which have nothing to do with the traditional sounds of the Pontian songs that were performed few moments ago. This scene indicates, therefore, that contemporary Greeks do maintain a strong connection with their national traditions, old customs, and folklore practices (*demotic* music and dancing), yet elements of ‘popular culture’ have achieved a catalytic impact to their national cultural expressions. This alteration or, better yet, ‘enrichment’ of their cultural expressions is a phenomenon that, either intentionally or unintentionally, got (re)presented in the Comedy series of the 1990s. Therefore, this constitutes necessary the examination of Greek ‘popular culture’ as an important element of Greek national culture and identity.

As Smith (1991, p. 77) asserts, national symbols, traditions, customs, ceremonies (such as the practising of Easter customs and traditional dancing in the example above, episode 130 of *Just Us*) may indeed be some of the most potent and durable representational aspects of national culture, as they embody the basic concepts of a nation, making them visible and distinct for every member. However, according to Edensor (2002, p. 9), traditions hold now less weight, as they are commodified, have become part of popular mediascapes or are increasingly being diffused amongst competing stimuli, as portrayed in the case above with the characters entertaining themselves with commercial Greek music of the era after having practised a series of old customs beforehand. He also claims that the spectacular, the ‘pre-

modern' folk and the historic (that is 'folk culture' and 'high culture') has been 'overwhelming' (Edensor, 2002, p. 10) - a claim, which seems to be case for some characters as analysed earlier in the section: in episode 49 of *Two Strangers*, where the aircraftmen get tired of the ancient Greek play and demand contemporary Greek songs; and in episode 11 of *The Unacceptables*, where Dimitra disapproves of the replica of the ancient Greek amphora, while Spiros' boss (along with Dimitra) ends up discarding Bellini's *Casta Diva* (which he appreciates) and prefers to be entertained with *laika* songs instead. In all three examples, therefore, 'popular culture' (in these cases, contemporary Greek music) appears to have prevailed over 'high culture' (ancient Greek theatre/sculpture, and European classical music influences) and 'folk culture' (Pontian music/dances, Easter customs), and takes centre stage in the spectrum of the 1990s national culture of Greece, and by extension, Greek identity.

According to Guibernau (2007), the formation of national identity is a complicated process in which individuals identify themselves with a collection of symbols and traditions ('high' and 'folk culture') that have the capacity to unify and reinforce the sense of community. In fact, for Guibernau, all groups require symbols and rituals to thrive, preserve cohesion, and reaffirm the collective ideas that they generate. However, this identification process entails a continual flow between people and symbols/traditions, in the sense that people must constantly re-create and attach new meaning to previously established symbols/traditions in response to the changing conditions through which the community's life unfolds. Thus, tradition must be reinvented and continuously actualized (pp. 31-32). As Edensor (2002) puts it, national identity and culture cannot be defined only by that which is consciously presented as 'symbolic' ('high' and 'folk culture'). For him, 'high' and 'folk culture' are, after all, ingrained in unreflexive patterns of social life and assumptions about how a country's cultural identity 'should' be, and hence, they obscure the everyday experience of its people, the mundane, the cultural commonsensical practices and 'the popular' distributed by 'mass culture.' So, he asserts that discourses (such as academic analysis) around the shaping of national identities that emphasise only on 'high' and 'folk culture' excluding the significance of 'popular' or 'mass culture' lead to underrepresentation. He acknowledges, on the one hand, that artists, writers, historians, scholars, and folklorists have undoubtedly contributed to 'official' and 'high culture', to education systems and public exhibitions of nations. Yet, on the other, as he suggests, in modern times, discourses around national culture need to incorporate a variety of other cultural producers, such as pop stars, film and television producers, advertisers, tabloid hacks, fashion designers, athletes, as well as 'popular cultural practices including dancing, sports-spectatorship, common pastimes, holidaying and touring' (p. 10). He notes that attempts were

definitely made by elites and intellectuals, throughout history, to create a nationally codified body of knowledge which prioritised ‘high culture’ in order to shape and represent national culture. Nonetheless, he stresses that once a nation is established as a common-sense entity, in the context of modernity, mass media and the means that can create and disseminate ‘popular culture’ dramatically expand. These tools, then, largely escape the control of the state, being distributed through commercial and less formal networks; - all made possible by the mobilities caused by advances in communication technologies (p. 4).

Nevertheless, episode 57 of the *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)* offers us an alternative and quite unique moment in which ‘folk culture’ manages to ‘prevail’ over ‘popular culture’, unlike the rest of the examples analysed in this section, and despite Smith (1991) and Edensor’s (2002) theories about the prevalence of ‘popular culture’ over ‘high’ and ‘folk culture’. In detail, Apostolis, a gay secondary character, played by Alexandros Rigas, who is the director of the series and the one of the two scriptwriters (alongside Dimitris Apostolou), has a one-night stand with an American soldier. Once Konstantinos and Marina find out about it, they say to him ironically: ‘You’ve become a traitor, don’t you understand! You went (had sex) with your enemy! You used to be an anti-American! Till yesterday, you considered them murderers, the bastards that control the planet! And now you went (had sex) with the worst tribe ever. During it, did you think at all of Cyprus, of the Kurds, of the Blacks? Shame on you!’ Once they are done telling Apostolis off, a dream sequence starts depicting a group of American soldiers dancing to the soundtrack of *Full Metal Jacket* (Kubrick, 1987). They are observed by a group of Greek soldiers, which consists of the main cast of the series dressed in army uniforms (this means that some of them are women, in contrast to the American group which consists only of men). Once the American soldiers finish with their ‘silly’ performance, the Greeks get up and proudly sing *Πότε θα κάνει ζαστεριά/Pote tha kanei xasteria (When will the night sky be clear and starlit)*, a *rizitiko* (Cretan folk) song whose origins are lost in the medieval era, though it became particularly popular in the 20th century. Contrary to the American soldiers’ performance, the Greek soldiers stand still and serious while singing this dramatic song, which speaks about tyranny, war, and struggle. At some point, we see Marina’s eyes water due to the sincere emotional thrill that this patriotic folk song evokes.

The nostalgic celebration of Greek ‘folk culture’, which is being obliterated by contemporary ‘mass culture’ - in this case, the American ‘mass culture’ as a result of globalization (see section 4.1.2) - is prominent in this scene. It is a scene that highly valorises Greek ‘folk culture’ constituting it as probably the most authentic reflection of Greek culture deeply ingrained in the hearts of the characters. Its ‘mythical’, uncommercial, and time-

honoured essence represents what is considered to be the ‘true nature’ of the Greeks, and Greekness in general; - as opposed to the external cultural influences, and the various internal forces generated by the expansion of Greek ‘popular culture’ and its dynamics. However, as observed in the rest of the scenes of this section, contemporary Greek identity has been highly characterized by ‘popular culture.’ Thus, ‘popular culture’ should be taken into account in any academic discourse around Greek culture and Greek national identity. That is because, due to ‘popular culture’, the cultural ingredients that shape national identity have proven to be increasingly mediated, highly polysemic, contested, and always subject to change. As Edensor (2002) puts it, culture is negotiated, open to dialogue and creative expression, and impacted by the contexts in which it is created and experienced. Hence, our sense of national identity is not fixed, but rather ‘dynamic and dialogic, found in the constellations of a huge cultural matrix of images, ideas, spaces, things, discourses, and practices’ (p. 17).

4.1.6 The Greek national identity and the sense of belonging: the case of *Just Us (Emeis ki Emeis)*

According to Guibernau (2007), one of the most important dimensions of national identity, alongside the historical and the cultural dimensions, is the psychological dimension. In the previous sections, we explored aspects of the historical dimension of the Greek national identity by analysing scenes in which characters try to reconnect with their history and roots, or ‘compare’ their history to the history of other national groups in order to differentiate themselves from ‘the other’ - a necessary process for the ‘marking’ of one’s own unique sense of national identity. The study then proceeded with investigating the cultural dimension of the Greek national identity as portrayed in the series selected, specifically through characters discussing or practising ‘culture’. This section, therefore, is dedicated on exploring the Greek national identity through its psychological dimension, which according to Guibernau (2007), emerges from the awareness of belonging to a nation through the felt closeness shared by people who belong to it. As she explains, such closeness might be dormant for years before bursting to the surface anytime the nation is confronted with an external or internal enemy - actual, potential, or imagined - endangering its people, prosperity, traditions and culture, territory, international status, or sovereignty. She notes that throughout the world, there are innumerable examples of individuals willing to make sacrifices and eventually die for their country, proving that, at least for them, national identity is real and worth fighting for. Thus, the belief in a shared ancestry produces a sense of belonging, which in turn generates loyalty and social coherence among fellow nationals (pp. 11-12). In fact:

‘The internalisation of national identity results in individuals charging it emotionally,’ and therefore, ‘in certain circumstances, sentiments of love of the nation and hatred of those threatening it are intensely felt by fellow nationals’ (Guibernau, 2007, p. 12).

Indeed, we have already seen examples of characters getting emotionally charged as a result of their love and pride for Greece, such as Marina in episode 57 of *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)*, analysed at the end of the previous section. However, amongst the series examined, *Just Us (Emeis ki emeis)/Εμείς κι Εμείς* (MEGA, 1994-1998) is the one that offers a plethora of moments that reference what Guibernau (2007) describes as ‘loyalty’ and ‘willingness to make sacrifices and die’ for one’s country, ‘sentiments of love’ for one’s country, ‘hatred’ for those that may threaten it, and a sense of ‘closeness’ with the fellow nationals.

For instance, an example of a character in *Just Us (Emeis ki emeis)* that emphatically ‘confesses’ that he is willing to fight and die for Greece can be found in episode 136. In detail, when Antonia (Maria Kanellopoulou) introduces her new fiancé, Nikos (Nikos Kapsis), to the rest of the characters, Champos (Tasos Perzikianidis) her cousin, asks Nikos where he is from. Nikos replies that he is from Athens, but his family is originally from the Greek island of Fourni, which lies close to Turkey. Champos responds to the information by saying: ‘I’ve heard that islanders are good people. [...] Do the Turks want to get this island too? If they dare (to invade), I’ll run first (to fight). Because we, Nikos, are Pontians⁵ and therefore we aren’t afraid of anything. We’re brave. We would give everything for Greece, even our souls.’ Nikos adds on to what Champos just said that he knows many Pontians in person and has realized that their patriotism is exceptional. Champos goes on elaborating on the subject of patriotism stating that: ‘All Greeks are patriotic, but we, the Pontians, are even more patriotic because we lost our territories. [...] I personally never got to know the actual Pontos because our ancestors fled to escape. But they didn’t go straight to Greece, they went to Russia. [...] We have suffered a lot. But, above all is GREECE!’ He then goes on ‘advertising’ the assets of the Pontian women, saying that they’re good wives and mothers, as an attempt to make his cousin Antonia more attractive to Nikos’ eyes.

⁵The Pontic Greeks or Pontians are an ethnically Greek group indigenous to the region of Pontos (Pontus) in northeastern Turkey. From 1913 to 1923, the Greek communities, including the Pontians, residing in Turkey faced destruction through expulsion, war, and genocide, which reduced the Greek population in Turkey from 2 million (in 1913) to fewer than 3,000 (as of 2015). According to the 1928 census, 240,695 Pontian refugees arrived in Greece. Not all Pontians, however, fled to Greece as many settled around areas of the Black Sea, such as in Russia (Meichanetsidis, 2015).

In episode 4 of the same series, Champos' sister, Parthena (Eleni Gerasimidou), - who also recently moved to Greece from Novorossiysk (Russia) where their ancestors used to live after they fled Turkey - after a dinner feast with the rest of the characters, gets on a chair and starts performing a patriotic poem from her childhood, which she used to recite at her school in Russia on the Greek Independence Day (25th of March). The verse she proudly recites is: 'You people, ask me - this humble little girl that stands before you - what is my name, and I'll say I'm named Greek!' She then breaks into a traditional Pontian song called *Εκάεν και το Τσάμπασιν/Ekaen kai to Chabasin* (*Çaybaşı was burnt down too*) and soon everyone in the room starts dancing in a big circle.

Alongside moments of 'loyalty' and 'love' towards the nation, the series also offers examples of the 'closeness' and 'sense of belonging' that characters can feel as a result of their national identity. In detail, in episode 54, there is a scene where Parthena has a conversation with Maria's grandmother, Maritsou (Kostakis Konstantinou), who came from Cyprus for a visit. Antonia, Parthena's cousin, observes them and is fascinated by the way these two women are able to communicate so well - one speaking in the Cypriote dialect and the other in the Pontian dialect. She asks Maria (Maria Filippou), who is a Greek language teacher, how such a thing is possible, and Maria answers: 'It's the roots! My grandmother and Parthena are not just two simple women. They are two *Akritai of Hellenism* (*akritai* being a term used in the Byzantine era meaning 'border defender', here used symbolically).' Maria uses this term to show that, even though the two women come from the 'edges of Hellenism' - areas spread around of the physical borders of the 20th century Greece - and even though the places they originate are far from each other (Pontos at the Black Sea, and the island of Cyprus at the Mediterranean Sea), Parthena and Maritsou are able to communicate and experience a 'sense of belonging'. This 'sense of belonging' is achieved effortlessly despite speaking in two different Greek dialects and despite the physical and cultural distances between their two distinct Greek communities, the Pontian and the Greek Cypriot.

Interestingly, the (re)connection of these two women - and by extension, the (re)connection of these two Greek ethnic groups - takes place in Athens, which lies in central Greece, and, in this series, constitutes the meeting point where the main characters of the series have gathered to live their lives. In detail, Maria has come from Cyprus, Stelios (Stelios Pavlou) from the island of Rhodes in southeastern Aegean, Vasilis (Vasilis Koukouras) from Patra, a city in Peloponnese (southern Greece), Antonis (Antonis Xenos) from Sparta, which is also in Peloponnese, and the sisters Antonia and Smaragda (Smaragda Diamandidou), who have Pontian ancestry, from Kilkis, a town in Central Macedonia, an area in northern Greece. Makis

(Giorgos Giannoutsos) and Natasa (Natasa Manisali) are Athenians, though Natasa's ancestors came from the Turkish city Izmir (at the central-west coast of Turkey), when the Greeks fled the city in the 1922 (Meichanetsidis, 2015), while Parthena and Champos originate from Pontos as mentioned already.

All these characters live in flats in the same two apartment buildings, which lie next to each other, in a picturesque and quiet neighbourhood of Athens, called Mets. Some of them are couples, some are blood-related, while some are just friends. Throughout the 140 episodes (four seasons) of the series, - which constitute *Just Us (Emeis ki Emeis)* the longest running Greek comedy series of the 1990s - these characters, who originate from all over Greece, seem to have created some sort of community, almost detached from the rest of Athens. One could even argue that their 'community' is a miniature version of Greece. Within it, they experience the everyday aspects of life, such as their personal relationships and occupations, but also practise 'culture', as seen in the previous section (4.1.5), through the many episodes that portray music, dancing and traditions. The feelings of 'closeness' and 'belonging' are exemplified in the series not only because of a shared cultural identity but through the topic of friendship around which the premise of the series revolves. These feelings are actualised despite various elements that might seem as differences which could potentially prevent these characters from sharing their lives together - such as differences in dialect, depicted especially through the characters Parthena and Champos, and sometimes through Maria, in education, and in personal interests. As Anderson (1991) puts it, the people who share a national identity, will never know most of their fellow-nationals, meet them, or even hear of them. Yet, in the minds of each lives the 'image' of their communion. This constitutes their community an 'imagined' community' (p. 6). *Just Us (Emeis ki Emeis)*, however, having gathered characters from various parts of Greece, who enjoy their living together, seems to have managed, at least in a symbolic way, to convert Anderson's 'imagined' community into reality.

4.2 REPRESENTATIONS OF POLITICAL IDEOLOGIES AND PRACTICES IN THE GREEK COMEDY SERIES OF THE 1990s

4.2.1 The (a)political entertainment of the American Television

According to Gianos (1995), ‘the conventional wisdom of the (entertainment) industry is that political subjects are to be avoided’ spreading the idea that ‘politics is neither interesting nor important’ (p. 3). Yet, as Christensen and Haas (2015) put it, political themes in entertainment texts can be ‘important’ and ‘interesting’ when they constitute the ‘backdrop’ to more popular themes, such as romance (p. 31). In general terms, however, decisions on programming are mostly taken based on what sort of television product could satisfy the tastes of as wide a public as possible, while, at the same time, meet the needs of advertisers (Gitlin, 1994). According to Croteau and Hoynes (2003), commercial television is, after all, ‘a for-profit enterprise in the business of delivering audiences to advertisers’ (p. 254). Nevertheless, they make sure to highlight that political implications may lurk behind every kind of cultural product, including entertainment programmes which are not explicitly political. They claim that even sitcoms portraying characters that have nothing to do with political matters make a normative political statement by their avoidance of politics.

‘Refusing to take a stand is, in fact, taking one. [...] In not questioning the status quo, such programs reinforce it by contributing to its taken-for-granted nature. Sometimes, by disparaging all politics or efforts at change, these shows may foster a cynicism and a fatalism that are dismissive of real efforts to promote change. Therefore, we can find much of the political implication of prime-time television in unstated assumptions. [...] Creating entertainment that does not contradict the capitalist agenda is television’s major form of political proselytizing’ (Croteau and Hoynes, 2003, p. 254).

Thus, Croteau and Hoynes argue that entertainment programmes mostly uphold a conservative political ideology and reinforce it instead of promoting alternatives for change (p. 256). As Prince (1992, p. 193) explains, by not exploring possible alternatives, prime-time television seems to embrace existing inclinations toward political passivity and feelings of social helplessness.

According to Gray, Jones and Thompson (2009), if we look back at the history of the American television, we will notice that keeping television content apolitical was an established trend since the 1950s, a decade known as a period during which social criticism, in forms such as political satire and parody, was tremendously popular with the masses, at least

in print and music culture. During the 1960s, with the exception of news coverage, this trend continued as television programming kept neglecting the significant social changes and conflicts occurring. The goal of television executives was to appeal to as big an audience as possible, while ‘alienating as few advertisers as possible’. That meant producing the ‘least objectionable’ content, such as comedies, deliberately manufactured as a means for escapism. Nonetheless, as Gray, Jones and Thompson inform us, television studies on the subject have noted that some sociopolitical criticism lurked behind some of the American television programmes of the 1960s. For example, some of the popular fantasy sitcoms of the era, such as *The Addams Family* (ABC, 1964-1966), *Bewitched* (ABC, 1964-1972) and *The Munsters* (CBS, 1964-1966) hinted some resentment towards ‘suburbs and gender roles idealized in domestic sitcoms’, while the musical sitcom *The Monkees* (NBC, 1966-1968) often served as a site for the articulation of ‘nascent countercultural identities’. However, despite the 1960s being a historically crucial period - amid cultural confrontations in the streets and an unpopular war in Vietnam - explicit sociopolitical satire did not qualify as a suitable entertainment product for mass consumption, even though the American audience might have ‘desired’ it the most (pp. 19-22).

The sketch/variety comedy shows *The Smothers Brothers Comedy Hour* (CBS, 1967-1969) and *Rowan and Martin’s Laugh-In* (NBC, 1968-1973) were two programs of the era which, according to Gray, Jones and Thompson, did manage to incorporate politico-satirical content. Yet, the potential impact of their political satire was gradually lessened in both instances. In the case of *The Smothers Brothers Comedy Hour*, its engagement with political content proved even ‘fatal’, with CBS deciding that ‘hassling performers over politics wasn’t worth the network’s time or effort’ - hence, cancelling the show. Narrowing down, therefore, the main trends of the 1960s in relation to representations of politics in entertainment programmes, we can conclude that the reluctance of the American television networks to support satire as a popular aspect of television comedy may be interpreted as an acknowledgement that political humour can be ‘potent enough’ to offend viewers, drive away advertisers, and thus jeopardise network profits (p. 22).

In the early 1970s, the reluctance of the American networks to incorporate socially relevant content in their programming, particularly in comedy series started to shift. For instance, CBS brought to an end a lineup of successful comedies, such as *The Beverly Hillbillies* (CBS, 1962-1971), to make space for more ‘socially relevant’ content that aimed to attract ‘upscale audiences’ desired by advertisers back to television. Ideal for this new approach was the family sitcom *All in the Family* (CBS, 1971-1979). Even though it was not radically

different from previous family comedies, as its narrative followed on the traditional sitcom format, it portrayed some ‘socially relevant’ events, which sometimes disrupted the stereotypical narrative equilibrium. Nonetheless, the series in question did not attempt to parody the sitcom genre, neither satirize the American way of life, but focused on presenting the generational quarrels taking place in everyday homes around the country. As Gray, Jones and Thompson summarize, the American television of the 1970s appeared to accept satire as long as it restricted itself within traditional sitcom boundaries or ‘hovered on the fringes of late-night TV’. The situation did not change during the 1980s, as the sketch comedy show *Not Necessarily the News* (HBO, 1983-1990), based on the British *Not the Nine O’ Clock News* (BBC, 1979-1982), even though it successfully parodied newscasts and commercials, failed as a site for political satire, unlike its British equivalent. On a similar note, while the British puppet comedy show *Spitting Image* (ITV, 1984-1996) satirized politicians, such as Reagan and Thatcher among others, its American copy *D.C. Follies* (SYNDICATION, 1987-1989), despite receiving two Emmy nominations, offered little to no significant political humour (pp. 23-24).

Since the 1990s, the animated sitcom *The Simpsons* (FOX, 1989-present) has been creating televisual space for satire to flourish, offering moments of ‘irreverence’ and breaking of television norms. Nevertheless, according to Gray, Jones and Thompson, *The Simpsons* has been providing little explicit and cutting-edge political satire, despite the fact that its ‘all-pervasive parodic sensibility’ has altered the tone of television comedy as a whole, establishing the satirization of social norms and of the genre of sitcom a common practice (p. 25). In terms of the ways it provides us with moments of political satire, Holbert (2005) explains that the storyline of its episodes is rarely driven by its political satire. Instead, the series offers short snippets of political satire, usually embedded into the episodes merely for the generation of comedic effect. Still, the audience has learnt to expect such semiregular satirical moments of insinuated political commentary, in the series, mostly addressing a range of public affairs, such as social security, policy groups (for example, the National Rifle Association), and political figures. As Holbert points out, however, these short moments of political satire are mostly grounded towards discussions of sociopolitical issues related to ‘the family unit’ (pp. 444-445).

Eventually, the most prominent shift in American comedy and political satire occurred in 1991 with the launch of the cable channel Comedy Central, whose main strategy was to utilize political humour and satire as a means of branding itself. One of its most popular early programmes was *Politically Incorrect* (Comedy Central, 1993-1997; ABC, 1997-2002), a humoristic political roundtable discussion show garnering the channel critical acclaim and brand identity. Hosted by comedian Bill Maher, the show immediately became the network’s

flagship program by mingling serious and humorous political conversations into a hybrid entertainment-political talk show with an unusual mix of guests including celebrities, writers, musicians, comedians, and politicians. Even though the show proved more humorous than satirical, it addressed the artificial division of past years which used to keep politics and entertainment programmes apart. Through *Politically Incorrect*, Comedy Central managed to broaden the horizons of television, combining entertainment with serious talk by depicting conversations between political experts and nonexperts, becoming, therefore ‘the one television network that has most thoroughly developed satirical treatments of state and society’. Over the years its programming has included many provocative shows such as *The Daily Show* (Comedy Central, 1996-present), *South Park* (Comedy Central, 1997-present), *That’s My Bush!* (Comedy Central, 2001), *Chappelle’s Show* (Comedy Central, 2003-2006), *The Colbert Report* (Comedy Central, 2005-2014), and *Lil’ Bush* (Comedy Central, 2007-2008) allowing the channel’s executives ‘to contend that they offer more than simply the comedic’ (Gray, Jones and Thompson, 2009, pp. 25-26).

According to Jones and Baym (2010), Comedy Central’s *The Daily Show* and *The Colbert Report* are the epitome of postmodern media, characterised by border-crossing hybridity. As they explain, these two shows blend politics with pop culture, entertainment with facts, and rational discourse with spectacle. Perhaps because of this, some academic and journalistic critics have expressed concern that these shows constitute examples of ‘infotainment’ yet ‘more creative’- ‘a corruption not only of serious news but of the democratic ethos itself’. Nevertheless, Jones and Baym stress that shows like *The Daily Show* and *The Colbert Report*, having deviated from the old model, feature politics in ways that entertainment programmes ‘simply did not or would not several decades ago’. They conclude that, overall, it is ‘untenable’ to continue to study ‘politics’ and ‘entertainment’ as two different realms separated by boundaries (pp. 281-282).

Delli Carpini (2012) agrees with Jones and Baym’s stance on the subject, however, he argues that as entertainment media is becoming a ‘more’ legitimate subject of study - because of 1) the increased infiltration of politically relevant content in entertainment genres, 2) a newly-found realization of this content’s potential input, and 3) the increasing prevailing of entertainment over news consumption - scholars conducting politically-engaged academic discourses are often ‘struggling’ to integrate entertainment genre theories into their studies. For Delli Carpini, the existing studies that incorporate both political and entertainment discourse usually fall into one of the three categories he has come up with - each representing one of the three ‘overlapping and competing views’ circulating among scholars on the subject. In the first

category, he places studies which see entertainment media as ‘particularly effective genres for reinforcing deep-seated, semi-conscious and hegemonic values’. The second category involves studies which see entertainment media as ‘at best a distraction from politics and at worst a cause of disengagement’. Finally, the third category gathers studies that see entertainment media as ‘an alternative venue for many of the same processes of learning and opinion formation that occur through traditional news and public affairs genres’ (pp. 10-11). The overlapping of views within these categories can be observed in the study of Inthorn, Street and Scott (2012), who claim that media texts which are primarily designed for entertainment and distraction (category 2) may draw (young) people in discussions about political issues, ‘providing them with at least some of the resources they need to actively engage in the public sphere, even if those are conventionally not understood as political’ (category 3) (p. 348).

4.2.2 The (a)political Greek sitcom

As mentioned in the Introduction chapter, with the launch of private channels in Greece from 1989 onwards, prime-time programmes were intentionally kept apolitical in order to achieve high viewing rates, and, within the context of competition, attract the most profit from advertisement (Koukoutsaki-Monnier, 2010, p. 442). Alignments with political ideologies of state powers, as it happened during the 1970s and 1980s, were therefore incompatible with the private-economic criteria of the 1990s commercial television (Papathanasopoulos, 1997, pp. 213-214). As stated in the Literature Review chapter, when Aitaki (2020) interviewed Greek television professionals/creators asking them about potential political ideologies influencing their series-making, they denied intentional infiltration of any ideological system of (political) beliefs into their creations. Instead, they characterised their ‘television fiction’ as being in ‘general alignment with dominant norms, values and versions of the world’ (p. 230).

However, there are plenty of instances that characters express and debate their political views throughout the Greek comedy series examined in this thesis. This section, therefore, consists of a close analysis of scenes in which political discussions take place. These discussions offer an insight to the concerns Greeks had about the political status quo of the 1990s, as well as the range of political ideologies that circulated and shaped the everyday experience and way of thinking of the era. The outcomes of the investigation of the following scenes and episodes constitute a response to Aitaki’s (2020, p. 222) call for further studies on potential political ideologies influencing Greek television fiction (see section 2.1) and attempt to put claims about the apoliticality or reinforcement of conservatism of prime-time television in question. They suggest that the 1990s Greek prime-time comedy was in fact political on its

own merit, overturning the American paradigm of the mainstream television comedy genre explored in the previous section.

The first scene investigated comes from episode 3 of *The Bad Vizier (O Kakos Veziris)/O Kakós Beζύρης* (MEGA, 1997-1998). In detail, Kleon Veziris (Charis Romas) - the Secretary General at the Ministry for the Environment, Physical Planning and Public Works, whose fierce desire and premise of the series is to find a way to *dethrone* its minister, Evangelos Moschos (Christos Efthimiou), and take his position - advises Roza (Maria Georgiadou), the wife of the minister, to hold a reception for a (fictional) member of the former royal family of Greece. Roza, however, is concerned that such a movement might not be ‘politically correct’ (as she describes it), because her husband, being one of the ministers of the socialist government of the time (PASOK: Panhellenic Socialist Movement) would give the impression to the party that he is a royalist. That would put his career as a minister in danger, which is exactly what Kleon endeavours to achieve. In order to convince her, Kleon claims that monarchy is about to be restored in Greece ‘anyway’, and there is a possibility that if she supports the former royals prior to their ‘return’, they might give her a title once they are back. ‘But is there any chance the constitution changes, Mr. Veziris (from Unitary Parliamentary Republic to Constitutional Monarchy)?’ she wonders, and he clarifies: ‘Yes, this is where we’re heading to!’ He then goes on analysing his rational why this is the case: ‘Let’s start from the beginning! What makes monarchy special? Heredity! The crown is passed from the father to the heir. This is exactly what happens in Greece all these years! Georgios Papandreou (Prime Minister of Greece, 1944-45, 1963-65) gave the *crown* (he symbolically uses the word ‘crown’ to mean premiership) to his son, Andreas Papandreou (Prime Minister, 1981-1989, 1993-1996), who then made his son, *Giorgakis* (diminutive of Georgios) Papandreou, a minister (of National Education and Religious Affairs, 1988-89, 1994-96). Konstantinos Mitsotakis (Prime Minister, 1989-93) has his daughter, *Doraki* (diminutive of Dora), to succeed him! And most remarkably! We had Konstantinos Karamanlis (as a Prime Minister) a hundred years ago (1955-63, 1974-1980) and now we have his nephew Kostakis (diminutive of Konstantinos) Karamanlis as leader of the opposition. And as far I can tell, this chubby guy will soon wear the tiara (meaning he will soon become Prime Minister).’

Kleon is then interrupted by his assistant, Lazaros (Giorgos Galitis), who commends that what Kleon has been describing is not monarchy but nepotism. Kleon goes on claiming that monarchy and nepotism are the same thing under two different names. Yet, Lazaros proudly states: ‘We are socialists!’ implying that the political ideology of their party would never support the restoration of the monarchy. Kleon replies that socialism comes in many

versions, such as ‘modernist socialism, old-communist socialism, democratic socialism’ and, therefore, they should invent a kind of socialism that would be a bit more *glamorous*. He names it ‘crowned socialism!’ This final statement convinces Roza to hold a reception for that ex-Greek royal, hoping that in the future, when ‘crowned socialism’ is established in Greece, she will become a duchess.

Such ‘debates’ between left and right-wing ideologies, in this case socialism and monarchy/conservatism, did not just dichotomize the Greek public but in many cases seemed to overlap often as conscious or unconscious attempts to bridge the politico-social chasm. Another example of this ideological overlap can be found in episode 25 of *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)/Οι Απαράδεκτοι* (MEGA, 1991-1993), offering the opportunity to identify and further analyse its complexities within the Greek society of the era. In short, Spiros (Spiros Papadopoulos), producer of television commercials, has a ‘business’ dinner with a successful businesswoman, named Natalia (Natalia Tsaliki). Even though he is married to Dimitra (Dimitra Papadopoulou), Natalia and he start flirting at the dinner. At some point, she sings a verse of a love song to him called *Άσε με να φύγω/Ase me na figo (Let me go)* by Aleka Kanellidou (1974), stating that this song is her favourite. Spiros, excited by her singing, wishes to sing his favourite song as well, which is *Μαύρα κοράκια/Mavra korakia (Black crows)* composed by Thanos Mikroutsikos (1977). Filled with emotions of pride, he sings: ‘Black crows with sharp claws have fallen upon the working class.’ Natalia taken by surprise asks him: ‘Is this your favourite song? This is a communist song!’ and he proudly responds: ‘Yes, it is! You know, I was a fighter at the Athens Polytechnic uprising⁶. I took great action there! I stood proudly before the tank! I fought against the establishment in every way!’ Natalia, however, informs him that she does not support his political beliefs saying: ‘We’ve always belonged to the right wing in our family, and I was never fond of the communists!’ to which he responds: ‘And I was never fond of the capitalist worms, but I suggest we bridge the political gap tonight.’ He then unsuccessfully tries to justify that the reason for bridging the political gap has little to do with romance but comes as result of the then-politics of PASOK, which promoted ‘national reconciliation’ as an attempt to bridge the chasm between left and right-wing ideologies that polarised the Greek society for years (as he explains).

According to Gazi (2015), in October of 1981, the centre-right party New Democracy was defeated in the elections by the socialist party PASOK (Panhellenic Socialist Movement).

⁶ A student revolt against the Dictatorship of 1967-1974, which occurred in November 1973 and ended with casualties and a tank crashing through the gates of the Athens Polytechnic (Kornetis, 2013, p. 1).

Claiming national liberation from the shackles of NATO, the US and, more broadly, western imperialism was a core objective on the political agenda of PASOK. Among the goals of its early period in government was the ‘Hellenization’ (‘Greekization’) of the country, a process aimed to mobilize full national detachment from influences of western powers. The dismantling of those within the country who sought to reinforce the relationship of Greece with imperialism and, consciously or not, promote the interests of ‘foreigners’ was also part of the ‘Hellenization’ effort. Even the ‘cultural penetration’ of the West was deemed to aim to cut off Greeks, and especially the new generation, from their cultural roots and history (p. 250). Thus, for Botsiou (2015), PASOK wanted to present Greece as a country which was still struggling to establish its elementary right of self-governance and self-determination. This stand was summarised in the motto of PASOK: ‘Greece belongs to the Greeks’, which worked as an answer to the motto of New Democracy: ‘Greece belongs to the western world’ (p. 216).

Nonetheless, as Gazi (2015) notes, the initial socialist orientations of PASOK, which asserted the sovereignty of the public, gradually changed during the 1980s. The accession of Greece into the EEC in early 1981 implemented by New Democracy, the rise of PASOK to power, and, above all, the fiscal crisis of 1985 followed by a loan agreement with the EEC imposed a gradual reconsideration of the previous political rhetoric, as well as integration of, at least, essential European strategies into the governing of PASOK. At the same time, New Democracy, whose political and ideological starting point after the fall of the Dictatorship in 1974 was ‘Europeanization’ in order to distance itself from the far-right ‘nationalist’ ideology of the dictators, started promoting that Greece’s European perspective was of great national interest (pp. 251-252). According to Botsiou (2015), since the late 1970s, it considered the accession of Greece in the EEC key to the raising of living standards and the reformation of anachronistic structures and attitudes. It deemed the EEC as a way to strengthen Greece against enemies, and reinforce its relationships with partners, especially the USA. In short, it advocated that the political and social problems of the country would be solved through economic prosperity and institutional modernizations based on European guidance (p. 215).

After the shifting of the politics of PASOK regarding the place of Greece in the EEC, what was once a cause for polarization between PASOK and New Democracy, turned into a point of agreement. Having compromised with the European perspective, PASOK started utilizing EEC membership resources and advantages increasing the living standards of the Greek public. This led to full abandonment of its initial anti-European rhetoric and consequently to a flattening ‘equalization’ with the politics of New Democracy. During the following years and until the economic crisis of 2008, due to the many similarities between

these two main parties it seemed to be of almost no importance which party was in power, and which one was in official opposition (Botsiou, 2015, pp. 222-224).

There are instances that this ‘equalization’ of the political ideologies of PASOK and New Democracy - in other words, the ‘equalization’ between right and left ideology - has been portrayed in the comedy series of the era. The ideological gap caused by the absence of ‘real’ socialist orientation within the Greek parliament seemed to decompress the political polarization of the previous years, causing a sense of ‘ideological confusion’ to the public. This confusion can be observed in episode 37 of *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)*, when the main characters, Spiros, Dimitra, Vlassis (Vlassis Bonatsos) and Giannis (Giannis Bezos), decide to create a new political party, having read in a newspaper that Greece needs an ‘alternative (political) suggestion.’ Alongside the party, they come up with the idea of launching their own television channel, so they can use it to promote their ideological agenda to the people. Yet, not being able to settle what the political ideology of their party is going to be, Dimitra suggests that they meet again in the late evening as she plans to prepare various Greek sea-food delicacies accompanied by ouzo (alcoholic drink) to help them come up with ideas about the political position of their party. During their ‘feast’, Spiros, the only character who throughout the series openly expresses his left-wing beliefs, is the one who presents his idea first. In detail, he suggests: ‘Comrades, give me your attention! I’d like to announce to you the fundamental ideological principles of our party. [...] Firstly, the fact that socialism (in the Soviet Union) has fallen has nothing to do with us, because it was the *Real Socialism* model that fell. We’re not interested in *Real Socialism*. [...] We’re interested in *Unreal Socialism*. I believe, therefore, that our party should be based on the principles of Marxism, Leninism and Mao Tse-tung’s way of thinking.’ The rest of the characters highly disagree with his ideological position, with Dimitra specifically stating: ‘I’m not going to allow Mao Tse-tung enter the house!’ Giannis, on the other hand, is not interested in any political orientation and declares: ‘Listen, my boy, I’m only interested in the TV channel and my public image! I don’t care about the rest (political ideologies).’ Then, Vlassis presents his idea: ‘In my opinion, what we need is a party that promotes chilling-out and relaxing! [...] And I don’t mind getting tired by advising people not to get tired!’ When Dimitra, finally, expresses her point of view, she says: ‘I’m interested in the position of women in society, because, to this day, the woman still waits for the man to be the first to make a pass at her. [...] She should make a pass at him first, asking him if he’s up for a quickie!’ The characters conclude that since they cannot agree to a political ideology, their party would consist of members, who each is allowed to have and promote their own opinions and political orientations. Spiros is the only one who is sceptical about such an

approach stating: ‘This sounds quite anarchic to me!’ However, his wife, Dimitra exclaims: ‘No, it’s not anarchic, it’s perfect, perfect, perfect!’

Anarchism as a ‘leftist’ replacement of socialism in the battle against right-wing ideology is an issue that is also brought up in episode 65 of *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)/Οι Τρεις Χάριτες* (MEGA, 1990-1992). In this case, however, it is not considered ‘perfect’, as in the above example, but is portrayed as terroristic. In detail, Olga (Anna Panagiotopoulou) having moved out of her sisters’ place, rents a flat just above her daughter’s, Teti (Anna Kouri), who lives with her boyfriend, Petros (Vladimiros Kiriakidis). Paranoid that her daughter might be involved in some dangerous situation, Olga places a secret bug in Teti’s flat to spy on her and find out if her suspicions are true. Teti and Petros, however, having detected the bug, decide to play a practical joke on Olga to ‘punish’ her for her intrusive behaviour. They figure out that in order to achieve this, they would have to put a bug at Olga’s flat as well, listen in on her private conversations and wait for the right moment. Soon, Olga’s sisters, Maria (Nena Menti) and Irini (Mina Adamaki), along with their aunt Bebekka (Anna Kyriakou), pay Olga a visit and all together start listening in (using special equipment) on Teti and Petros’ flat. This seems to be the perfect opportunity for the couple to play the practical joke they were planning. So, they begin a fictitious conversation about the terrorist organization to which they claim to belong.

As expected, once Olga hears that her daughter is a terrorist she gets highly agitated and starts blaming her sister, Maria, for being a bad influence on Teti, because of the left-wing political beliefs she used to have. In detail, she claims: ‘It’s your fault, Maria! You misled her (Teti) because you were leftist! [...] Didn’t you have relations with the extra-parliamentary left opposition?’ and Irini agrees adding: ‘That’s right, you (Maria) were the one who brought home the proletarian flag!’ Olga goes on deducing that: ‘This is how these things (terrorism) start! We supported left-wing too, but we did it with dignity. I even voted for PASOK once!’ Maria fights back saying: ‘Teti was always surrounded by progressive people. Even Bebekka (their aunt) during the *post-polity* (the transitional period that followed the fall of the dictatorship in 1974 and the restoration of democracy) read *The Little Red Book* by Mao (Tse-tung).’

Once they stop fighting, they resume listening in on Teti and Petros’ conversation to retrieve more information about the terrorist organization. When the couple realizes that the ladies are listening in again, Petros says to Teti passionately: ‘You must maintain a steady ideology! You must deeply believe in our organization. [...] Teti, the world will never change until the last capitalist is strangled with the entrails of the last bureaucrat!’ They escalate the situation by ‘revealing’ the name of the leader of their organization. The person, according to

the couple, is Teti's uncle, Andreas (Michalis Reppas), the younger brother of Olga, Maria and Irini.

In the next scene, the three sisters invite their brother over and, along with their aunt Bebeka, try to indirectly get the truth out of him. They 'incidentally' start making comments such as: 'We (all) live a very boring and empty life', 'without objectives and ideals', 'the socialist dream fell apart', 'the people's movement is in a quagmire!', 'imperialism does whatever *he* likes undisturbed.' Andreas, of course, has no clue why this conversation has come up, which urges them to change their interrogation approach. They, instead, start asking him personal questions, some of them being: 'Are you an anarchist?', 'What's your opinion on parliamentarism?', 'Do you like liberal democracy? In case you don't, do you want to abolish it?' They go on claiming that if he does indeed wish of abolish democracy, they will understand his reasons why. They state that they also dislike capitalism as, according to their words: 'it is based on human-to-human exploitation', 'has caused environmental disaster and impoverishment of the third world', 'the capital and the means of production are limited to the hands of an oligarchy, therefore the employee becomes a wage-earner slave'.

However, throughout the conversation, Andreas expresses quite moderate views about his political beliefs, yet his sisters seem to discard whatever he says. They insist on believing that he is the leader of a terrorist organization and 'compassionately' claim that it does make sense for them that he desires to overturn the establishment, since 'he is young' and 'has ideals.' Yet, according to their words, the establishment cannot be overturned with sporadic violent acts, because, as Irini puts it: 'Capitalism is like Hydra! If you kill one industrialist, ten more sprout up!' Therefore, capitalism can never be abolished, so there is no other option but to accept it. They advise their brother that if he still wishes to fight capitalism, he needs to do it while remaining within the system and adhering to the laws, as 'capitalism can only be fought from the inside.' They, then, move on offering some recommendations on how to fight capitalism from the inside. What they personally do, for example, is 'sign various protests', 'read progressive newspapers' and 'make offensive gestures at the television screen when seeing politicians on the news.' As Olga strongly argues, such acts demonstrate their fierce war against capitalism! Despite this 'fierce' resistance, however, it is apparent that capitalism has managed to prevail. Or, at least, this is how it has been (re)presented in the comedy series of the 1990s. As seen in the above scene, the characters seem to have accepted 'the system' and they even defend it against potential threats. Their old leftist influences and beliefs appear to be nothing more than 'romantic' attributes of the past.

Episodes 45 to 47 of *Just Us (Emeis ki emeis)/Εμείς κι Εμείς* (MEGA, 1994-1998) offer a similar representation of political ideology and its transformation, as they demonstrate, mostly indirectly, the progression of political beliefs in Greece, from the mid-1970s all the way to the mid-1990s. They depict leftist ideologies, such as anarchism, which were prominent among young Greeks during the late 1970s and early 1980s - the period PASOK was promoting its most hard-core anti-imperialist views. They then showcase the shift towards a more capitalistic way of living after the gradual abandonment of the leftist beliefs. In detail, in episode 45, Antonia (Maria Kanellopoulou), a woman in her late thirties, receives a phone call from an old friend, Sostis (Spiros Sarafianos), whom she hasn't seen for many years. He informs her that he will soon pay them a visit. His upcoming arrival puts great stress on Antonia, because Sostis used to be a known 'rebel' when he was younger, whose anarchist ideology she and her friends had warmly embraced during the prime of their youth. She is concerned that their current lifestyle will not make a good impression on Sostis, as according to her words: 'We're (now) in the system through and through!' Her younger sister, Smaragda (Smaragda Diamandidou), attempts to calm her down, yet Antonia insists saying: 'Apart from being my ex-boyfriend, Sostis was also the ideological leader of our clique, back when we had realized that the political parties and factions didn't have anything substantial to offer us, so we adopted a more anarchic way of living! [...] (Therefore, now) we are accountable for what we've done to ourselves, to Sostis, and to history! For when Sostis left us, we were anarcho-autonomous, and now he's going to find us living like petit bourgeois-jerks!' Smaragda explains to her that this phenomenon is quite common, stating: 'This is life, Antonia! When someone is younger has a more leftish way of thinking. When he grows older, he gradually starts leaning more towards the right (wing). Something like the Leaning Tower of Pisa!'

The rest of these episodes (45 to 47) revolve around Antonia's endeavours to turn back time by convincing the other characters to readopt the anarchic lifestyle of their youth for Sostis' visit, as an attempt to prove to him that they all have remained loyal to the political ideology of their past. Therefore, she prepares the ground by asking her friends and relatives to dress with bohemian-looking clothes, pretend (for Sostis' eyes) to have polyamorous and homosexual relations amongst them, reread books such as *Listen, Little Man!* and *The Sexual Revolution* by Reich, and not wash themselves. Some of the moments of prominent comedic effect derive from scenes in which Antonia tries to explain the anarchic way of living to her Pontian cousin, Parthena (Eleni Gerasimidou), who recently moved to Greece from the Black Sea (see section 4.1.6). Having lived under the Soviet regime for almost all her life, Parthena has great difficulty comprehending what the quotes (by Reich), which Antonia forces her to

memorize, really mean. She almost passes out, shocked by Antonia's request to pretend to be in a romantic relationship with Natasa (Natasa Manisali). In detail, she cries: 'In Russia if they found out you were one of those (lesbians), they'd send you for hard labour in Siberia to break rocks!' However, Parthena soon gets the grip of the anarchic way of thinking and just before Sostis' arrival, when everybody has gotten ready dressed as 'anarchists', she spots Natasa, who chose not to dress up as the rest them (because, as she declares, she's an anarchist therefore she can wear whatever she feels like) and exclaims: 'Antonia, Antonia! Natasa is dressed like a representative of the authorities, who sits on the governmental chairs and raises her offspring so they can take the same chairs (positions) via the practice of deceit, corruption, violence, and massacres!' Nevertheless, all their efforts are wasted, because, once Sostis finally shows up, he is dressed in a dark suit holding a briefcase. He informs them that he now works as a stockbroker and business consultant, and that seeing them holding onto their old ideology makes him feel guilty for becoming a *petit bourgeois*. Soon, the characters reveal that this was the case for them too - they have all become 'petit bourgeoisies' of the system!

From these examples, it is evident that the political status quo, political ideologies, and political history were indeed showcased by the Greek prime-time television, as opposed to the commercial practices regarding the established advertisement strategies of the apolitical sitcom presented previously in the subchapter (Croteau and Hoynes, 2003, pp. 254-256; Koukoutsaki-Monnier, 2010, p. 442; Papathanasopoulos, 1997, pp. 213-214; Prince, 1992, p. 193; Gianos, 1995, p. 3; Christensen and Haas, 2015, p. 31). The Greek comedy series examined here may not have offered alternatives for change, or distance themselves from a reality in which capitalism has prevailed. But instead, they explicitly portrayed the acknowledgement of its prevalence, and the implications that that had upon the romanticized alternative ideologies of the past. As Croteau and Hoynes (2003, p. 253) put it, most people consider programmes, such as comedy series, 'only entertainment.' However, as seen in this section, these programmes feature characters and stories that directly or indirectly have political significance. 'All TV is, in fact, political' (p. 253). Accordingly, the Greek prime-time comedy was not apolitical, but political on its own merit, as it did not silence the political physiognomies that influenced Greece during the late 20th century. This claim can be also reinforced by the fact that the Greek comedy of the 1990s did not just deal with portraying political ideologies but depicted a wide range of political practices prominent in the everyday life of the Greeks of the era. The following section consists, therefore, of a close analysis of moments such practices were represented throughout the series examined.

4.2.3 The socio-political practices: ‘rousfeti’, ‘meson’ and ‘fakelaki’

According to Chalari (2015, p. 162), Greece has experienced continuing social and structural dysfunctions over the entirety of the 20th century, resulting in major delays in its political, economic, and social development. As stated by Michas (2011, p. 3), one of the fundamental principles that has characterised the political and economic life of the country is political clientelism. Since the foundation of Greece in the early 19th century, the country has developed a system according to which political support is offered in exchange for benefits - a practice known as *rousfeti* (ρουσφέτι) (Michas, 2011, p. 3; Chatzisavvas, 1990, p. 38; Hallin & Papathanassopoulos, 2002, p. 185; Georgiades, 2006, p. 111; Michelis, 2011, p. 16; Chalari, 2015, p. 162; Faustmann, 2010, p. 270). The word *rousfeti* comes from the Turkish word *rüşvet*, which means bribery, although in Greek it is mostly used as *special favour*. Additional political ‘anomalies’ that have influenced the Greek mentality when it comes to politics and the relationship of Greeks with the state are: the concept of *volema* (βόλεμα), which translates as to *getting comfortable* and refers to being appointed to a work position without meeting the right criteria or remaining in a situation that works for oneself without considering others; the concept of *ohaderfismos* (ωχαδερφισμός), which translates as ‘oh, brother’ and means to get by without caring about tomorrow or negative consequences; the practice of *meson* (μέσον), which means *medium/means* and it refers to political figures (used as means) that help citizens accomplish what they wish by pulling strings and exploiting their political power (Chalari, 2015, p. 164; Chatzisavvas, 1990, p. 38); and the practice of *fakelaki* (φακελάκι), meaning *little envelope*, and referring to the envelope which contains the money that is given to the receiver of a bribe (Michas, 2011, p. 13; Michelis, 2011, p. 16).

Out of these problematic concepts and practices, what has remained constantly central to Greece’s societal and political organising principles is clientelism (Michas, 2011, p. 7). According to Faustmann (2010), Greek politics are exercised within a framework of extensive and deeply rooted clientelistic patterns and structures, occurring in two interrelated forms. The first form can be described as ‘impersonal party patronage’ according to which a political party, as an organisation, dispenses favours to its supporters, expecting votes in return. On the other hand, the second form is implemented by individual politicians such as members of parliament, ministers, or other power holders, for examples in civil, military and health services. Being personally approached by citizens, they distribute special favours/*rousfeti*, establishing clientelistic sub-networks (pp. 283-284). The favours dispensed may include appointments, promotions, transfers, exemptions from the implementation of laws, access to services and administrative favours. From the citizen’s perspective, if he/she is already a party member or a

supporter of a certain politician, he/she expects to be rewarded with a favour. Failing to deliver favours might result in the loss of the citizen's vote. From the politician's perspective, the citizen must be a supporter of the party or the politician in question for the favour to take place. Therefore, citizens are expected, sometimes pressured, to join the party responsible for the favour if they are not already members (p. 270).

The following scenes taken from episodes 40 and 45 of *The Penthouse (To Retire)/To Πετιπέ* (MEGA, 1990-1992) and episode 56 of *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)/Οι Τρεις Χάριτες* (MEGA, 1990-1992) are indicative examples of political clientelism represented in the comedy series of the era. Starting with episode 40 of *The Penthouse (To Retire)*, the protagonist, Katerina (Katerina Gioulaki), who works as a talk-show presenter at the television studio Cosmos, decides to undertake an additional job assisting a member of the parliament and old schoolmate of hers, Mrs. Petraki-Lechraki, with her public relations. The news spreads fast and soon enough Katerina is surrounded by neighbours, colleagues, friends and relatives, who eagerly demand from her to mediate and ask the MP she works for to fulfil their personal favours. For instance, Charoula (Elda Panopoulou) asks to be given a duty-free shop to run at an airport or port, while Amalia (Nefeli Orfanou) wants her daughter's boyfriend to fulfil his military duties closer to Athens and not at the border with Turkey.

Additional striking examples of the nature of the personal favours that the characters ask from the MP can be also found in episode 45 of *The Penthouse (To Retire)*. Charoula, for example, approaches Katerina once again and expresses her dissatisfaction with the amount of money she gets paid from her office job at Cosmos studios. Having tried and failed to earn more by running a bar along with her friend Eleni (Kleri Katsantoni), she attempts to convince Katerina to mediate and ask the MP for a *rousfeti*. She specifically requests: 'You really must find me a second occupation, because the salary I get from this job is not enough to make a living, and when I say living, I mean a good living! [...] So, you must find me a job that pays me well and isn't very tiring! It'd be better if I got hired to a job that didn't require my everyday attendance, as well.' Katerina, irritated by Charoula's demand, commends: 'I see! So, you want a job that pays well but you wouldn't have to work!' Yet, Charoula 'corrects' her saying: 'No, you didn't understand! I want a job with a good and frequent salary - yes, but I also want to be paid overtimes!' Katerina, even more infuriated by Charoula's brazen way of thinking, clarifies: 'With no requirement to work at all, right?' Charoula realizing that her request might not be fulfilled fervently adds: 'Yes, Katerina, I'm neither the first nor the last one who does it! We live in the country of *rousfeti*, and we know an MP personally! Shouldn't she (the MP) make a *rousfeti* for us too?'

The intensity of the scene escalates even more as alongside Charoula's demand to get hired to a second job, which will pay her well without having to work at all, a stranger comes in and asks to see Katerina for another, more absurd request. He claims that before the elections, the MP that Katerina works for had promised him a job at the Social Insurance Institute of Greece if he voted for her. However, after the elections, she did not keep her word, therefore, the man now requests from the MP to take his wife's urine for a urinalysis. He hands in a bottle of urine to Katerina and demands that it is taken to a medical clinic immediately, otherwise he would never vote for that MP again. The episode ends with Katerina announcing the (fake) results of the urine test to the stranger, which state that his wife suffers from prostate issues. She characteristically says: 'It serves you right! That's what you get when you ask an MP to analyse your wife's urine! There you go, she has prostate issues! If you had brought yours, we would have told you that you were pregnant!' With this line she attempts to 'punish' the stranger for his irrational and provocative behaviour, but also make an indirect reference to the lack of trustworthiness and efficiency of the MPs, and by extension the Greek government.

Episode 56 of *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)* is entirely dedicated to this phenomenon of *rousfeti* (special favour). It starts with Andreas (Michalis Reppas) announcing to his older sisters, Olga (Anna Panagiotopoulou), Maria (Nena Menti) and Irimi (Mina Adamaki), that his fiancé, Charoula (Joyce Evidi), who works for the Public Treasury, was asked to be transferred to another town (Gytheio) to work in the same sector. Her work relocation is, of course, devastating for the couple, therefore Andreas urges his sisters to find a way, through their social relations, to help Charoula keep her position in Athens. He reminds Olga that she and her late husband used to be friends with a member of the parliament called Giorgos Pitsidis (Christos Simardanis). He requests that they go to Pitsidis' office and ask him for a *rousfeti* - namely, ask him to use his power as an MP (although of the Official Opposition) to make sure that Charoula's working place remains in Athens. At first, his sisters refuse to ask for a *rousfeti* due to its impractical and unethical complications. In particular, Irimi says: '*Rousfeti* creates some obligations!' meaning that at the next elections one is morally obliged to vote for the MP that has done him/her a favour. Maria adds: 'We have ideals! We don't deign to ask MPs for *rousfetia* (plural)!' Andreas, then, points out that Irimi works at the Administration of Justice, because their father, who used to be a judge, had pulled some strings and ensured that she got the job. Irimi unapologetically clarifies that the lack of meritocracy in her case is an unimportant matter, as getting a job at the Administration of Justice was a 'serious life choice' for her and not something as trivial as the prevention of Charoula's undesirable workplace transfer.

In the following scene, the three sisters, having decided to help their brother, visit Pitsidis' office to ask for the favour. Once they enter the reception area, they realize that it is packed with people. Olga asks her sisters: 'Did all these people come here to ask for a *rousfeti*?' Indeed, all those people were waiting for their turn to enter the MP's office and ask for a personal favour. One of them, Stavroula Perdika (Maria Kanellopoulou), starts a conversation with the sisters explaining what she has come to ask from the MP. She says that she is a widow, and her only source of income is her late husband's pension. However, recently it was discovered that a minor fraud was committed by her husband with the help of an employee of the public insurance association which used to provide him the pension. Since he is now deceased and unable to make amends for the fraud, his pension was discontinued. Hence, she came to ask Pitsidis to solve the issue so she can start receiving her husband's pension again. Apart from that, she confides that she also plans to ask the MP to give her son a job as a port guard on the island of Andros, where she resides, and once her underage daughter becomes of age, she will return to Pitsidis' office to ask him to give her a job as well.

Soon, Olga, Maria and Irini are called by a secretary to enter Pitsidis' office. At first, their discussion with the MP mainly consists of praises towards him and his party (which is not the governing party). The four of them then start accusing the government of the various problems that Greece faced since Pitsidis' party lost the elections. This gives the opportunity to Irini to say: 'Alongside the big problems, there are smaller, individual problems. What I want to say is that the everyday citizen suffers sometimes from adversities, which you politicians can very easily solve via the prestige and authority given to you by the Greek people.' When the sisters finish explaining Charoula's case, asking him to intervene and undo her transfer, he responds: 'Not to do *rousfeti* is our party's principle, which I respect and abide by. [...] When we were in power no *rousfeti* were taking place! [...] Whoever was appointed (to work in the civil services), was appointed on merit. [...] Unfortunately, I don't do *rousfeti*. But because I can imagine your devotion to our party and the fights you gave and will give on our side, I'll make an exception for your particular case and speak to someone I know (to fix your problem).'

Ten days pass and the characters have no news about Charoula's case. The sisters' aunt, Bebeke (Anna Kyriakou), advises them to approach an MP who belongs to the governing party instead. She proudly informs them that the brother of her husband's brother-in-law has a friend who knows one named Kleon Papatzalas (Kostas Tsianos). As it happened with Pitsidis, once they visit Papatzalas to ask for his help, he says: 'Look, my ladies! I understand your worry about the transfer of your sister-in-law, but things are not as they used to be. The previous

government used to make *rousfeti*, ours doesn't! We support meritocracy! *Rousfeti* is a politico-sociological phenomenon that derives from underdevelopment. Now that Greece belongs to the EEC (European Economic Community), we run at different speeds! The year 2000 is awaiting us! [...] Our country suffered enough from this phenomenon (*rousfeti*)! Our government is determined to uproot this evil!' Nevertheless, he agrees to sort out the issue because he is acquainted with their aunt Bebeka.

Personal gain, such as getting a job at the civil sector or acquiring other facilitations are not the only reasons Greeks are prone to clientelism. The difficulties caused by the extensive bureaucracy of the Greek public administration, civil and tax services with their bewildering plethora of laws and regulations trigger clientelistic politics as they can provide shortcuts to get things done or ease access to state subsidies, licences, and other forms of protection (Tsakalotos, 1998, p. 130; Chatzisavvas, 1990, p. 29). Thus, citizens seek to establish social relations with people in positions of power in order to surpass bureaucratic formalities through *rousfeti* practices (Georgiades, 2006, p. 111). Bureaucracy, however, does not only contribute to the emergence of such corruptive behaviours, but due to its maze of laws and regulations may cause entrepreneurs, businessmen, even everyday citizens to easily find themselves accused of tax-evasion or some other misdeed forcing them to pay exorbitant fines. If such a situation occurs clientelistic politics can provide a way out for the citizen in trouble (Michas, 2011, p. 12). An example on this issue, indicating the inflexibility of the Greek bureaucratic system, can be found in the above episode (56) of *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)*, when the deceased husband of the guest character, Stavroula Perdika, was in the eyes of the law the one accountable to fix the problem she was facing. Therefore, she was left with no other choice but to ask an MP for a *rousfeti*.

Approaching politicians for a *rousfeti* is not the only way out of troubling or merely uncomfortable situations. People in positions of power, such as in the army, police, etc. are also sought out by citizens in need for a favour or special assistance. These people are considered a *meson*. As stated earlier, the literal meaning of the word *meson* is medium or means, but figuratively it can mean connection or contact with someone who, similarly to politicians, has the power to fulfil a person's special request because of his/her position. Such a situation takes place in episode 37 of *Dolce Vita/Ντόλτσε Βίτα* (MEGA, 1995-1997). In detail, Antonis (Thanassis Efthimiadis), a man in his mid-twenties, having been summoned by the army to fulfil his military duties (as in Greece, to this day, men are required to serve in the military for a number of months that can vary according to their personal circumstances) throws a farewell gathering at a tavern, the day before his recruitment. His ex-girlfriend, Dorita (Katerina

Ziogou), is also invited along with her mother, Christina (Anna Panagiotopoulou), a middle-aged woman with whom Antonis has a secret love affair. Throughout the feast, his friends, Manolis (Isidoros Stamoulis) and Loukas (Pavlos Orkopoulos), who have already served in the army, entertain themselves by ‘informing’ him about the difficulties that he is about to face. At some point, they warn him that after the initial training is complete, he is going to be relocated to another army base where he will execute the main body of his duties. The odds are that that base will be at a remote place, which will make it hard for him to visit his friends and family often. Therefore, they suggest he finds a *meson* to ensure that, after his training, he will be taken to a base near Athens where he normally resides. In the following scene, Dorita has a conversation with their housekeeper, Aspasia (Maria Kavoyianni), about the fact that Antonis might need a *meson* to arrange that he is not sent far away from Athens for his military service. Dorita expresses that she is not fond of *meson* as a tactic for someone to get what he wants. Aspasia disagrees saying that if Dorita was in Antonis’ shoes, she would have done the same, because of the fear and stress that the situation would have caused to her.

The *meson* is found by Christina’s best friend, Sasa (Katiana Balanika), who is aware of Christina’s secret love affair with her daughter’s ex-boyfriend, Antonis. In detail, Sasa invites to her place an army Major named Mr. Lampiris (Alexandros Mylonas), with whom it is implied she used to have an affair. She and Christina try their best to convince him that he should intervene and send Antonis to a nearby base to fulfil his duties. In order to achieve this, they come up with a series of lies about Antonis’ past. For example, they claim that he is a ‘cursed’ poor man with an ill mother, that he was forced to work since he was four years old because of his father’s passing, and therefore he received no education. The Major, touched by Antonis’ misfortunes, says: ‘I’m going to do whatever I can to help this boy. However, there’s that law that states that relocation to the borders is mandatory. [...] And I firmly believe in the principles of equality before the law and meritocracy.’ Christina pretends to agree with his principles saying: ‘We definitely understand! All our lives, we have given battles for equality and meritocracy, right Sasa?’ and Sasa replies: ‘I personally have put my chest forward for meritocracy!’ Christina, then, adds: ‘But for Antonis Kaloudis we must make an exception!’ The scene finishes with the Major stating: ‘I’m deeply moved that you (want to) help a poor guy, without any personal gain!’

In small societies, such as Greece, personal connections inevitably become crucial for the interaction of the citizens with the state, and the promotion of their personal goals. According to Faustman (2010), and as seen in the example above, most Greeks either have personal relations with a person in a position of power or, at the very least, know someone who

does. As a result, through a highly developed system of favours that shapes public and private interactions, one can do practically anything provided they have the right *meson*/connection. In the scene above, the Major does not ask anything in return for helping Antonis. As Faustmann puts it, among everyday citizens, favours taken place by a *meson* does not involve any immediate service in exchange, apart from the feeling of a moral obligation to return the favour one day if asked. Often, it has more to do with just helping a friend or a friend of a friend (p. 270).

For Michelis (2011), the terms *rousfeti* and *meson* are closely related to the term *fakelaki*: the former being political practices and the latter a social one. The word *fakelaki* (φακελάκι) is the diminutive version of the noun *fakelos* (φάκελος), which means *envelope*, and refers to the envelope which contains the money that is given to the receiver of a bribe. As he explains, besides asking politicians for favours, there is a long-lasting tradition in Greece according to which citizens may have to pay civil servants, doctors, lawyers, etc. under the table in order to ‘get something done.’ For example, a citizen may choose or be ‘asked’ to bribe in order to obtain a driving licence, building permits, swift hospital admission, reduce a tax bill. Of course, all the *fakelaki* transactions are part of the shadow economy, which is not subject to taxation. As well as contributing to tax evasion, these transactions encourage the unequal distribution of income in the Greek economy, as the *fakelaki* receivers end up with higher after-tax incomes and the *fakelaki* givers with less (p. 16).

As Michas (2011) puts it, many employees, such as civil servants and doctors, would use the infrastructure of the state apparatus for their own benefit. This means that services that are supposed to be offered to the public for free have in fact been privatized. This practice is particularly prominent in the health sector: ‘when a Greek has to undergo surgery in a public hospital, he knows that he will have to grease the surgeon’s hand with some money under the operating table. Such payments can range anywhere from 1,000 to 20,000 euros depending on the kind of surgery and are of course illegal since the services in public hospitals are supposed to be free.’ As a result, services which are free in principle constitute a substantial expense especially for the lower income citizens, who are supposed to be the primary beneficiaries of such services (pp. 12-13).

There are a couple of instances in the comedy series examined that portray the practice of *fakelaki*. The first one takes place in episode 21 of *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)/Οι Τρεις Χάριτες* (MEGA, 1990-1992) when Irimi (Mina Adamaki) gets a heatstroke and is rushed to the hospital by her sisters, Olga (Anna Panagiotopoulou) and Maria (Nena Menti). At the hospital, all the rooms are full to capacity with people that suffer from the same condition due

to the heatwave. Therefore, many extra beds have been placed at the corridors in order to accommodate the excess number of patients. Once Irini regains consciousness, is highly discontented with the fact that she has been placed in a folding bed at the corridor alongside many others. Her sisters inform her that they have tried to talk the hospital director into giving her a proper room to no avail. Yet, Irini insists: ‘There is always a bed (in a room) for someone that knows his way around things! Put pressure on them (the hospital management) or find a *meson* who would put pressure on them instead.’ Olga and Maria come up with the idea of contacting a member of the parliament, who is the husband of an old schoolmate of Olga, in order to find a proper bed in a room for their sister. Unfortunately, failing to come to contact with the MP gives Irini no alternative but to ask her sisters to bribe a doctor. ‘There is no other solution, (apart from) the *fakelaki*!’ she shouts but is silenced by Maria. Her sisters disagree with such an attempt, saying: ‘There are no *fakelakia* (plural) anymore (in Greece)!', yet Irini passionately argues: ‘Like hell there aren’t! Give the money! Don’t keep it like stingy ones! It’s for my health!’

The second instance that features the practice of *fakelaki* occurs in episode 50 of *Constantine’s and Helen’s (Konstantinou kai Elenis)/Κωνσταντίνου και Ελένης* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000). This episode takes place in a public hospital as Constantine (Charis Romas) and Helen (Eleni Rantou) need minor medical treatment after having been in a car accident. The scriptwriters of the series, Anna Chatzisofoia and Charis Romas, take the opportunity to satirize the challenging conditions under which the Greek medical system of the era operated. Some of the problematic situations that are portrayed throughout the episode include: the lack of basic medical supplies, insufficient number of beds, misplace of medical records of patients by the staff, operation on the wrong person, etc. The phenomenon of *fakelaki* is also present, however, contrary to episode 21 of *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)*, it is deemed by the characters as a highly negative issue, and not as a means which assists them in fulfilling their needs faster.

In detail, when Dr Korvokis (Spyros Merianos) enters Constantine and Helen’s room to have a look at an elderly man, Mr. Papadopoulos (Giannis Fyrios), who shares the room with them, Constantine complains, once again, about the poor quality of the hospitalization. The doctor replies by asking him to: ‘Show some understanding. Under these adverse conditions we try to do our service!’ Then, Mr. Papadopoulos, who is soon to have a prostate surgery, says to the doctor: ‘Doctor, I wasn’t able to gather all that money you asked me to give you (for the upcoming surgery), but once my daughter comes from the village today, I’ll get the rest and give you the *fakelaki* you asked.’ As soon as Constantine hears that, he shouts angrily: ‘Disgrace! Doctor, you get bribed? Isn’t the salary from the hospital enough for you? You took

the Hippocratic Oath! Shame on you!’ The doctor defends himself saying: ‘Don’t listen to an old dense man! Doctor Korvokis (he refers to himself) is well-known for the operations he performs on the destitute!’ Mr. Papadopoulos then exclaims desperately: ‘I’m a destitute, too! Why are you asking me for so much money?’ only to be silenced by the doctor: ‘Shush! We’ll discuss this in private!’

The characters’ ‘adventure’ at the hospital comes to an end with Constantine being accidentally taken for the prostate surgery instead of Mr. Papadopoulos. Doctor Korvokis, unaware of the mistake, asks the anaesthesiologist if the patient has been anaesthetised, so he can start the procedure. But before he is given an answer, he adds: ‘Well, it doesn’t matter if he’s under anaesthesia or not. He didn’t give me *fakelaki*, so I’ll open him up as is!’ Little did he know that a nurse had mistaken Helen for being an anaesthesiologist, brought her to the operating room and asked her to anaesthetize Constantine just before he (the doctor) walked in. Therefore, the minute Helen hears the doctor saying that he’d ‘open up’ the patient ‘as is’ because he didn’t give him a *fakelaki*, takes a syringe filled with anaesthetic and strings it on the doctor’s arm yelling: ‘You’re not worthy of being here (working here)!’ saving Constantine from an unnecessary prostate surgery.

Recapitulating the main aspects of the socio-political phenomena of *rousfeti*, *meson* and *fakelaki* that played such a central role in the lives of Greeks in the 1990s, we can understand that as modernization disrupted traditional hierarchical social structures, clientelistic practices seemed more than capable to provide mechanisms for the once isolated citizens to gain access to resources. Therefore, clientelism in Greece evolved as ‘a correlate of modernity’ (Günes-Ayata, 1994, p. 24). Social connections may have indeed catalysed upward social mobility processes, they replaced, however, merit requirements in areas such as hiring, promotion, access to services, etc. (Georgiades, 2006, p. 117). The practice of bribery in the health sector, for example, did not only contribute to the increase of tax-evasion, but had detrimental consequences to low-income citizens (Michelis, 2011, p. 16; Michas, 2011, pp. 12-13). All these constituted Greece’s form of social organization particularistic and asymmetrical. The opposite of what is considered a form of citizenship in which access to resources depends on universalistic criteria and equality before the law (Hallin & Papathanassopoulos, 2002, p. 185).

Furthermore, according to Michas (2011) when a country becomes heavily involved in granting benefits to some citizens at the expense of others, individual politicians and parties will invest more resources into efforts aimed to influence political outcomes to their advantage. Offering jobs, for instance, in the civil sector on the basis of *rousfeti* (politically allocated jobs, without meeting the right criteria in the exchange of political support), is not only harmful in

regards of sub-utilizing existing talent, but financially wasteful as by giving a coveted position to an individual, the politician wastes resources they could have been used differently (pp. 13-14). Unfortunately, according to Georgiades (2006), the reinforcement and perpetuation of phenomena such as *rousfeti*, *meson* and *fakelaki* end up being part of a country's history and culture. With the passage of time, these phenomena become ingrained in people's psyches, solidifying themselves as the cultural norm, causing frustration and pessimism to the citizens about their elimination (p. 117).

Therefore, the fact that these political practices were frequently portrayed in prime-time comedy series of the era, indicates that they did manage to become part of the country's culture - in this case, popular culture. Throughout the scenes analysed above, the phenomena *rousfeti*, *meson* and *fakelaki* were presented as cultural norms, ingrained in collective behaviour, since the characters would not hesitate to utilize them to benefit or get themselves out of unpleasant situations related to their affairs with the state - such as sorting out issues regarding public services (for example, hospitalization), work related issues (at the public sector), and army duty. Alongside the portrayal of political ideologies investigated earlier (section 4.2.2), the representation of the shared, everyday, and, predominantly, political practices examined in this section constitutes an additional component that accentuates the politicalness of the Greek television comedy of the 1990s. Despite the commercial and entertainment purposes of prime-time television, the sitcoms studied here did not refrain from showcasing political aspects that influenced the daily lives of the Greeks of the era. As mentioned in the previous section, these series did not offer an alternative for political change, neither did they deny the prevalence of capitalism. Nevertheless, they dealt with politics in a universalistic yet brave manner, demonstrating contrasting political views and dysfunctional political practices, while at the same time remaining ideologically moderate in order to appeal to as wide an audience as possible. Thus, the Greek comedy series of the 1990s constitute a paradigm of how prime-time television can be both political and ensure its commercial and entertainment objectives.

4.3 REPRESENTATIONS OF ‘THE FAMILY’ IN THE GREEK COMEDY SERIES OF THE 1990s

As mentioned in the Introduction chapter, according to the proceedings of the conference ‘50 years of Greek television’ (Thessaloniki, 9-11 December 2016), some of the proposed areas that require academic investigation and analysis are topics such as ‘the family’, gender roles, sexual identities, social bonds and values, as represented throughout Greek television fiction (Paschalidis, 2018, p. 37). In the Literature Review chapter, Vamvakas (2019) suggests that in the case of comedy ‘the satirical confrontation of the normative and legitimation aspect of tradition is linked to the topic of family’. He points out, however, that ‘there is a lot of work to be done in order to confirm the existence of such connection’, which will entail the examination of prominent Greek comedy series of the last 30 years (p. 35). The following section is, therefore, dedicated on analysing episodes from the comedy series selected in relation to their portrayal of ‘the family’, as represented through the characters’ views and behaviours. Urged by Vamvakas’ claim, the main objective of the analysis is to investigate the link between ‘tradition’ and ‘family’ when it comes to Greek comedy-making and examine its creative utilization by the creators in their endeavour to entertain.

Before embarking on such investigation, a historical overview on the evolution of ‘the family’ will set the sociocultural framework through which we can examine how the ideological changes that occurred during the 20th century in the western world and the assimilation of new paradigms regarding ‘the family’ shaped the American and British sitcom. The historical and ideological context framed through the existing literature on popular anglophone sitcoms in relation to their portrayal of ‘the family’, will then constitute the basis upon which the analysis of the selected Greek comedy series will take place, in accordance with the research objectives stated in the previous paragraph.

4.3.1 ‘The family’ in the 20th century and its portrayal in the anglophone television comedy: A historical overview

For centuries, in western societies, Christianity and puritanism had been defining sexual relationships, procreation and childcare as properly taking place within the nuclear family, with the construction of marriage as an unbreakable bond, which sustained men’s authority and women’s mothering. The emphasis was placed on salvation through a Godly life making the family central to the formation of a Godly society. Trust and fidelity were exalted, while

sexuality was deemed purified only through marriage. Marriage, therefore, was regarded as a partnership based upon common labour and love, constituting the family as a sentimental reality, as well as the centre of morality (Elliot, 1996, pp. 6-7).

According to Elliot (1996), in the late 19th century, these family values were given a renewed legitimation by sociobiological accounts of the ‘naturalness of heterosexuality’ and by psychological theories around the necessity of stable, intimate family relationships to the emotional security of children and adults (p. 7). At the same time, the notion of a ‘natural’ division, as Chambers (2001) puts it, between a feminine private sphere of domestic unpaid work and a masculine public sphere of paid labour was endorsed by the ‘separate spheres’ ideology, which perpetuated women’s marginalisation from the public life. As she explains, the feminine role could only be realised if women were separated from the competitive and ruthless public sphere of the market and masculinity. The efficacy of this ideology could be determined by the way in which certain places and activities were perceived to be ‘tainted’ by the public world, and thus inappropriate for women. On the other hand, the sacred duties of housekeeping and childrearing were elevated as virtuous and pure. Therefore, the home and family world seemed to be ruled by the public world, with the women’s ability to engage with the latter to be limited (pp. 42-43). According to Davidoff et al. (1999), within the ideological framework of the ‘separate spheres’, women’s direct involvement in paid labour was not only deemed inappropriate, but it threw doubt on their femininity and undermined the status of their male relatives. However, despite the dependence of women to their male relatives indicated by the ‘separate spheres’ ideology, many working, and even middle-class, women had to work in order to make ends meet for themselves and their families regardless of the limited employment options available (pp. 27-28).

From the 1920s onwards, the concept of the ‘companionate marriage’ started to spread, initially in North America, and evolved into an important component of the modern functional family form. This marriage model maintained the notion that men and women had different roles, but they were now deemed ‘complementary’. It encouraged dialogue and mutual decision-making by the couple on matters such as family size, and implied sexual satisfaction and friendship on the basis of equality. The ‘companionate marriage’ model supported the idea of a sexually intimate relationship between heterosexual partners founded on romantic love and mutual interests, which ought to be fulfilling for both (Chambers, 2001, p. 61; Davidoff et al., 1999, p. 190). Nonetheless, the ideals of the ‘companionate marriage’ of the early twentieth century may have suggested egalitarian relationships between men and women, but they were still attached to a model of family which required a male ‘head’ and was fundamentally

patriarchal. Therefore, the concept integrated the seemingly oppositional characteristics of power and control with the sexual and emotional attributes of what was later called the 'conjugal family' (Linton, 1949; Goode, 1963). Yet, the public acceptance of the 'companionate marriage' laid the groundwork for the separation of reproduction from sex and the idea that marriage was not simply a means to childbearing, even if this was still considered a key function (Chambers, 2001, p. 62).

According to Elliot (1996), by the 1950s, sociologists considered sexual and parental relationships in western societies to still be anchored around the nuclear family unit, traditionally based on everlasting marriage and women's mothering. However, they started to realize that the nuclear family had become relatively independent of kin and was influenced by a renewed emphasis on the emotional closeness of 'husband and wife', and 'parents and children' - constituting the 'conjugal family', or else, the 'modern functional family' as the norm. The already existing emphasis on mutual affection, psychological intimacy, and egalitarianism was now facilitated by the rising living standards, which boosted investment of resources, time and energy in the house and in family leisure. This was also the case with the growing engagement of men in the everyday family routine. Hence, the nuclear family was deemed as a key factor to personal happiness and self-fulfilment (pp. 6-7). Nevertheless, for Chambers (2001), the regular practices of the 1950s family life, including key undertakings like domestic consumption, did not entail co-operation between family members as an undifferentiated family unit, but the exercise of male dominance and female subjection. In fact, domestic consumption was neither communal nor egalitarian. It was structured around men's ideological claim to economic authority and breadwinning status, and women's dependence. Yet, despite the components of consumption and individualism being influenced by gender inequalities, they were naturalised through the 'nuclear family narrative' (pp. 50-51).

As Stacey (1999) notes, this golden phase of the 'nuclear family narrative' of the 1950s coincided with television becoming a mass medium, and indeed the new 'member' of the American family. The decade was also marked by the tensions of the Cold War and the emergence of the US as the dominant global power. Therefore, the first wave of American sitcoms produced, such as *The Adventures of Ozzie and Harriet* (ABC, 1952-1966), *The Amos 'n Andy Show* (CBS, 1951-1953) and *The Life of Riley* (NBC, 1949-1950, 1953-1958), projected idealized images of middle-class, white, 'invincible' families into the collective national unconscious, reflecting, even romanticizing, the existing structure and values of the family audiences they aimed to entertain (pp. 199-200).

However, the sentimental imagery television used in its early days to construct the boundaries of the American nuclear family would soon shift. According to Chambers (2001), as the decade progressed, in sitcoms such as *The Beverley Hillbillies* (CBS, 1962-1971), *I Love Lucy* (CBS, 1951-1957), *The George Burns and Gracie Allen Show* (CBS, 1950-1958), and the animated sitcom *The Flintstones* (ABC, 1960-1966) the ideal family was rarely depicted in a straightforward manner. Instead, the comedic elements of these series derived from breaching the rules of the idealized family - in other words, comedy was generated by depicting the 'dysfunctional family'. Its dysfunctionality was often mediated via a narrative of rupture and crisis, which were either caused by the peculiar yet charming personalities of the main family members or by intrusive outside influences. In *The Beverley Hillbillies* and *The Flintstones*, for instance, the resolution to the dysfunctionality would often come from the kin of the family members or characters of the wider community, who would step in to 'morally rescue' the family. Thus, in the first couple of decades of the American sitcom, despite the portrayal of family dysfunctionality, the series tended to express the ideals of the mid-century family, such as compassion, loyalty, dedication, selflessness, and stability. In this way, the depicted fragility of the white, nuclear family could be alluded to in order to highlight the necessity to 'work at' creating the ideal family 'for real' (Chambers, 2001, pp. 71-72).

By the 1960s, this paradigm of the ideal nuclear family was to face challenging pressures for change, as a vigorous critique of the 'conjugal family', along with demands to validate alternative lifestyles, emerged. As Elliot (1996) explains, a variety of groups and tendencies, such as self-actualization advocates, proponents of sexual freedom and gay liberation, sections of socialism, and sections of feminism, gave the incentive for the development of the notion of permissive morality and alternatives to the traditional family. Permissive morality and its new alternatives were founded on a shared emphasis on equality, individual autonomy, and self-realization, as well as a shared view of the traditional family as limiting freedom, preventing self-realization, and constricting intimacy. In line with these liberationist thoughts, individual freedom ought to encompass the ability to choose from a range of sexual and parental relationships, while a social life based on mutual negotiation of commitments, rather than obedience to societally established obligations, was also embraced. At the same time, the emphasis on procreational sex and the needs of the child, which had predominated the ideology of the traditional family, was sought to be replaced with an emphasis on recreational sex and the rights of adults (p. 9). Additionally, the growing participation of women in the paid labour force, along with the mid-twentieth century increase in state welfare, diminished the necessity of the nuclear family regarding the economic support of women and

children, allowing for the creation of alternatives (p. 12). The feminist strands of alternative lifestyles that emerged associated the conventional 'conjugal family' with male oppression and attempted to reconstruct sexual and parental relationships in ways that aimed to transform the gender norms (p. 9).

According to Elliot (1996), the spread of these ideologies, however, was not universal and equally persistent throughout the western world. Originating in Scandinavia and other Nordic nations, they rapidly expanded to northwest Europe and the Anglo-Saxon world. In these places, acceptance of sexual relationships before marriage soon evolved into acceptance of unmarried cohabitation. In Scandinavia, for example, long-term cohabitation before marriage became the norm, age at marriage increased, while the proportions of women marrying decreased. Nevertheless, in Ireland and southern Europe, where extended family bonds seemed to be more resilient, gender inequalities apparent, religious values to play a pivotal part in the public and private life, and the notion of family to be historically anchored around collectivist rather than individualistic values, they developed slowly (pp. 12-13).

Within this 1960s framework of societal changes, an American sitcom which, according to Chambers (2001), managed to stand out in terms of its family representation was *The Addams Family* (ABC, 1964-1966). With its inherently dysfunctional, graphic family members, it attempted to expose the hypocrisy and prissiness of the bourgeois American family of the era. Twenty years later, sitcoms such as *Married...with Children* (FOX, 1987-1997), *Roseanne* (ABC, 1988-1997) and the animated comedy *The Simpsons* (FOX, 1989-present) would follow on that path and turn their back on the pristine representation of family life in predecessor series. They would instead depict family members as spiteful, selfish, antisocial, pretentious, unintelligent, and sneering at others' troubles. This representation would harshly oppose the personalities of characters of series, such as the 1970s drama *The Waltons* (CBS, 1972-1981), where the mother, Olivia (Michael Learned), was portrayed as a selfless, loving, supporting, content with life, often displaying an artistic and dreamy nature; and the father, John (Ralph Waite), was framed as a hard-working, wise, protective, fearless, good-natured, sometimes stern and authoritative (pp. 71-72).

As to British sitcoms of the 1960s and 1970s, Eaton (1978) notes that the family was usually represented as an insular unit through a narrative signified by an inside/outside structure. For him, a British family sitcom that exemplified this structure was the *Till Death Us Do Part* (BBC1, 1965-1971), whose title alone demonstrated the endurance of the comic possibilities/situations that can occur within the family. Similarly, the title of its American equivalent *All in the Family* (CBS, 1971-1979) set the boundary: 'we do not have to look

outside the family for comedy or drama'. Other British shows that placed even greater emphasis on the inside/outside dichotomy portraying the relations of the family with the outside world - usually with neighbours, who were invited into the family drama - were: *Love Thy Neighbour* (ITV, 1972-1976), *Beggar Your Neighbour* (BBC1, 1966-1968), and *Meet the Wife* (BBC1, 1963-1966). In these sitcoms, 'the outside elements were essentially institutionalized in stock sets and running characters, the focus of the situation being the way one family unit reacts to another' (pp. 72-73).

Therefore, as Chambers (2001) puts it, in the sitcoms of the 1960s and 70s, 'the family' is presented as stable unit experiencing its weekly 'chaotic' drama caused by the outside world. During that era, series continued to celebrate the white nuclear family through dysfunctionality, but now within a private/public dichotomy, which highlighted the inside/outside boundary of the family as a distinct nuclearized unit. Also, the discords and tensions between the family and the inside/outside or the private/public represented significant societal concerns of the second half of the 20th century about 'how the individual, the family and the public world should interconnect with one another in the formation of gendered and sexed human subjects' (p. 74).

According to McNeil (1975, pp. 16-17), the 1970s American television, in terms of its representation of the 'gendered and sexed human subject' seemed to have highly overlooked the feminist movement described earlier in this section. Women were portrayed to still be more interested in marriage, parenthood, and domesticity (Gunter, 1995, pp. 13-14). When it comes to statistics, the vast majority of the female roles (74%) were married housewives concerned with romance or family issues, while men's interactions with these matters were just 18% of the cases. Women were hardly shown to have a job, especially if they had a family, and even if they did work, their working place/life was almost never seen on screen. In the rare occasions they were successful at their work, they were unsuccessful with men and relationships (McNeil, 1975, pp. 16-17). The female characters that were seen at their working place were often portrayed as 'incompetents and inferiors', as victims or having insignificant interests. Even in their 'traditional' domain, 'the home', men were the ones who solved both emotional and practical problems leaving women with little value in the American television world of the 1970s (Tuchman, 1978, pp. 13-14). Female characters appear, therefore, to have subject positions created for them, which placed them in 'the patriarchal work of domesticity and beautification' increasingly being able to have careers and explore their individuality, while, at the same time, look attractive (Barker, 2012, p. 324). Men, on the other hand, were depicted as dominant, assertive, adventurous, active, decision-makers, commanders, even aggressive (Gauntlett, 2008, p. 47). They were usually engaged with work and career or other outdoor

activities, such as sport. Hence, men and women were represented according to a set of fixed characteristics mostly determined by oppositions, such as 'indoors/outdoors, domestic/public, worker/boss, passive/active, rational/irrational' (Thwaites et al., 2002, p. 153).

By the 1980s, as liberation ideologies spread at varying rates in all the major industrial countries of the West, the separation of parenthood from marriage and the separation of childrearing from biological fatherhood constituted major areas of change in the family structures, giving rise to single-parenthood levels and cohabiting and stepparent family units (Elliot, 1996, p. 22). Divorced or alternative family forms gained more visibility and social acceptance. Old stereotypes and stigmatising characterizations such as 'the unmarried mother', 'deserted wives', 'broken homes' and 'fatherless families' started to be replaced by terms such as 'lone-parent families' and 'solo parenthood' (p. 26). As Elliot (1996) explains, diverse interpretations regarding these changes in sexual, parental, and gender relationships, which contributed to the transformation of family life, took place: for example, by traditionalists, who believed that departures from the 'conjugal family' was the disintegration of social order; radicals, who claimed the 'conjugal family' was an oppressive and bankrupt institution and welcomed its demise; and liberals, who saw diversity in family forms as a pathway to choice and self-determination. Despite the various interpretations and stands, however, what could be asserted was that there was no longer a dominating family form in the western world, but rather a rising pluralism (p. 35).

According to Dyer (1987), unlike the previous decades, the 1980s American television did not seem to overlook the ideological shifts in western societies. In fact, by the mid-1980s, programmes, mostly documentaries and talk shows, started incorporating women's issues, such as infertility, cervical and breast cancer, into their agenda - giving women central stage (p. 7). A sitcom of the era that portrayed women's issues through a progressive lens was *The Golden Girls* (NBC, 1985-1992). Staying away from stereotypes related to aging and femininity, the series featured three middle-aged women, Rose (Betty White), Blanche (Rue McClanahan), Dorothy (Bea Arthur) and an elderly woman, Sophia (Estelle Getty), living together and facing everyday matters, such as sexual life, career, health issues, and relationships. This sort of progressive representation continued through the early 1990s, as gender roles seemed to gradually become more equal, emancipated, and non-stereotyped. Towards the middle of the decade, just 8% of the female leading characters were the traditional 'homemakers' and only 3% had housewifery as their main occupation - 'a massive decrease from the 1970s' (Gauntlett, 2008, pp. 63-64). The woman of prime-time television was now mostly portrayed as 'young, single, independent, and free from family and workplace pressures' (Elasmar, 1999, p. 33). In

on-screen conversations, women and men were equal in terms of ‘the degree of control they exerted over dialogue, the power of their language use and the frequency with which they gave direct advice’ (Gauntlett, 2008, p. 64). As Lauzen (2006) notes, alongside the spread of liberation ideologies, a significant factor for that shift was the increasing percentage of women working in powerful behind-the-scenes positions. The employment of women as writers or producers was not only positively related to the percentage of female characters but contributed to their ‘more accurate’ on-screen representation, while their involvement in the plot, in terms of conflict and resolution, was more egalitarian for both female and male characters (p. 453).

Therefore, according to Gauntlett (2008), the American television series of the 1990s managed to arrive at more ‘comfortable, not-particularly-offensive models of masculinity and femininity’, which the majority of the viewers seemed to accept. For example, in the sitcom *Friends* (NBC, 1994-2004), the three male characters, Ross (David Schwimmer), Chandler (Matthew Perry) and Joey (Matt LeBlanc), merged within traditional representations of masculinity, but featured characteristics such as sensitivity, gentleness and male-bonding, while the three female characters, Rachel (Jennifer Aniston), Monica (Courteney Cox) and Phoebe (Lisa Kudrow), although undoubtedly feminine, were self-determining and non-housewifey. A pioneer characteristic of this particular series was that it revolved around the theme of male-female friendship; a friendship which worked as ‘a refreshing modern replacement for the traditional family’, which had dominated the narrative of sitcoms of the previous decades. Attempts to depict such ‘more equal genders’ took place in many series from the 1990s onwards, such as the medical drama *ER* (NBC, 1994-2009), the teen drama *Dawson’s Creek* (The WB, 1998-2003), the sitcom *Frasier* (NBC, 1993-2004), and the political drama *The West Wing* (NBC, 1999-2006) (p. 65).

4.3.2 The portrayal of ‘the family’ in the Greek comedy series of the 1990s: Tradition versus Modernity

Before embarking on the analysis of the portrayal of ‘the family’ in the Greek comedy series of the 1990s, it is important to point out that, similarly to the American trend of the era, the Greek series examined in the study tended to revolve around the topics of friendship and cohabitation with friends or relatives, rather than focus on portrayals of ‘the family’, especially the nuclear family. Such series were *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)/Οι Απαράδεκτοι* (MEGA, 1991-1993) and *Just Us (Emeis ki emeis)/Εμείς κι Εμείς* (MEGA, 1994-1998) which, even though preceded or aired simultaneously with the American sitcom *Friends* (NBC, 1994-2004), had friendship as their main theme and not the nuclear family. Whereas series such as

The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)/Οι Τρεις Χάριτες (MEGA, 1990-1992) and *With Two Mothers (Me Dyo Mamades)/Με Δύο Μαμάδες* (MEGA, 1998-1999) followed on the path of the American sitcom *The Golden Girl* (NBC, 1985-1992), which was still running when *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)*, in particular, went on air in early 1990. The focus of these two series was to depict the everyday life of a household which consisted only of women, related or unrelated, mostly over the age of 40.

Out of the sample of series selected for examination, few have the members of a nuclear family as protagonists. One of these limited cases is *Just Us (Emeis ki Emeis)*, in which, among the group of friends that star in the series, two of them, Maria (Maria Filippou) and Stelios (Stelios Pavlou), get married and, by the end of season one, have a baby - a necessary decision taken by the creators due to the pregnancy of the actress Maria Filippou. In the subsequent seasons, however, the on-screen portrayal of their baby son is scarce. Maria would usually inform the other characters that the baby is asleep in the bedroom, and thus the plots of the episodes would be irrelevant to the everyday life of a nuclear family and the upbringing of a child. Another series, analysed later in the section, which portrays a nuclear family consisting of a mother, Roza (Maria Georgiadou), a father, Evangelos (Christos Efthimiou) and a teenage son, Aristomenis (Panagiotis Panagopoulos), is *The Bad Vizier (O Kakos Vezyris)/Ο Κακός Βεζύρης* (MEGA, 1997-1998). Yet, the son of the family appears only as a guest character in two episodes (episodes 15 and 16), as he is at a boarding school in Switzerland. There are also few instances that main female characters become mothers towards the last episodes of series, such as Dorita (Katerina Ziogou) in *Dolce Vita* (MEGA, 1995-1997), Marina (Evelina Papoulia) in *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)/Δύο Ξένοι* (MEGA, 1997-1999), and Flora (Iro Mane) and Soso (Kaiti Konstantinou) in *Crimes (Eglimata)/Εγκλήματα* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000). Nevertheless, in most of these cases, the series ‘utilized’ the addition of the babies to steer the plot in ways that create conflicts, and hence push storylines forward. For example, after Marina gives birth to twins, the plot revolves around her endeavours to keep the babies away from their biological father, Konstantinos (Nikos Seryanopoulos). In the case of *Crimes*, a pure black comedy, Flora’s baby comes as a consequence of her affair with Soso’s husband, Alekos (Kostas Koklas), while her own husband, Achilleas (Christos Chatzipanagiotis), is infertile - ‘unfortunate’ situations which would contribute to bringing the series to a tragic end. In Dorita’s case, her marriage to Charis (Christoforos Papakaliatis) and the birth of their child towards the end of the series, would start bringing her story arc, as a secondary character, to completion.

The lack of representation of nuclear family life in Greek comedy series of the 1990s started to shift in the 2000s with the production of family comedies, which established the incorporation of underage actors in the main cast. Some of these series were *Strictly in the Family (Akros Oikogeneiakon)/Άκρως Οικογενειακών* (ANTENNA, 2001-2003), *Happy Together (Eftihismenoi Mazi)/Ευτυχισμένοι Μαζί* (MEGA, 2007-2009), and *My Lovely Neighbours (Latremenoi mou Geitones)/Λατρεμένοι μου Γείτονες* (MEGA, 2007-2009). According to Vamvakas (2019), the 2000s were also the era that representations of divorced families, and especially the complex relationship between divorcees and their children became more frequent. He notes that even though, in the past, series portraying alternative types of families fixated on the difficulty regarding their acceptance by public opinion, with matters such as remarriage being satirized, comedies of the 2000s started presenting such issues as an inevitable, if not desirable, reality of contemporary life (p. 27). Some of the 2000s series that offered representations of divorcee parents or remarriage were *What Soul Will You Deliver, You Fool Woman? (Ti Psychi Tha Paradoseis Mori?)/Τι Ψυχή θα Παραδώσεις Μωρή;* (MEGA, 2000), *All the Best (I Ora i Kali)/Η Ώρα η Καλή* (MEGA, 2004-2007), and *Happy Together* mentioned above.

Nevertheless, the Greek comedy series of the 1990s, which is the focus of this study, can still provide sufficient and solid data to examine representations on the topic of ‘family’. Portrayals of nuclear families might have been scarce, but there is a family type heavily utilized in the comedies of the era - the single parent only-child family. In the cases investigated, the single family comes to be after the death of one of the parents, mostly the father, which always occurs before the storyline of each series begins. The only-children are either young adults, usually attending university, at least at the beginning of the series [such as Teti (Anna Kouri) in *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)*, Dorita (Katerina Ziogou) in *Dolce Vita*, and Annoula (Chara Kefala) in *With Two Mothers (Me Dyo Mamades)*, who, in her case, constantly failed to get into one], or are older, having careers and living alone, but always retaining a very close relationship with their parent [such as Konstantinos (Nikos Seryanopoulos) in *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)*, Anna (Nena Menti) in *Sinning Twice (To Dis Eksamartein)*, Iasonas (Pavlos Evangelopoulos) in *The Penthouse (To Retire)*]. The widowed mothers that we meet in the series are Olga (Anna Panagiotopoulou) in *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)*, Christina (Anna Panagiotopoulou) in *Dolce Vita*, Amalia (Nefeli Orfanou) and Thalia (Maria Martika) in *The Penthouse (To Retire)*, Ermioni (Maria Martika) in *Just Us (Emeis ki Emeis)*, Yolanda (Ntina Konsta) in *Sinning Twice (To Dis Eksamartein)*, Deni (Ntina Konsta) in *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)*, Koula (Chrysa Ropa) in *With Two Mothers (Me Dyo Mamades)*, and

Machi (Soula Athanasiadou) in *Crimes (Eglimata)*. Unlike widowed women, however, there are no widowed men in the main cast of the series. Widowers appear as guest characters for a small number of episodes, as in the case of Mr. Delivorias (Dimitris Kallivokas) in *Dolce Vita*, Mr. Brakoulis (Nikos Kapios) in *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)*, Mr. Angelopoulos (Spiros Kalogirou) in *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)*, and Mr. Mantarinakis (Giorgos Velentzas) in *Constantine's and Helen's (Konstantinou kai Elenis)*. The only exception that a widower is a member of the main cast takes place in *Crimes (Eglimata)*, where Achilleas and his wife, Flora, cohabit with his bedridden widowed father Aristidis (Athinodoros Prousalis).

As we can see from the number of characters that are single parents, despite the trend of the era which focused on the topic of friendship, family images are apparent in the 1990s series. Even though the offsprings of the single parents are all adults, their complex relationships constitute a crucial part in the construction of plots through conflicts created from their everyday interactions. Furthermore, in terms of the ideological context around the topic of 'family', the series offer a plethora of examples where characters' views on the subject are expressed. In the cases analysed below, we can see that scenes that depict discussions on the topic usually occur when a young character comes up with a decision or a point of view that contradict the established ideology, which strictly revolves around the 'conjugal family'. The alternatives to the traditional family model that repeatedly come up in the series examined are the ideas of single parenthood by choice and out-of-marriage children. The following examples, therefore, showcase the ideological framework presented within the conflicting beliefs of characters on the above 'alternative' family models, giving us the opportunity to investigate the link between 'tradition' and 'family', mentioned in the beginning of the subchapter, and its contribution to the creation of Greek comedy.

Starting with *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)/Οι Τρεις Χάριτες* (MEGA, 1990-1992), in episode 52, Teti (Anna Kouri) confides to her aunts, Maria (Nena Menti) and Irini (Mina Adamaki), that she is pregnant. Even though she is broken up with her boyfriend, Sakis, who is unaware of the pregnancy, she desires to keep the child and raise it as a single parent. She asks from her aunts to mediate and announce the news to her mother, Olga (Anna Panagiotopoulou), who is known to be an oppressive mother. Maria and Irini accept and attempt to let their sister, Olga, know that Teti has decided to become a single parent. Maria and Irini - who later admit of having been shocked by Teti's decision but hid their surprise during their conversation with her - start giving Olga hints to prepare her for what she is about to hear. One of their indirect cues comes through a discussion about Greece's low birth rates, which, according to Maria and Irini, causes demographic problems that would lead to 'the

elimination of Hellenism'. Even though this point of the episode diverts slightly from the single parenthood theme, it offers an interesting insight on the characters' views on the sociocultural issue of birth deficit and its consequences to the country, its traditions, and language. In detail, Maria and Irini say: 'What a pity! Our mores, our customs, our language are going to be lost! The language of Homer, Aeschylus, Aristotle!' leaving Olga completely puzzled by their sudden 'romanticised' patriotic turmoil. The only solution to the 'demographic problem', according to Irini, is that Greeks have more children; a suggestion put in place as a failed attempt to pre-empt Olga's negative reaction to Teti's decision to become a single parent.

Once Olga finally finds out that Teti is pregnant and has decided to raise the child on her own gets outraged and exclaims: 'Where is she? I'm going to pull her hair out! I'm going to kill her! [...] I'll kill my child, *I'll become a Medea* (a mythological woman who killed her children)! She's better off dead than hurting me all the time! [...] My Christ, my daughter will become a mother of a fatherless child!' This exaggerated 'dramatic' monologue, which highly demonstrates Olga's unaccepting views on the subject of single parenthood, contradicts Maria and Irini's position on the topic. They both express that the birth of a child is 'the joy of life' and 'the hope of tomorrow', calling Teti a progressive person. Nonetheless, Olga claims that being a mother gives her the right to be a 'fascist' (as she describes herself) and demands that her daughter marries the father of her upcoming baby. After an intense conversation, Irini states that 'a woman must have a child when she feels the need to have one and must get married when she feels the need to get married' to which Maria adds 'we cannot force these two needs to occur at the same time if that's not the case.' Olga, unmoved, accuses her sisters of 'sounding too *left-winged*.' As a last resort, Maria and Irini admit to Olga that when Teti had told them about her decision to raise the child on her own, they were shocked yet pretended (in front of Teti) to be 'progressive' and 'comfortable' with the idea. They advise Olga that she does the same and, at least, pretend to be 'comfortable', 'progressive' and 'civilised' with the matter - a suggestion which Olga temporarily accepts.

Breaking down and analysing the behaviours and expressed beliefs of the characters in the above scenes, it is evident that single parenthood is portrayed as a controversial issue, signifying the non-homogenised ideological attributes met within the Greek society of the era. Teti (1), Maria and Irini (2), and Olga (3) constitute the three angles of a triangle, which exemplifies the key attitudes and views on the matter. Teti, the youngest, is fully in favour of single parenthood, representing a progressive aspect of Greece of the 1990s, detached from conservative social restraints and traditional beliefs around the issue of family and child-upbringing. Her mother Olga, on the other hand, embodies the 'old way of thinking', which

endeavours to uphold and 'save' the cultural physiognomies of the past. Lastly, Maria and Irini, Olga's slightly younger sisters, find common ground on both Olga and Teti's opposing beliefs. Therefore, they constitute a different category, which merges between the 'old' and the 'new' representing a group of people that even though respects the cultural values and established traditions, is open to potential change and breaking of social norms. The fact that they ultimately 'pretended' to have been comfortable with the idea of single parenthood does not eradicate their willingness to keep a positive attitude towards Teti's progressive decision.

The next episode (53) starts with Olga describing Teti's situation to aunt Bebekka (Anna Kyriakou). Bebekka is the sister of the deceased father of Olga, Maria and Irini, and therefore, the oldest character in the series. It would not have been unexpected if she held an even more negative opinion about Teti's decision, however, the scriptwriters, Michalis Reppas and Thanasis Papathanasiou, shaped the character of aunt Bebekka as non-conservative, active, rebellious and 'well-informed'. This tactic often helped them push the narrative of episodes forward as, on many occasions, aunt Bebekka's ideas resolved difficult situations (or brought complete chaos), but mostly increased the comical impact of the series, due the paradox deriving from the fact that the oldest person in the family was one of the most radical, non-essentialist figures - an element which was not common in the 1990s Greek comedy series. In this particular case, once Olga says to aunt Bebekka that Teti plans to have a child without being married ('without having made a family first!' - note that Olga does not recognise Teti and her child as a 'family'), Bebekka responds: 'What's all this fuss about 'the family'! What do you think 'the family' is? In our days the institution of the family is in crisis. [...] Family is a mechanism of human alienation. [...] Read *The Death of the Family* by David Cooper, and you'll understand. [...] The family is a social phenomenon of a patriarchal society which is in crisis nowadays, much like capitalism. Teti's decision is a rebellious act against the phallogocentric society. [...] My Olga, you have a daughter who wants to grab a hold of her own life without any man's support. You are so lucky to have a daughter who is a proud amazon!' Nevertheless, Olga replies to aunt Bebekka's 'didactic', feministic, strongly progressive words by stating: 'Quite the opposite! I'm so unlucky to have a crazy daughter and an even crazier aunt!'

After a failed attempt (in episode 52) and despite Teti's objection, Olga, assisted by her sisters, finds out the whereabouts of Sakis (the father of Teti's upcoming child, who Olga had never met before) and informs him about Teti's pregnancy. This action puts an end to Teti's wish to become a single parent, as after Olga's intervention Teti and Sakis (who we never see onscreen) make up. Even though the topic of single parenthood is over, a long part of episode 53 is dedicated to yet another related issue: out-of-marriage children. Olga over the moon with

Teti's reunion with Sakis and their moving-in together, asks Teti where they are going to buy the wedding dress from. Teti takes the opportunity to announce to her mother that she is just going to cohabit with Sakis and not get married. Predictably, this news leads to one more fight scene between Olga and Teti, which finishes with Olga yelling: 'Do whatever you like, but bear in mind one thing: I'm not giving you my blessings! If you don't get married, I'll write you off! [...] Don't call me mum! Call me Mrs. Charitou! [...] You should know that wherever you go, whatever you do the curse of your mother will follow you everywhere!'

'If they don't get married, I don't want to know neither of them' announces Olga to her sisters, in the next scene, devastated by the fact that her 'dream' to see her daughter having a double last name was shattered, alongside her wistfulness to 'kiss their wedding *stefana* (wreaths)'. At first, Maria and Irini try to help Olga realize that, at least, her wish that Teti raises her child with the support of the father has been fulfilled. However, Olga's obsession with the institution of marriage, forces them to use an alternative route in order to persuade her to reconcile with her daughter. They put emotional pressure on her by warning her that she will not get to see her grandchild if she remains negative with the idea of Teti and Sakis' living together unmarried; quite an effective tactic, as the prospect of Olga being a stranger to her grandchild is highly unwelcome. Finally, they remind her of her own obligations and responsibilities as a grandmother, which eventually convinces her to make up with her daughter.

The following scenes revolve mostly around Olga's overprotectiveness towards Teti (by overfeeding her, not letting her carry weights, etc.) and her eager attempts to become a 'proper' grandmother. 'The *granny* has been *awakened* in me!' Olga admits happily while crocheting baby socks to which aunt Bebeko 'progressively' responds: 'Don't say this word! You're not a granny! [...] You're the mother of a mother!' Teti listens in amazement as Olga, while knitting, feels free to decide that when the baby is born it will be named after her, if it's a girl, or after her deceased husband, if it's a boy. She moves on choosing what sort of subjects it will pick in high school, along with what its profession is going to be. The situation leads of course to another intense argument, yet everything is soon turned upside down once Teti finds out that the gynaecologist had made a mistake, and she is not actually pregnant. Consequently, Teti does not become a single mother, neither raises an out-of-marriage child along with Sakis. On the contrary, the lives of the characters return to the initial equilibrium state and the topics of single parenthood by choice and out-of-marriage children never attain an actual on-screen representation in the series.

Another example where the issue of single parenthood by choice is met occurs in episode 30 of *Dolce Vita/Ντόλτσε Βίτα* (MEGA, 1995-1997). In detail, Dorita (Katerina Ziogou) says to her mother Christina (Anna Panagiotopoulou) that she wants to have a baby and raise it on her own: ‘Mama, I want to have a child [...] It is a fact that I’m on fertile days.’ Christina, having been informed by their housekeeper, Aspasia (Maria Kavoyianni), that Dorita puts pressure on her ex-boyfriend, Antonis (Thanassis Efthimiadis), to have a child together (because of his ‘good genes!’), ironically yet irritated replies: ‘Is it a daughter that I have or a kitchen garden?’ - referring to what Dorita said about being on fertile days. Dorita ignoring her mother calling her a kitchen garden responds: ‘My concern now is to find a prospective father [...] I’m looking around. I’m checking the genes.’ Their intense conversation finishes with Christina furiously asking: ‘Are you also going to put an ad in the newspapers?’ to which Dorita answers determined: ‘If it’s necessary, yes!’ Coincidentally, Anna Panagiotopoulou in the role of Christina is the same actress who played Olga in *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)* few years earlier. Even though *Dolce Vita* was written by a different duo of scriptwriters (Alexandros Rigas and Lefteris Papapetrou), the premise of this episode follows the same pattern as the episodes related to single parenthood in *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)*: a conservative mother in conflict with her radical daughter in regard to the latter’s wish to become a single mother by choice.

The conflict created between the characters, directly and indirectly affected, provides information about the spectrum of the various ideological beliefs and behaviours simultaneously met within the Greek society of the 1990s. This spectrum of different ways of thinking around the topic of single parenthood is shortly portrayed in a scene in *Just Us (Emeis ki emeis)/Εμείς κι Εμείς* (MEGA, 1994-1998), as well. In detail, in episode 38, while the main characters wait at the corridor of a maternity clinic for their friend Maria (Maria Filippou) to give birth, Natasa (Natasa Manisali), a dynamic, career-oriented, single woman in her 30s, expresses her desire to have a child. According to her words, however, being unmarried such an idea is out of her reach. Specifically, she utters: ‘You see, I’m left with the petit bourgeois residues which don’t allow me to go find a clever guy, have a child with him and then tell him: My dude, go back to your mum now, thanks for the help! I’m going to take over with the kid now! You see, I don’t dare doing it!’ Her friend, Parthena (Eleni Gerasimidou), the Pontian woman who recently migrated to Greece from Pontos (see section 4.1.6), confused with what Natasa just said, wonders: ‘What’s this woman saying? Is she going to have a child without a man?’ to which her cousin Antonia (Maria Kanellopoulou) responds: ‘Don’t bother, Parthena! Her ‘emancipating from the nation’ feministic beliefs woke up!’ Nevertheless, Parthena does

bother and insists on making her views on the subject clear by stating: ‘A child wants both its mother and father. When it grows up and asks you: Mum, where is my daddy? What are you going to answer? Go find him? Crazy woman, shame on you!’ Even though Natasa is known to be one of the most opinionated, unconservative, strong female figures in the series, is unable to reply and repel Parthena and Antonia’s remarks on what she said about becoming a single parent and their conversation on the subject stops there.

Evidently, none of the characters of the series analysed above that wanted to become single parents managed to succeed in fulfilling their wish and decision. There is, therefore, no actual representation of single parenthood by choice in any of the Greek comedy series of the study. The episodes examined are just attempts of the creators to flirt with the idea of single parenthood, scratching the surface of a phenomenon which the Greek society of the era was not ready to accept. According to Maratou-Alipranti (1998), in 1991, the single-parent households with at least one child under the age of 15 constituted the 5.7% of the family households in Greece (p. 189). She observes, however, that single parenthood was not a conscious choice in most cases (p.190). Despite the lack of sufficient data, she notes that the majority (80%) of single-parent families came to be as a result of divorce or death of one of the parents (p.194). Indeed, the series examined seem to reflect these data as, especially when it comes to the portrayal of single-parent families, they are ‘legitimized’ only as a result of widowhood, as mentioned earlier in this section.

Similarly to the topic of single parenthood, there is no actual representation of out-of-marriage children in the comedy series studied either. Parenthood is represented as merely taking place within marriage, or else, the ‘conjugal family’. The idea of out-of-marriage children might have been teased in the beginning of the 1990s in episodes 52 and 53 of *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)* with Teti and Sakis’ attempt not to get married due to Teti’s (supposed) pregnancy, yet even towards the end of the decade, the general attitude around this subject remained unchanged. For instance, in the fourth season of *Just Us (Emeis kai Emeis)*, the whole premise of episode 114 is dedicated to the issue of out-of-marriage children. In detail, Smaragda (Smaragda Diamantidou) after a sudden loss of consciousness takes a pregnancy test which comes out positive. The child’s father is her boyfriend Vasilis (Vasilis Koukouras), a famous soap-opera actor, with whom Smaragda cohabits. When she announces her pregnancy to her friends Maria and Natasa, and her older sister Antonia, who shares the flat with the couple, the latter says: ‘Since we have so many expenses during this period it’s not convenient to undertake wedding arrangements, but what alternative do we have after what you have done?’ to which Smaragda unapologetically responds: ‘Wedding arrangements? What

wedding? [...] I'm sorry girls but you don't get it, at all!' After such statement, Natasa breaks the fourth wall and addresses to the camera: 'The serial starts now!' - a one-liner which insinuates that the focus of the episode will not only revolve around the fact that Smaragda and Vasilis are having a child without being married, but around the conflict among the characters as a result of that.

As noticed, once Antonia, Maria and Natasa hear about the pregnancy, they take for granted that Smaragda and Vasilis are immediately going to get married, even though the couple is known for standing against the institution of marriage throughout the series. Soon, it becomes clear that the couple's decision is not just disrespected but evokes extreme objections by their relatives and friends. For example, in a private conversation between Smaragda and her sister Antonia, the latter, fed up, calls out: 'Stop the bullshit! You live with Vasilis for years. Because of the child, it's an opportunity for you both to get married. It's dead simple! [...] Don't you care about *the people*? What are going to say?' to which Smaragda answers: 'I don't give a shit (about what *the people* are going to say)!'. The tension escalates more as Antonia opposes again: 'But I take people's opinion into account, and I respect them. If you're under the impression that you just sprouted into this world, I remind you that you have two parents and whatever you are right now you owe it to them. It's your duty not to dishonour them! [...] Your life is not yours at all! It belongs to the ones that gave it to you, your mum and dad!' As observed, Antonia's behaviour towards Smaragda, regarding her opposition to marriage, is highly coercive and rigid, exemplifying not just the unacceptance of the idea of out-of-marriage children, but also the emotional abuse, interventionism, and isolation that family members undergo if they do not adhere to the cultural values and traditions.

Therefore, the series, as a pure prime-time comedy show of the era, produces humour by sustaining a sarcastic and satirical attitude towards norms and social constraints, whose portrayal is essential in constructing the premise and plot of episodes. The series does not just tease progressive ideas, such as having a family out of marriage, but employs, on the one hand, representations of rigid, conservative sociocultural beliefs and, on the other, their opposing forces, as the base upon which the plot, and by extension the series, is built. The fact that the creators chose to use this approach to crafting episode premises and plots is a strong indicator of the potency that cultural and behavioural models possessed in the Greek society of the 1990s. The comedic effect is produced by characters attempting to inverse those models and introduce a new way of thinking. During that specific point in history, however, the old ways seemed to still have the upper hand. In fact, according to Maratou-Alipranti (1998), in 1995 out of all the member countries of the European Union of the time, Greece had the smallest percentage of

out-of-marriage births, standing at 3%, while for other southern member countries, such as Italy, Spain and Portugal, their out-of-marriage birth rates were significantly higher, standing at 8%, 10.8% and 18.7% respectively (pp. 191-192). Thus, out-of-marriage births was a rare phenomenon in the 1990s Greece. Through the examination of how this issue was portrayed in the comedy series of the era, we can deduce that the small percentage of out-of-marriage births was the result of a persistent prevalence of traditional ideologies on the matter, which sustained an adverse social milieu that discouraged Greeks who wished to have children outside the institution of marriage from doing so.

Within such an unaccepting social environment, Smaragda asks her boyfriend Vasilis, who supports her decision not to get married because of the unexpected pregnancy: ‘Vasilis, because I can foresee that many things are going to happen (meaning they will face many objections by their friends and family), I want to know if you’re going to be by my side during my battle to remain an unmarried mother. [...] Are you going to support me in my fight for equal rights against the social establishment?’ The selection of words, such as ‘equal rights’ and ‘against the social establishment’ alongside the exaggerated, satirical way this sentence is performed by the actress Smaragda Diamantidou imply that ‘equal rights’ within the ‘social establishment’ (at least on this particular matter) are not just out of the question but the mere articulation of such words constitutes a comical phrase put in place to provoke laughter from the audience.

News spreads fast within an environment where interventionism and the lack of privacy are prominent attributes among kin, friends and ‘the neighbourhood’. So, soon enough, the shopkeeper Champos (Tasos Perzikianidis), the Pontian second cousin of Smaragda and Antonia, is informed by the latter about the situation. He shouts furiously in his shop, mostly in the Pontian dialect: ‘My own cousin! My own cousin wants to have a child without being married! [...] Antonia, I’m going to get crazy, don’t tell me such things! [...] I’ll beat her! I’ll break her ribs! [...] If her dad finds out about it, he’ll kill himself! [...] She’ll be forced to marry him (Vasilis), otherwise I’m going to kill her!’ This graphic over-reaction highly satirizes the phallocratic, violent establishment of the past, whose elements are concentrated in the character of Champos constituting him the ‘traditional’ Greek man - and by extension, a representative of anachronistic cultural and behavioural models that could still be found in the 1990s Greece. However, the beliefs and attitudes he represents are just remnants of their former self, as Champos is not capable of executing any of his violent threats, neither are the other characters truly afraid of him. His role remains a mere graphic reminder of the old ‘Greek-self’

utilized for comic effect. Yet, his influence is often enough to evoke frustration and problematic situations for the people around him.

An opposing force to Champos and Antonia's views on the subject emerges with the arrival of Telis (Konstantinos Katselis), who is a young dentistry student. Once he steps in the shop, Antonia attempts to tell him straight away about the situation with her sister's pregnancy and her insistence not to get married. Champos, however, interrupts her: 'Don't tell him, we're going to be ridiculed!' Clearly, such a thing, according to Champos, should be kept secret from the public as it will dishonour the family. Still, Antonia insists on informing Telis as: 'The guy is ours' meaning that Telis is a neighbour friend, therefore he belongs in their circle. Telis responds to the news by saying: 'Well-done her!', proud of Smaragda's decision not to get married because of her pregnancy. As expected, this causes Champos to verbally attack Telis, yet Telis strikes back yelling: 'She (Smaragda) is a free person, she can do whatever she likes!'

Once Smaragda and Natasa enter the scene, Telis exclaims encouragingly: 'Hurrah Smaragda! I'm with you!' He is evidently the only character in the series, apart from the actual couple, who is positive towards out-of-marriage children. Even Natasa, who in episode 38 conveyed her desire to become single parent, admits that she would have gotten married for practical reasons if she was in Smaragda's shoes. Likewise, Maria in a conversation with Smaragda, later in the episode, comments that such a thing is 'unheard of', while her husband, Stelios (Stelios Pavlou), adds: 'As you know (Smaragda) I'm not a conservative person, but your obsession not to get married doesn't make any sense!' The resolution to the commotion comes with Smaragda receiving a call from her gynaecologist letting her know that the positive pregnancy test result she had got was wrong.

Thus, *Just Us (Emeis kai Emeis)* does not offer an on-screen representation of out-of-marriage children - an approach to the matter that does not differ from the examples on single parenthood examined earlier. Hence, the alternative paradigms to the 'conjugal family', even though 'negotiated' throughout the Greek comedy series of the 1990s, seemed unable to overturn the established, traditional beliefs. As Vamvakas (2019) puts it, 'a matter of interest is not so much the insistence of tradition in popular Greek series but the existence of cases in which the depiction of the past becomes dominant and destabilizes modernized beliefs and roles' (p. 34). Indeed, in the cases analysed so far, 'the past' prevailed over all attempts for modernization. Nonetheless, there are two series that, unlike the above cases, managed to break new frontiers on the subject, as their portrayal of family diverged from the 'conjugal family' paradigm. They did not just tease alternative ideas only to return to the initial equilibrium, but they either achieved the fruition of an unconventional family model by the end of the story or

based their whole premise on portraying the everyday life of an alternative household since episode one. These two series are *Sinning Twice (To Dis Eksamartein)/To Δις Εξαμαρτείν* (MEGA, 1993-1996) created by Michalis Reppas and Thanasis Papathanasiou (the writing duo of *The Three Charites*), and *With Two Mothers (Me Dyo Mamades)/Με Δύο Μαμάδες* (MEGA, 1998-1999) written by Panos Amarantidis and Spiros Metallinos (the scriptwriters of *Just Us*).

In detail, *Sinning Twice (To Dis Eksamartein)* takes place at the facilities of a fictitious television channel, called Media Channel. The protagonist of the series is Anna (Nena Menti), a successful news director, who is married to a renowned news presenter, Giannis (Charis Sozos). Her flamboyant mother, Yolanda (Ntina Konsta), one of the shareholders of the channel (and later on in the series, the programme director), contributes to hiring Petros (Alexandros Antonopoulos), another famous news presenter, to co-present the newscast with Giannis. At first, the focus of the series seems to be the professional rivalry between Giannis and Petros, however, Petros would soon start an affair with Giannis' wife, Anna. For a period, the plot revolves around their secret relationship, and its emotional and social complexities. Eventually, after seven years of marriage, Giannis and Anna break up. Still having feelings for one another, they manage to make up, but Anna fails to cease her affair with Petros. Hence, the three of them compromise on forming an 'atypical' situation where she would have both men as her partners. The plot is, then, built around their struggle to make this sort of relationship work and gain the approval of their circle of colleagues and relatives.

Alongside its comedic and entertaining nature, the series succeeds in portraying multidimensional personalities and complex emotional states, especially through Anna's character integrity, who, despite her infidelity and the 'love triangle' situation she put herself into, does not comply with the negative, one-dimensional stereotype of the 'easy' or hypersexual woman. The story continues with Anna giving birth to a baby girl. In spite of her mother's, Yolanda, eagerness to discover who of the two men is the father, it is never revealed. Instead, the series ends with the creation of a family which consists of two fathers (Giannis and Petros), one mother (Anna) and a daughter, who they named after her grandmother, Yolanda - an 'unusual' family, which eventually gets warmly accepted by the rest of the characters. The series, therefore, does not only portray the battle between the 'old' and the 'new' throughout its premise, but provides a brave, unconventional resolution. The attempt to finish the story with the representation of a three-parent family stands out from the rest of the series analysed above, where alternative paradigms on the topic of 'the family' (such as single parenthood and out-of-marriage children) would be let down by the narrative itself, with, e.g., the revelation that the pregnancy test result was wrong.

With Two Mothers (Me Dyo Mamades), on the other hand, portrays a family which consists of two mothers, Koula (Chryssa Ropa) and Dora (Nena Menti), and a daughter in her early twenties, Annoula (Chara Kefala). The biological mother of Annoula is Dora, who after giving birth to her, secretly leaves her at the doorstep of Koula and her husband, Prokopis (uncredited). Koula and Prokopis, who do not have children of their own, take Annoula in and raise her. A couple of decades later, at Prokopis' funeral, Dora introduces herself to Koula and Annoula and reveals that she is Annoula's real mother. Three years later, Dora and Koula, having become friends, decide to cohabit in a new house, so all three women can live together as an 'unusual' family. The plots of the episodes often revolve around Annoula, a rebellious and vibrant young woman, as she tries to figure out her next steps in life, such as decide if she attends a university or starts some sort of career. Time and again, the comic effect of the series derives from Dora and Koula's conflicts in their attempts to advise their daughter and steer her to the right direction, not only when it comes to studies or career, but also in regard to her love life, housekeeping, ways of thinking and behaviour. However, through these conflicts the series offers direct representations of mothering executed by two mothers without the help of a father. There are, of course, male figures in the series, such as Annoula's boyfriend Akis (Giorgos Kritikos), and her uncle Vasilis (Christos Nomikos). Even though Vasilis, who lives at a different flat in the same building, may sometimes work as a father figure, he is mostly utilized through the plot as Dora's secret love affair, and not as a character with substantial interactions with Annoula. This highlights even more Koula and Dora's mothering responsibilities within this atypical Greek family.

Despite the 'alternative' approach of *With Two Mothers (Me Dyo Mamades)* in regard to the portrayal of 'the family', the dichotomy between the 'traditional' and the 'modern' still plays as important a role in the comedy-making of this series, as was the case with the rest of the series analysed earlier in the section. In this case, however, the dichotomy between the 'old' and the 'new' is not only actualised through the presentation of competing points of view on issues related to the institution of family, but through the incompatible personalities of the two mothers. On the one hand, Koula represents the 'traditional Greek woman', characterised by conservative opinions on gender, housekeeping and family raising. She is caring, skilful, hardworking, self-sacrificing, and loyal mother and friend. At the same time, she is fearful, neurotic, uneducated, and emotionally scarred by her late husband's infidelities. She is strict with Annoula, constantly raising her voice, commanding, and criticizing not only her daughter but all the characters of the series. Apart from restricting Annoula's freedom of choices, she often restrains herself when it comes to life pleasures and diminishes her own worth as a

woman. On the other hand, Dora is an independent, experienced and satisfied with life woman, who never married. She is intelligent, calm, educated and well-travelled, often demonstrating femme fatale traits. As a parent, she is aggregable, permissive, open-minded, and wise. In episode 7, for example, in an argument with Koula, she says: ‘When I first moved in here, we had so many discussions, and among other matters we arranged our responsibilities concerning Annoula. [...] You agreed that when it comes to psychological and inner-self issues (that Annoula might be dealing with), I’m going to be in charge.’ Alongside her progressive beliefs, interests in psychology, welfare, and sexual liberation, Dora often comes across as self-absorbed, snobbish, dismissive and lazy.

Apart from the portrayal of the relationship of the two mothers with themselves and with their daughter, the series also focuses on stories irrelevant to the topic of family, with plots built around interactions with friends, relatives, work, love interests, and various guest characters. On the whole, *With Two Mothers (Me Dyo Mamades)*, despite presenting an unconventional family unit, does not seem to be as daring a series as *Sinning Twice (To Dis Eksamartein)*. A reason that could have contributed to that is the fact that Koula and Dora are just friends and not a same-sex couple. Therefore, the series does not portray members of a family that have to struggle to get the acceptance of relatives and wider community. There is only a minor moment in episode 1 with Koula’s sister-in-law, Maroulia (Vana Partheniadou), briefly commenting that she finds the cohabitation of Koula and Dora strange, but despite her old-fashioned, obnoxious, judgmental character, she never brings this topic up again. Consequently, as in the previous cases examined, the comic effect of this series is, once again, shaped by conflicts deriving from the battling forces of tradition, which, in this instance, come from Koula’s conservative way of thinking, and forces of modernization, represented by Dora’s progressiveness.

When it comes to other, more ‘conventional’, family formations, such as ‘the childless family’ consisted of a heterosexual married couple, *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)/Oi Aparádekttoi* (MEGA, 1991-1993) offers us an episode (episode 36) which is, once again, shaped around the dichotomy between the ‘traditional’ and the ‘modern’, as is the case with the rest of the examples analysed in this section. Nevertheless, in this instance, there is a twist in the portrayal of the opposing forces of the ‘old’ and ‘new’. In detail, the episode starts with Dimitra (Dimitra Papadopoulou) sitting in the living room with her gay friend Giannis (Giannis Bezos) and, influenced by a romantic novel she was reading, she says to him: ‘I want a brutal man!’ to which Giannis answers: ‘You have (your husband) Spiros’. Displeased, she clarifies: ‘Spiros is not brutal, he’s a splat ball! [...] If only he was more brutal. I don’t mean I want him

to beat me up, just to be more decisive'. In the following scene, we see Spiros (Spiros Papadopoulos) at his workplace contemplating the handle of his office door. He is lost in thought reflecting upon his upcoming eight-year wedding anniversary with Dimitra. Vlassis (Vlassis Bonatsos) enters the office, and they start a conversation about Spiros' concern that he has lost part of his manliness and control over Dimitra: 'I've lost the upper hand in our household [...] In the past, once I entered the house and raised my voice, the walls trembled, and she (Dimitra) stood at attention! Now, I speak and shout, nothing happens! [...] I don't feel like a man lately [...] I can't impose myself. I've lost my toughness. Yet, I'm Greek, not weak, so normally if a woman talks back to me (objects), I cut off her ears!' The two men conclude that Spiros should toughen his behaviour towards Dimitra in order to reclaim his lost manliness. Therefore, once he returns home and finds out that Dimitra did not have the time to prepare a meal for him, he starts yelling and breaking plates. Dimitra shouts back irritated: 'Why are you breaking the plates? Are you retarded?' and he answers: 'I'm a man, that's why I break them!' Angry but unintimidated she responds: 'Then break the fridge too, to feel even more like a man!' When their wedding anniversary day finally comes, Spiros decides that after the anniversary dinner, instead of spending time with Dimitra, he and Vlassis would watch a football match on the television. Dimitra strongly disagrees with this idea, yet the two men believe that choosing football over anniversary celebrations would be what 'real' men would do. The episode ends with Dimitra throwing the television they were watching the football match on down the balcony, seemingly prevailing over Spiros' expressions of 'manliness'. Nevertheless, the television she throws down the balcony injures an old lady, the mother of their landlord's fiancé - an unfortunate situation which forces Dimitra to apologize to Spiros and the rest of the characters for her behaviour.

Unlike examples analysed earlier in the section (related to the issues of single parenthood and out-of-marriage children, in which 'new' models would emerge, create conflicts that would eventually seize, bringing the characters' lives to the initial equilibrium), this episode depicts an already emancipated wife, who does not submit to her husband's phallographic attitudes, and a husband worried of the fact that he has no control over his wife, and hence, believes that he has lost his manliness. We notice, therefore, that, in terms of the gender dynamics within this childless family unit, the 'new' (represented by Dimitra) is portrayed to have already prevailed over the 'old' (represented by Spiros). For Spiros, this 'unfortunate' conjuncture implies that he has 'failed' as a 'Greek man' as, according to his way of thinking, the 'traditional' (here, anachronistic) role models expect a husband to have total dominance over his wife. Despite the fact that in this example the gender roles are presented

as ‘non-traditional’ and even progressive at first, the plot would soon focus on showing the couple’s endeavours to ‘return’ to an ‘old fashion’ state in which Spiros becomes ‘more brutal’ (according to Dimitra’s desire) and Dimitra ‘stands at attention once he enters the house’ as she used to do it the past (according to Spiros’ words). However, such endeavours fail, as Dimitra would eventually refuse to comply with Spiros’ decision to start acting in more ‘manly’ and ‘brutal’ ways. Her overzealousness, on the other hand, to act as an ‘overly’ dynamic and emancipated woman, towards the end of the episode, by throwing the television down the balcony injuring a passerby, would force her to apologize and reconsider her radical behaviour. Thus, the episode depicts a constant battle, or else, a constant back and forth, between the ‘old’ and the ‘new’ as they try to establish or reestablish their prevalence, in this case, in relation to the gender dynamics within a married couple.

In terms of ‘unconventional’ family units, such as families consisted of LGBT parents, there are no cases represented in the comedy series examined. In fact, when it comes to LGBT representation, throughout all the comedy series of the study, there are only two main characters that identify as gay, Giannis (Giannis Bezos) in *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)* and Apostolis (Alexandros Rigas) in *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)*, and one main character, Michalis (Stavros Nikolaidis) in *Crimes (Eglimata)*, who after a lot of inner struggle comes out as bisexual. In regard to family-related interactions, these three men are shown to be completely disassociated with anything that has to do with ‘the family’. In other words, it is not that we do not see them create a family of their own, but we never get to see (at least as guest characters) any members of their kin, such as their parents, siblings and other relatives, either. The only exception takes place in episode 20 of *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)*, in which Giannis tries to keep his homosexuality secret from an aunt of his, Virginia (Aliko Alexandraki), who happened to pay him a visit. In general, even though these three LGBT characters constitute active members within their community of friends and colleagues, they are usually portrayed as ‘lone wolves’, not only in regard to their limited on-screen interactions with their families, but in term of the romantic aspect of their lives as well.

Nevertheless, episodes 15 and 16 of *The Bad Vizier (O Kakos Vezyris)/O Kakós Βεζύρης* (MEGA, 1997-1998) offer the opportunity to examine the topic of ‘the family’ in association with LGBT-related representation. The example does not portray LGBT parents, but the struggle of a 16-year-old gay son within a ‘traditional’ Greek family. Yet even though the parents of the family, Evangelos (Christos Efthimiou) and Roza (Maria Georgiadou), are two of the main protagonists of the series, their underage son, Aristomenis (Panagiotis Panagopoulos), appears for only two consecutive episodes. In detail, episode 15 starts with

Roza receiving a phone-call from her son Aristomenis, who informs her that he has left the boarding school in Switzerland and is on his way to Greece. Worried, she calls her husband Evangelos, who is the minister for the Environment, Physical Planning and Public Works, to let him know. The news is distressing for Evangelos too, as is the case for his secretary Fani (Anna Chatzisofoia). Fani is the only employee at the ministry who knows that the minister has a son. Their stress and secrecy around Aristomenis' existence derive from the fact that he is gay - which is the reason why he is 'locked up' at a boarding school in Switzerland, in the first place. Even though at first Evangelos, Roza and Fani try to maintain Aristomenis' existence secret despite his arrival, the rest of the employees would soon find out about him and his sexuality. Once Kleon (Charis Romas), the Secretary General, whose fierce desire, throughout the series, is to find a way to 'dethrone' the minister and take his position, is informed about Aristomenis' 'case', decides to reveal to the public that the minister's son is gay. By doing so, he hopes the government would dismiss Evangelos, due to his son's sexuality, and appoint Kleon as the minister. Kleon's assistant Lazaros (Giorgos Galitis), however, warns Kleon that the government will not dismiss the minister because his son is gay. On the contrary, parts of the public would go against Kleon instead, blaming him for attacking minorities. This gives Kleon the idea to 'convince' Evangelos and his wife Roza to behave in a cruel way to their gay son for 'their child's own good and for maintain their reputation', then expose them through a television show for their cruelty, which would eventually lead to Evangelos' dismissal and Kleon's appointment as the new minister. In order to do that, Kleon uses Evangelos and Roza's negative predispositions against homosexuality to manipulate them to try to 'cure' Aristomenis by keeping him captive in the house and starving him until he 'reconsiders' his sexuality.

In the following episode (episode 16), through a series of events, alongside Evangelos and Roza's 'failure' to torture their son due to their parental love which, despite their prejudices and fears, manages to come to the surface, Kleon's evil plan falls apart. In particular, the people who ruin it are three employees of the ministry, Fani, Lazaros and Poli (Vaso Goulielmaki), along with Evangelos' secret mistress Anita (Natalia Kapodistria). Having found out about Kleon's plan to expose Aristomenis' torture through a television show, whose presenter, Makis (Kimon Rigopoulos), is known for his fights for human rights, they help Roza organise a drag-queen party. So, when Kleon and Makis, along with a government official, 'unexpectedly' arrive at the minister's house to expose him, they are confronted with a 'wild' party, which consists of many drag-queens, Anita, Aristomenis, his parents and various guests, such as ministry employees, all dancing to the music. The minister, in particular, is seen to be dancing

with a drag-queen - something that urges Makis to say to Kleon: 'From now on, I'm going to be supporting this man!'

These two episodes of *The Bad Vizier (O Kakos Vezyris)*, within their excessive representation of homophobia and sexuality-related misconceptions and prejudices, still structure their subject-matter around the battle between the 'old/conservative' and the 'new/unconventional', as is the case with the rest of the series examined earlier in the section. As we have seen so far, this battle between the 'old' and the 'new' is portrayed through conflicts that occur between two competing groups of characters. On the one hand, we have the 'unconventional' group of characters who attempt to overturn the norms by expressing new ideas, for example on how a family could come to be (e.g., through single parenthood or out-of-marriage children) or on self-actualization issues related to gender and sexuality (e.g., Dimitra in *The Unacceptables* and Aristomenis in *The Bad Vizier*). On the other hand, we have the 'conservative' group of characters who express 'traditional' points of view in their attempt to maintain the established ideologies and behaviours on these matters. Therefore, the portrayal of the relationship between the 'traditional' and 'modern', which, as noticed, has characterised the Greek comedy-making of the 1990s, takes place through the verbally expressed opinions of these two competing groups of characters - in other words, it is conveyed to the audience through dialogue. The only exception takes place in *The Bad Vizier (O Kakos Vezyris)* as, along with verbally expressed opinions that support or are against homosexuality, there is some 'action' taken by the group of characters that are against homosexuality as they temporarily keep Aristomenis captive. However, there are three instances, within the sample of series investigated, that the portrayal of the relationship between the 'old' and the 'new' is actualised not through verbal expressions of opposing opinions (or 'actions' that derive from opinions), but through three 'alternative' scriptwriting approaches.

According to the first 'alternative' approach, the dichotomy between the 'old' and the 'new' is presented through one single character, unlike the previous examples, where opposing beliefs and attitudes were portrayed through conflicts between characters that supported the 'new' and characters that supported the 'old'. The character in question is Korina (Maria Kavoyianni) from the black comedy series *Crimes (Eglimata)/Εγκλήματα* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000). In detail, Korina was temporarily given to an institution when she was 2 years old, but when her family returned for her, she had mysteriously disappeared. Around 30 years later, her bother Achilleas (Christos Chatzipanagiotis) searches for her through a television show and finds her. Korina had grown up to become a kind and vibrant woman. Yet, her relatives are surprised to discover that, regarding her profession, Korina is one of the most 'famous'

prostitutes of Athens. Even though, at first, she tries to present herself in a more ‘conservative’ way in front of her newly found family, she is not able to hide for long her sexually liberated, independent, non-traditional and, at the same time, empathetic, giving and ‘colourful’ personality. She is thrilled for having reunited with her family, especially with her bother with whom she builds a warm and accepting relationship, despite various tensions created due to her profession with other family member. Through her family, she would soon meet and fall in love with a medical doctor, Pavlos (Vasilis Eftaxopoulos), a charming and caring man. However, due to his ‘conventional’ and ‘quiet’ personality, she is afraid that she will lose him if he finds out what her real way of life is. Therefore, she creates a fake ‘persona’ for herself. She tells him that she is a primary school teacher and behaves as a ‘traditional’, low-profile and conservative woman. Of course, when she is not with Pavlos, she returns to her usual lifestyle, behaviour and profession. Through the following two examples taken from episodes 13 and 21 of *Crimes (Eglimata)*, we can see in practice how Korina, who as a character represents the ‘new’, ‘progressive’ and ‘unconventional’, manages to embody values of the ‘old’ and ‘traditional’ to her advantage. Alongside the portrayal of the ‘old’ and the ‘new’ essentialized through the same person, the scenes examined below were specifically chosen, among various moments in which Korina pretends to be a ‘traditional’ woman for Pavlos’ eyes (e.g., see analysis on episode 14 in section 4.1.3), because they are related, in their own way, to the subject of ‘family’, which constitutes the main topic of this subchapter. For instance, they reference the institution of marriage, outdated marriage-related customs, sex before marriage, and satirize anachronistic and sexist behaviours against women within the Greek household. The focus of the analysis, however, remains on examining the ‘alternative’ scriptwriting approach to the portrayal of the relationship between the ‘old’ and the ‘new’, as mentioned earlier, while aspects of the ‘family’ topic are still present.

Starting with the first example, in episode 13 of *Crimes (Eglimata)*, we see Korina trying to convince Pavlos for her conservatism and ‘properness’ by telling him that she is sexually inexperienced. Worried, however, that when she and Pavlos finally have sex, he is going to realize that she is not a virgin, she fabricates a story. In detail, she tells him that when she lived at the orphanage as a child, she got adopted by a boorish landholder farmer and his wife and grew up maltreated at a village in the countryside. Years later, after some wedding had taken place in their neighbourhood, she saw a blood-stained bedsheet spread out of their neighbours’ window. During that ‘golden epoch’ as she describes it, ‘the purity (virginity) of a bride-to-be was of most importance’. Therefore, it was tradition the white bedsheet that a newlywed couple used during their wedding night to be displayed out of their window the

following day. That practice was in place in order to show to the village that the bride was a virgin before the wedding - proved by the blood stains on the bedsheet indicating that her first sexual encounter took place during the wedding night. However, as a 'young and innocent girl (lady)' as she claims to have been, once she saw the blood-stained bedsheet hanging out of the neighbouring house, she ran to her foster parents yelling that the groom had killed the bride. She was rudely dismissed (especially by her foster father) and went back to the balcony to have another look at the neighbours' bedsheet. That time, though, she collapsed on the floor by attempting to climb on a chair to have a better view. Her foster parents called a doctor, who, after examining Korina, discovered that, during her fall, the wood of the chair ruptured her hymen. Such news was, of course, devastating for them. According to their words, it would be impossible to get her married in the future as she was now 'damaged (impaired)' - referring to the prospect that her potential husband would not believe she was virgin due to her ruptured hymen and choose not to marry her. Thus, the doctor offered to sign a 'virginity certificate' for them to use if such a case occurs. She continues recounting her made-up story by telling Pavlos that after that incident she went on with her life completely ignorant of what had happened to her. One day, while she was up a ladder trimming a tree, a village boy, Diamantis (Kostas Koklas), who came over to look up her skirt, convinced her to take her behind some bushes to show her a snake he had found. Not having realized that he was referring to his penis, once they got behind the bushes, they had sex. Diamantis suspected, however, that something was wrong with her hymen and informed the whole village about it. After that, they all considered her not to be a virgin. So, her family threw her out, and this was how she came to live in Athens.

In the second example (episode 21), Korina and Pavlos decide to have an official gathering at Korina's family home, so their families get to meet. Once Pavlos and his mother, Mrs. Logara (Betty Moschona), arrive at the place, he says to his mother privately: 'Don't be stressed. You'll see, they are all very warm people! A typical Greek family!' Soon, Korina enters the living room dressed conservatively in a grey dress, keeping her head down and her eyes on the floor in order to give the impression of a 'humble' lady. 'Excuse me for being late, but I was marking some school tests' she says to her future mother-in-law and Pavlos, who still believe that she is a primary school teacher. While they wait for the rest of her family to appear, Korina's sister-in-law, Flora (Iro Mane), offers them drinks. Pavlos and his mother ask for whisky, yet Korina 'humbly' proposes: 'I read that on such occasions they used to offer soumada (an orgeat syrup drink)'. Even though, with this line, Korina endeavours to pass as a supporter of tradition, at least for her mother's-in-law eyes, she indirectly suggests that decent women, as she pretends to be, do not consume heavy alcoholic drinks, whilst at the same time,

implies that her organism is so 'pure' that cannot handle alcohol. 'Korina is really into traditions' commends Pavlos as an attempt to make his mother appreciate Korina's 'properness'. 'Yes, she is indeed! Today, we had hard time convincing her to take off her traditional costume and wear something else!' agrees Flora, ironically, as she is completely aware of Korina's fake persona. Yet, along with the rest of the family, she is willing not reveal to Pavlos and his mother Korina's true profession and personality.

Soon, the rest of the family walk into the living room, all dressed up for the occasion. They start giving their blessings to the couple and making toasts with their drinks. One of them is Aristidis (Athinodoros Prousalis), Korina's father, an old man in a wheelchair, who years ago suffered a stroke which left him mentally disturbed. When his daughter-in-law, Flora, asks him what he would like to drink, he answers: 'Bring me, you moron, some tsipouro (Greek alcoholic drink), so I can give my blessings!' When she brings him a shot of tsipouro, he shouts: 'Bring me, you lame, the whole bottle. Why are you so frugal with it?' The rest of the people, listening embarrassed, try to stir the conversation to different topics, but once Aristidis has had few shots of tsipouro, turns to Pavlos' mother and Pavlos, and says: 'Listen co-mother-in-law! We consider Korina as our own child (even though she is). [...] I was planning to mate her, for a long time now. [...] I won't hide it from you, groom, that others are asking me for her too. [...] She's from a good breed. [...] And as you can see, I keep her in a very good condition. [...] Her skin, her fur. Touch to check, she doesn't shed. [...] I got her tail chopped off, too.' His assistant, Machi (Soula Athanasiadou), interrupts saying: 'Now I understand. He thinks he's selling an ewe.' His son, Achilleas, tensed and ashamed, asks Machi to roll Aristidis back to his bedroom. While he is rolled out of the living room, however, he yells to Pavlos: 'It doesn't benefit me to sell her. She gives me seven kilos of milk a day, plus the wool!' Korina, then, bursts into tears and runs out of the room too, while Pavlos' mother, stunned, asks Pavlos: 'Won't you tell me what's going on in here?' and he answers: 'I told you, mum, it's just a typical Greek family.'

As mentioned earlier, these two examples depict the 'traditional' and the 'modern' ways of thinking and behaving 'performed' by one and the same character, unlike the previous cases analysed. What is also notable, however, is the fact that Korina, as an 'unconventional' character within the Greek society attempts to 'exploit' behavioural characteristics that derive from a normative way of life to her advantage. In the series examined earlier in the section, the 'unconventional' characters (like Teti, Dorita and Smaragda) choose to clash with the societal norms in order to achieve what they desire. Here, Korina chooses to abide societal norms to get what she wants. Yet, her adapting to a 'traditional' lifestyle is fake, indicating an 'exploitative' utilization of the 'old' by the 'new' for the personal gain of the character (in this

case Korina) who in reality embodies the ‘modern’ and ‘unconventional’. This adds a new and complex layer to the portrayal of the ‘traditional/modern’ relationship, which this study investigates.

The second ‘alternative’ approach to the portrayal of the relationship between the ‘old’ and the ‘new’ is met in the series *Constantine’s and Helen’s* (*Konstantinou kai Elenis*)/*Κωνσταντίνου και Ελένης* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000). This series is not directly linked to the topic of ‘family’, as the two protagonists, Helen (Eleni Rantou) and Constantine (Charis Romas), get into a romantic relationship with each other only towards the final episodes, and do not get married until the very last one. However, since episode 1, they share the same household as they move in together to a big neoclassical house which they both seemingly inherited. Their ‘agreement’ is to co-habit until the court finally decides who of the two is the actual heir of house - a decision which takes two years to be made. Nevertheless, the co-existence of these characters under the same roof is full of rivalry and quarrels due to their contrasting personalities. As a matter of fact, it is their contrasting personalities that constitutes the canvas upon which the dichotomy between the ‘old’ and ‘traditional’ with the ‘new’ and ‘unconventional’ is drawn. In particular, the personality of Constantine accumulates what represents the ‘old’ and ‘traditional’, while the personality of Helen exemplifies the ‘new’ and ‘unconventional’.

In detail, Constantine is an academic working as an assistant lecturer at a university teaching Byzantinology. He is religious, conservative and comes from a wealthy family. He is old-fashioned, austere, disciplined and hard-working. He does not have much experience with women, does not understand slang and has the tendency to criticize, especially those who do not adhere to a ‘traditional’ way of life. He is usually grumpy, indifferent to other people’s problems and does not have many friends. On the other hand, Helen is rather uneducated, comes from a deprived family and works as a waitress at a bar. She is empathetic to other people’s problems, but she is also known to be impolite, quite direct and sometimes manipulative. She follows fashion and trends, and often uses slang. She is cunning, fearless, and a chaser. She is a good friend, but when it comes to her love life her various relationships with men are short-lived. Contrary to Constantine, she is terrible at housekeeping, always out of money, chaotic and undisciplined.

The cohabitation of two characters with such opposite and incompatible personalities leads, of course, to the infliction of conflicts, which help construct the plots of the episodes and provide the comedic effect of the series. However, the scriptwriters, Charis Romas and Anna Chatzisofoia, incorporated one additional element into the shaping of these dissimilar characters,

which we never meet in any of the other series examined in the study. This ‘unique’ element can be summarized in what the actress who plays Helen, Eleni Rantou, expressed in an official behind-the-scenes episode (episode 69). In particular, she said: ‘These two characters weren’t just the complete opposites - that would have been quite common. What wasn’t common was that the male part was played by a woman and the female part by a man. And all of a sudden, I found myself playing a character that swears, behaves like a ‘truck driver’, is the chaser when it comes to her love life, does whatever else except what women do, what’s feminine. And the male parts had all those feminine elements of shyness and bashfulness. I had so much fun with this!’ Through Rantou’s comment, therefore, we see that the shaping of the personalities of Constantine and Helen is not just based on the opposite traits of the ‘traditional’ and the ‘unconventional’, but on bestowing elements that are stereotypically considered ‘masculine’ on the personality of Helen, and ‘feminine’ on the personality of Constantine. In few words, the series portrays an ‘inversion’ of the ‘traditional’ gender-related attributes and behaviours. This ‘inversion’ is exemplified in the following examples, taken from episodes 63, 37 and 58.

In detail, in episode 63 Constantine draws the conclusion that swearing and fighting with Helen is pointless and announces that he is not going to swear at her again. Helen, ‘disappointed’, makes a series of attempts to insult him in order to make him reconsider. The way she finally manages to aggravate him is by grabbing his behind and then running away. Utterly irritated, Constantine runs after her yelling: ‘Repulsive being, your time has come! I’m going to smash you!’ Unfortunately for him, the moment he speaks these words Helen’s lawyer, Elli (Eleni Philippa), and Constantine’s lawyer, Nikos (Ilias Zervos), enter the house and are shocked at the way he shouted at her. Helen, as expected, takes advantage of the situation, and says to the lawyers: ‘You see! Now I’ve got witnesses! He swears at me and threatens me!’ Constantine, desperate, defends himself by telling them that she grabbed his behind a moment ago. However, Elli does not believe him and ironically asks: ‘Did she also rape you?’ to which Constantine answers: ‘She’d really like to, but I wouldn’t give in!’ This gives Helen the opportunity to lash out one more time saying: ‘There you have it! You don’t need any other proof! The guy is an idiot!’ A similar situation takes place in episode 37, when Helen accidentally consumes a drug (hidden in chocolate truffles) which flares up her libido so much that she loses any control of her actions. Thus, she makes a pass at every male character of the episode, but in a scene with Constantine her behaviour escalates to the extent of committing sexual harassment against him. She tries to force him to put on various kinds of underwear, dirty talks, spansks him and immobilizes him by covering his eyes with an underwear pushing his head against the wall, while he yells: ‘I don’t want to put on this goddamn bikini!’

In episode 58, Helen, assisted by a hairdresser friend, turns the house into an illegal hair and nails salon. When Constantine finds out, an intense fight takes place, which comes to an end when he very aggressively threatens to kill her. Helen, to make things go her way, pretends to have been convinced to get rid of the salon, scared off by his ‘manliness’. She even runs to the kitchen to squeeze some orange juice for him. Constantine, proud of his ‘manliness’ and its effectiveness on Helen, says to her while she offers him the orange juice: ‘From now on, this is how I want you to behave to the man, woman. Humbly and with respect!’ to which Helen responds: ‘Yes, man!’ bending her head downwards as a sign of submission. Of course, he is completely unaware that her submissive behaviour is fake. Her goal is to lure him into a false sense of security and put him to sleep by having dissolved some sleeping drug into the orange juice. Once, he falls asleep, she alters his hairdo by adding long box braids as extensions to his hair, turning him into a ‘Cleopatra’, as he later calls himself, once he wakes up and sees what she’s done to him.

As we observe in these examples, there is a constant attempt by Helen to ‘emasculate’ Constantine, while at the same time ‘present’ herself as the ‘conqueror’. Another way this ‘emasculatation’ takes place in the series, is through Helen’s ‘habit’ to sometimes use female pronouns when she refers to Constantine. She developed this ‘habit’ due to the fact that his last name, Katakouzinou, sounds similar to the word ‘kouzina/κουζίνα’, which is a noun meaning ‘kitchen’, and has feminine grammatical gender in the Greek language. Therefore, the subject-matter and the humour - in other words, the comedy-making - of this series is built upon striking ‘inversions’ of ‘traditional/stereotypical’, and often sexist, gender-related ‘expectations’, demonstrated through the above examples. This ‘inversion’ in gender representation is highlighted even more, if we consider the stereotypical gender-related archetypes that the secondary main characters of the series represent. In particular, there are four secondary characters that surround the everyday lives of the two protagonists. Two of these characters are female, Matina (Kalliroi Miriagou) and Peggy (Maria Lekaki), and two are male, Manthos (Vasilis Koukouras) and Nikolas (Stergios Nenes). In all four cases, conventional, but often problematic representations of gender take place through these characters.

In detail, Matina, Helen and Constantine’s spinster neighbour, is a conservative, modest, low-profile, shy, inexperienced with men young woman. She is obsessed with finding a husband, is an excellent cook and housekeeper, has a dull job in the public sector and takes care of her demented old father. She is kind, caring, forgiving, insecure, and even though educated and well-read, she is often naïve and easy to manipulate - especially by Helen with whom they are good friends despite their contrasting personalities. ‘The woman must obey the

man.’ she says to Helen in episode 2, when the latter is in an argument with Constantine. As expected, Helen responds by saying sarcastically: ‘You should have been put leader of the feministic movement!’ Peggy, another friend of Helen, is an unsuccessful actress, who works as a waitress at a bar along with Helen. She portrays the type of a woman who is after the rich handsome man upon whom she can rely. For example, in episode 2 she says to Helen: ‘Wait till my relationship with Manthos tightens. Then I can ask him for money.’ Nevertheless, even though she is not naïve, she repeatedly falls victim of her boyfriend’s lies, who constantly cheats on her. She is kind and considerate though she often behaves as an obnoxious diva actress to her friends. Manthos, Peggy’s boyfriend and Constantine’s only friend, is the stereotypical yuppie handsome man, son of a wealthy manufacturer, spoiled and a sex maniac. ‘We are large and big spender men, here to help beautiful girls!’ he says in episode 2 when Helen, with whom he never has an affair with throughout the series due to her strong refusal, is in need of money. Despite being in a ‘serious’ relationship with Peggy, he has many secret parallel relationships. He drives a Porsche, lives in a modern bachelor’s apartment and has an exceptional talent in making each of his girlfriends believe that they are the one and only. Finally, Nikolas is the bartender at the bar where Helen and Peggy work. He is quite a one-dimensional character, mostly focusing on being the ladies’ man, preparing drinks behind the bar, driving a Harley Davidson motorcycle, and being always out of money.

Up to this point, in the examples analysed above taken from the series *Crimes (Eglimata)* and *Constantine’s and Helen’s (Konstantinou kai Elenis)*, we investigated two of the three ‘alternative’ scriptwriting approaches regarding the portrayal of the relationship between the ‘old’ and the ‘new’, which, unlike the rest of the series examined in this subchapter, were not conveyed to the audience through expressed opinions by ideologically competing groups of characters. In the first ‘alternative’ approach, occurring in *Crimes (Eglimata)*, the ‘old’ and the ‘new’ were both essentialised through one single character, Korina. In the second ‘alternative’ approach, met in *Constantine’s and Helen’s (Konstantinou kai Elenis)*, the ‘old’ and ‘new’ dichotomy constituted the main premise of the series actualised by having one of the two protagonists, Constantine, represent the ‘old’ and the other protagonist, Helen, represent the ‘new’. In both series, there were additional layers of complexity in regard to the portrayal of the ‘old/new’ relationship and dynamics. In *Crimes (Eglimata)*, the complexity derived from the ‘exploitative’ utilization of the ‘old’ by the ‘new’ for the personal gain of the character that embodies the ‘modern’ and ‘unconventional’, who, in this case, was Korina. In *Constantine’s and Helen’s (Konstantinou kai Elenis)*, the complexity derived from the portrayal of an ‘inversion’ of the ‘traditional’ gender-related attributes and behaviours, by bestowing elements

stereotypically considered ‘masculine’ on the personality of Helen, and ‘feminine’ on the personality of Constantine.

The third, and perhaps the most creative, ‘alternative’ approach to the portrayal of the ‘old/new’ dichotomy takes place in the series *Sinning Twice (To Dis Eksamartein)*. As mentioned earlier, the story of this series comes to a happy end (in episode 71), with the formation of an ‘unconventional’ family that consists of one mother, Anna (Nena Menti), two fathers, Giannis (Charis Sozos) and Petros (Alexandros Antonopoulos), and a baby daughter named Yolanda. However, the scriptwriters, Michalis Reppas and Thanasis Papathanasiou, took an extra step in their attempt to exemplify and satirize even more the battle between new and old ideologies, met in the 1990s Greece, on the topics of ‘family’, ‘marriage’, and ‘gender’. They achieved that by adding an extra episode (episode 72), which, even though it does not add anything to the narrative, works as an imaginative ‘commentary’ on the morals presented by the series throughout its three-season run.

In detail, the episode features a guest character, Tonia Saplaoura Bithikotsi (Anna Panagiotopoulou), who, by addressing to the camera, introduces herself stating that she is a psychologist-sociologist. She informs the audience that she is about to present an ‘analysis’ on the series, regarding its representation of morals as they derived from the characters’ words and actions throughout the episodes. One of her first comments is about the resolution of the narrative of the series: ‘Is this a proper ending for a series: the three of them living together? This is why God will throw fire on us and burn us!’ Tonia then moves on commending on events that happened in the beginning of the series, during which Anna started her secret love affair with Petros, while her husband, Giannis, was in hospital after a car accident. What led Anna to give in to Petros’ flirt, however, was the fact that when Giannis’ accident took place, he was found with another woman in the car. Of course, Tonia condemns Anna’s decision to cheat on her husband, despite the fact that he had cheated on her, not only once, but multiple times during their seven-year marriage. In particular, she says: ‘The man is a man! [...] It’s in his nature (to cheat), but, at the end of the day, he (always) returns to his wife. You (Anna), if you wanted to be righteous, you should have shown patience (instead of perpetuating an affair with Petros)!’

Tonia would then commend on various scenes from throughout the series, which portrayed key points of the story, and especially moments of emotional agony, remorse, uncertainty and passion. Some of these scenes are refilmed, so Tonia can be in them as an invisible witness, who makes remarks on the characters’ morals as presented through their words and actions. All her remarks about Anna’s morality are negative, as is the case with the

morality of the rest of the female characters, such as Anna's mother Yolanda (Ntina Konsta), or her colleagues, Fouli (Iro Mane) and Valentini (Eleni Kastani). Tonia continues her 'analysis' by proposing how these women should have acted instead. In order for this to happen, some more scenes get to be refilmed. In their original versions, these scenes portrayed the female characters behave in an 'overly' emancipated manner (according to Tonia) that did not adhere to the 'traditional', or else, 'moral' models of gender-related behaviour - which, for her, require a wife to be submissive and serve her husband with self-denial and tolerance (for example, to domestic violence). In the new versions of the scenes, Tonia 'disguised' as Anna, Yolanda, Fouli or Valentini 'plays' their parts 'showcasing' how these women should have acted like, if they wanted to be 'morally correct'. In detail, when 'performing' Anna's parts, Tonia breaks up with Petros and dedicates herself to taking care of her husband by being an excellent 'homemaker', submitting to any of his criticisms and trying even harder to please him. When Tonia 'plays' Yolanda, she portrays a conservative middle-aged woman, authoritative and dismissive towards her daughter - the exact opposite of what the 'real' Yolanda was, who, despite constantly feeling stressed and worried because of her daughter's affair with Petros, she never revealed the secret. On the contrary, Tonia (as Yolanda) exposes Anna to Giannis without a second thought in order to 'punish' her for her immorality. Lastly, through Fouli and Valentini's parts, she claims that when a wife cheats on her husband, he has every right to be physically violent to her.

She, then, condemns the creators and the television channel for having produced this 'unacceptable' series, and wonders how come the actors accepted to play such roles. She finishes her 'analysis' by providing various alternative endings that would have made the story 'morally correct'. All of the endings she proposes involve the death of Anna in order to achieve her catharsis for having cheated on her husband and given birth to a baby, whose father might be either Giannis or Petros. According to Tonia, some of the ways Anna could die are by hanging herself, being hit by a train, cutting off her veins with a nail clipper or poisoning herself. Through her death, she could work as a warning for the people watching at home, not to be as 'immoral' as she was, if they do not wish to have the same terrible fate. Nevertheless, she proposes an additional alternative ending, which is actually happy. She suggests that Anna, instead of dying, remarries Giannis, Petros marries Fouli, and Valentini marries one of their colleagues, Evgenios (Michalis Reppas). This way, the series would have ended with a big 'traditional' wedding. Such choice would have promoted a 'morally correct' resolution, giving the 'right' example to the audience - unlike the official resolution of the story, according to which, the series ends with the creation of a family that consists of two fathers, a mother and a

baby daughter. She concludes her 'analysis' stating that marriage is the life purpose of every person, and by ending the story with a happy 'traditional' wedding, the series would have 'taught' people that: 'we should never deviate from 'the family'!'

As a matter of fact, this phrase can summarize the ideological core around which the whole discussion of this subchapter revolved. After all, all the Greek comedy series of the 1990s analysed above, in relation to their representations of 'the family', had the 'traditional', or else, the 'nuclear/conjugal family' as their ideological foundation. The limited cases of 'nuclear/conjugal families' in the series did not obscure the potency that traditional ideology on the topic of 'family' held throughout the everyday interactions of the characters that we met. In fact, traditional ideology constituted the cornerstone upon which the narrative of all the family-related stories of the section was built. Succinctly, what triggered the creation of stories was (1) the 'employment' of characters that tended to deviate from the traditional family ideology. Through their 'deviations', (2) they caused conflicts with the rest of the characters. The attempts to (3) resolve those conflicts was what constituted the main body of each story. The final resolutions of the conflicts usually promoted the everlasting endurance of the traditional family ideology, as was the case for characters that flirted with the 'radical' ideas of single parenthood by choice and out-of-marriage children in series such as *The Three Charites (Oi Treis Charites)*, *Just Us (Emeis ki Emeis)*, and *Dolce Vita*. However, in two occasions, the 'deviation' from the traditional family ideology managed to prevail with the creation of 'unconventional' family units portrayed in the series *Sinning Twice (To Dis Eksamartein)* and *With Two Mothers (Me Dyo Mamades)*. Consequently, in term of Vamvakas' (2019, p. 35) suggestion stated at the beginning of the subchapter - according to which he asserts that there is a lot of work to be done in order to confirm the existence of a connection between 'tradition' and the topic of 'family' when it comes to Greek comedy series - this study has demonstrated that such connection is not only existent but constitutes a core component within Greek comedy-making.

CHAPTER 5:

CONCLUSION

5.1 Addressing the Research Aim

The aim of this doctoral thesis was to contribute to covering part of the gap of academic discourse on the subject of Greek Television by investigating and analysing the creative formations and ideological physiognomies of the Greek comedy series of the 1990s as influenced by the sociocultural principles of their zeitgeist. This section summarizes the key findings, gathered from the three subchapters of the Analysis, dedicated to 1) national identity, 2) political ideology and 3) representations of ‘the family’. In detail, the following paragraphs recap the complex framework of ‘ideologies’ (ideological physiognomies) circulating in Greece during the 1990s, portrayed in the examined comedy series throughout the Analysis chapter. As demonstrated below, these ‘ideologies’ encompass and, at the same time, (re)present the ways of thinking, in the 1990s Greece, on issues like racism, xenophobia, globalization, sense of self, self-deprecation, sense of belonging, arts, tradition, modernization, family paradigms, gender roles and politics. By attempting to ‘understand’ the characters’ ‘ideologies’ on these matters, we attempt to ‘understand’ modern Greece and its sociocultural complexities - and a cultural product, like television fiction, constitutes a great vehicle for such an attempt.

Starting with the summary of the first subchapter of the Analysis, whose aim was to investigate the Greek national identity as represented through the comedies examined, one of the first things we find out is that the comedies referenced the subject of national identity, directly or indirectly, mostly in relation to the various dangers that, according to the views of characters, threaten it. For instance, an issue that could threaten the Greek national identity (according to the opinion of some characters) were the new possibilities that arouse due to globalization, which come hand in hand with new uncertainties and anxieties, as portrayed in episode 8 of *The Penthouse (To Retire)/To Πετιπέ* (MEGA, 1990-1992). In detail, in that episode, characters commented upon the ‘new possibilities’ that emerged within the Greek society of the 1990s due to the transnationalization of economic and cultural life as a result of globalization. However, at the same time they were concerned about potential ‘cultural convergence’, as distinct characteristics of their Greek identity, such as the language, culture

and lifestyles would gradually disappear as globalization spreads and strengthens. That would eventually lead to their national identity be in crisis, and them losing touch with their culture, history and sense of self. Another reason that was deemed to lead to national identity crisis was presented in episode 27 of *The Unacceptables (Oi Aparadektoi)/Οι Απαράδεκτοι* (MEGA, 1991-1993). That time identity crisis came as a result of a geopolitical conflict (the Macedonian name dispute) with a neighbouring country, inflicted during the period this series was produced. In order for the characters to ‘fix’ their crisis in their national identity they would try to reconnect with history and roots, and construct a ‘historicized’ version of their national identity, as Aitaki (2015) puts it.

The study then focused on analysing scenes from the series selected that portrayed moments in which characters, directly or indirectly, referred to their national identity in relation to other national identities, or else, in relation to the ‘other’. The first scene examined came from episode 14 of the black-comedy series *Crimes (Eglimata)/Εγκλήματα* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000) and it presented Greek characters who celebrated their national identity by bestowing pride and value upon it, which came into being by comparing their ancient history to an African country and its people. In that example, the differentiation from ‘the other’ led to the creation of a shared sense of superiority, as far as Greek national identity is concerned. That sense of superiority would then be what is satirized by the creators in order to create comedy (comedic effect). As is the case with many of the examples analysed in that section, Greek superiority, on the one hand, and negative assessments, stereotypes and racist overgeneralizations against foreigners, on the other, were features constantly met in Greek comedy series of the 1990s. The countries or individuals who received racism from the Greek characters in the series came from places such as eastern Europe, the Balkans, Asia, Africa and the Arabic world. Yet, there were a couple of instances (in episode 4 of *The Three Charites* and episode 7 of *With Two Mothers*) that Greek characters indirectly showed admiration towards western places, financially and politically stronger than Greece. That might indicate an underlying sense of inferiority when it comes to Greece’s endeavours to establish itself, culturally and financially, within the western world. That sense of inferiority was then analysed by examining scenes in which Greek characters stereotyped themselves (and not the foreigners). Some of the stereotypes they came up with to ‘describe’ themselves included characterizations, such as know-it-alls, overly patriotic, crooks, complainers, unable to respect personal space, overly accommodating and temperamental.

The next part of the first subchapter explored moments in which characters discussed culture or ‘performed’ cultural practices within their everyday experiences. In the examples

analysed we observe that the 1990s Greeks were in a juxtaposition between different sources of cultural influences, for example in music, which originated from the West and from the East. The biggest part of that section, however, focused on discourse around the competing forces of ‘high’ culture and ‘popular’ culture, and their effects upon the members of the Greek society. Nevertheless, ‘folk culture’, and its relationship with ‘popular’ and ‘high culture’, was also showcased in the scenes examined, adding yet another layer of complexity when it comes to the representation of contemporary Greek culture in the 1990s comedy series. In general, ‘high’, ‘popular’ and ‘folk culture’ were presented as opposing forces that characterize the contemporary Greek society highlighting its non-homogeneity in the field of music and other art forms. Yet, ‘folk culture’ seemed to constitute probably the most authentic reflection of Greek culture deeply ingrained in the hearts of the characters, as seen in episode of 57 *Two Strangers (Dyo Xenoi)/Δύο Ξένοι* (MEGA, 1997-1999).

The subchapter on national identity came to an end with a case study on the series *Just Us (Emeis ki emeis)/Εμείς κι Εμείς* (MEGA, 1994-1998), which offers a plethora of moments that reference what Gibernau (2007) describes as ‘loyalty’ and ‘willingness to make sacrifices and die’ for one’s country, ‘sentiments of love’ for one’s country, ‘hatred’ for those that may threaten it, and a sense of ‘closeness’ with the fellow nationals. Especially when it came to the sense of ‘belonging’ and the sense of ‘closeness’, the series, by having gathered characters from various parts of Greece, who were enjoying their living together despite their differences, seems to have managed, at least in a symbolic way, to convert Anderson’s (1991) ‘imagined’ community into reality.

The second subchapter of the Analysis investigated whether or not the Greek comedy series examined in this study comply with the notion that prime-time television is intentionally kept apolitical in order to achieve high viewing rates, and, within the context of competition, attract the most profit from advertising (Koukoutsaki-Monnier, 2010). By examining episodes in which characters expressed their political opinions, the study gained an insight to the concerns that Greeks had about the political status quo of the 1990s, as well as the range of political ideologies that circulated and formed the everyday experience and way of thinking of the time. The outcome of the investigation suggested that the 1990s Greek prime-time comedy series were indeed political on their own merit, overturning the paradigm regarding the established advertising strategies of the apolitical commercial television. The series analysed may not have provided with discourse related to alternatives for change or distanced themselves from a reality in which capitalism had prevailed. But instead, they portrayed the acknowledgement of its prevalence, and the implications that that had upon the romanticized

alternative ideologies of the past. Therefore, in that subchapter the study claims that the Greek prime-time comedy series of the 1990s were not apolitical, as they did not silence the political ideologies that influenced Greece during the late 20th century.

Some of these political ideologies were a range of political practices prominent in the everyday life of the Greeks of the era, which were not silenced by the series either. Throughout many scenes analysed, the political practises of *rousfeti*, *meson* and *fakelaki* were presented as cultural norms, ingrained in collective behaviour, since the characters would not hesitate to utilize them to benefit or get themselves out of unpleasant situations related to their affairs with the state. The Greek comedy series of the 1990s, therefore, constitute a paradigm of how prime-time television can be political and at the same time ensure its commercial and entertainment objectives.

The third and final subchapter of the Analysis was dedicated to examining comedy series in relation to their portrayal of ‘the family’, as represented through the characters’ views and behaviours. Urged by Vamvakas’ (2019) claim, that part of the analysis investigated the link between ‘tradition’ and ‘family’ when it comes to Greek comedy-making and examined its creative utilization by the creators in their endeavour to entertain. In alignment with the American trends of the era, the Greek series of the 1990s tended to revolve around the topics of friendship and cohabitation with friends or relatives, rather than to focus on portrayals of ‘the family’, especially the nuclear family. Nevertheless, the series could still provide sufficient data to examine representations on the topic of ‘family’. That was made possible through a number of ‘radical’ characters who would tease new ideas that opposed the traditional paradigm of the ‘conjugal family’. For example, they would express their wish to become single parents by choice or have a child out-of-marriage. That would cause conflicts within their community of characters, offering us the opportunity to observe the ways of thinking met within the Greek society of the era in regard to the topic of ‘the family’. In most cases, characters would object to ‘radical’ ideas that did not adhere to the traditional family values, and eventually, any attempts to overturn the established ideology of the topic of ‘family’ would not achieve on-screen representation. However, throughout the series examined, there were two cases which portrayed alternative formations of family units. One of those cases was *Sinning Twice (To Dis Eksamartein)/To Δις Εξαμαρτείν* (MEGA, 1993-1996), which concluded its three-year run with the creation of a family that consisted of a mother, two fathers and a baby daughter. The other case was *With Two Mothers (Me Dyo Mamades)/Με Δύο Μαμάδες* (MEGA, 1998-1999), a series which since episode 1 portrayed a family that consisted of two mothers and an adult daughter.

In general, the series examined would utilize the battle between the ‘old’ and the ‘new’, or else, the battle between the ‘traditional’ and the ‘modern’ to create conflicts and upon those conflicts build the plots of their episodes. On the one hand, the ‘old’ would be represented by an ‘conventional’ group of characters that endeavoured to sustain the traditional beliefs and practises on issues such as ‘the family’, and on the other, the ‘new’ would be represented by another group of characters, the ‘unconventional’ ones, that attempted to overturn the norms by expressing new ideas, for example on how a family could come to be (e.g., through single parenthood or out-of-marriage children). Nevertheless, there were three cases in the series examined, in which, the dichotomy between the ‘old’ and ‘new’ was not portrayed through two competing groups but through three ‘alternative’ scriptwriting approaches.

The first ‘alternative’ approach took place in *Crimes (Eglimata)/Εγκλήματα* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000). According to that first alternative approach the ‘old’ and the ‘new’ were both essentialised through one single character, Korina (Maria Kavoyianni). The second ‘alternative’ approach was met in *Constantine’s and Helen’s (Konstantinou kai Elenis)/Κωνσταντίνου και Ελένης* (ANTENNA, 1998-2000). In that case, the ‘old’ and ‘new’ dichotomy constituted the main premise of the series actualised by having one of the two protagonists, Constantine (Charis Romas), represent the ‘old’ and the other protagonist, Helen (Eleni Rantou), represent the ‘new’. In both series, there were additional layers of complexity in regard to the portrayal of the ‘old/new’ relationship and dynamics. In *Crimes (Eglimata)*, the complexity derived from the ‘exploitative’ utilization of the ‘old’ by the ‘new’ for the personal gain of the character that embodies the ‘modern’ and ‘unconventional’, who, in that case, was Korina. In *Constantine’s and Helen’s (Konstantinou kai Elenis)*, the complexity derived from the portrayal of an ‘inversion’ of the ‘traditional’ gender-related attributes and behaviours, by bestowing elements stereotypically considered ‘masculine’ on the personality of Helen, and ‘feminine’ on the personality of Constantine.

The third ‘alternative’ approach to the portrayal of the ‘old/new’ dichotomy took place in the series *Sinning Twice (To Dis Eksamartein)*. According to that approach, the series as a whole represented the ‘new’, with the creation of an atypical family that consisted of a mother, two fathers and a baby daughter. The ‘old’ was represented through the addition of a guest character in the very last episode of the series. In that episode, the guest character Tonia introduces herself to the audience stating that she is a psychologist-sociologist and informs it that she would present an ‘analysis’ on the series, regarding its representation of morals as they derived from the characters’ words and actions throughout the episodes. So, she would ‘revisit’

scenes as an invisible witness and negatively comments on any words, actions and behaviours by the characters of the series, which did not adhere to a ‘traditional’ way of life.

Overall, what that last subchapter of the Analysis attempted to do was to confirm the existence of a connection between ‘tradition’ and the topic of ‘family’ when it comes to Greek comedy series, as Vamvakas (2019) suggested. Thus, through extensive analysis on the topic of ‘family’ from examples taken from the comedy series selected for this study, it has been demonstrated that such connection is not only existent but constitutes a core component within Greek comedy-making.

5.2 Original contribution to knowledge

As observed in the Introduction and Literature Review chapters, this thesis claims to constitute a response to various calls from scholars for the conducting of investigations on areas of Greek television where they suggest there are still gaps in knowledge. For example, section 1.1 of the Introduction chapter lists a series of topics pointed out by the ‘50 years of Greek television’ conference which require more examination, such as on Greek television series that portray family relationships, gender roles, sexual identities, social bonds and values, cultural practices, collective and local identities (Vamvakas and Paschalidis, 2018). In section 2.1 of the Literature Review chapter, Aitaki (2020) calls for further investigations related to potential infiltration of political ideologies into Greek television fiction. In section 2.2 of the same chapter, Vamvakas (2019) asks for the conducting of studies examining the link between tradition and modernization featured in Greek series that portray family units.

As summarized in the previous section of this Conclusion chapter, this thesis has investigated and presented an extensive number of ‘moments’ within its sample of comedy series, which portray national identity, social bonds, cultural practices, and gender representations. Regarding Aitaki’s call, in particular, asking for further investigations on potential political influences upon Greek television fiction, the thesis, through a thorough analysis, gives a clear answer, stating that there are indeed representations of political ideologies in the Greek comedy series examined - despite various insistent claims about the apoliticality of the commercial Greek television fiction. The same process was undertaken in order to answer to Vamvakas’ call. Through the dedication of a whole subchapter on the matter, the thesis not only confirmed the link between tradition and modernization in family representations but recognised the significance of this link throughout Greek comedy-making and discovered various ‘alternative’ approaches regarding its utilization, summarized in the previous section.

On a broader scope, this thesis makes a significant contribution to the field of Greek television studies, particularly by shifting the focus away from the more traditional political-economic approaches to exploring the cultural and ideological aspects of Greek comedy series. While previous academic discourse has predominantly examined the relationship between Greek television and the state, this research instead delves into how television content reflects and shapes the social and cultural fabric of Greece. By analysing the creative processes behind the comedy series of the 1990s, the study highlights the vital role these programs played in the construction of Greek national identity, while also providing insight into the transformation of family structures, gender, and social norms during a period of considerable change.

Moreover, by focusing on Greek comedy, a genre often seen as trivial or purely entertainment-driven, this study brings attention to the ways in which seemingly light-hearted content can address deeper societal issues. It challenges the conventional wisdom of Greek television's role in reinforcing state ideologies and suggests a more nuanced view of how media can serve as both a mirror and a tool for negotiating national values.

Beyond Greek television studies, the implications of this research extend to broader fields of media and cultural studies. By examining Greek comedy series through the lens of national identity, family, gender, and political ideology, the study contributes to our understanding of how television, as a cultural product, can simultaneously reflect societal norms and challenge prevailing ideologies. This work aligns with global trends in media studies, where the focus has expanded from the political economy of media to the exploration of identity, representation, and cultural impact in television.

Furthermore, this study provides valuable insights for comparative media studies, especially in understanding how comedy can function as a space for negotiating and contesting national identity. The ways in which Greek comedy series satirise both national and foreign identities offer a unique perspective on the role of humour in reflecting and shaping societal values. The examination of gender and family portrayals adds another layer to the study of how television can either reinforce or subvert traditional gender norms and familial structures in the context of a rapidly changing society.

In terms of methodology (research design), the thesis' approach - combining textual analysis with sociocultural theory - offers a comprehensive way to understand the relationship between media texts and their cultural context. This approach can serve as a model for future research on media representations in other cultural contexts, particularly in countries where television has played a significant role in the formation of national identity.

5.3 Potential areas for future research

As stated in the Research Design chapter, this study on Greek comedy series was undertaken through textual analysis, without the incorporation of interviews with professionals, or focus groups of fans offering their personal experiences and opinions on the material. Therefore, a similarly themed study which does include interviews and/or focus groups would strengthen the arguments presented in this textual analysis focused project, as it would incorporate information related to moments of production (through the interviews with professionals) and moments of reception (through the focus groups).

Of course, there are many other ways this study could continue. For example, the most obvious path would be to examine Greek comedy series produced after the 1990s, investigating how they have been transforming over the decades, alongside the transformation of the Greek society. Comparing Greek television fiction with the television fiction of another country, European or not, would also be an interesting idea, as such an investigation would demonstrate the distinct characteristics of Greek series-making, as well as its similarities to other national television fiction.

5.4 Strengths and limitations: a reflection

Reflecting on the final version of the thesis, I believe that its limitation is the fact that it did not include interviews with professionals and focus groups, losing, therefore, the greater impact the overall arguments would have had if the thesis had examined the dynamics between the production and the reception of the cultural product it investigated. Namely, due to that omission, the thesis was not able to demonstrate the influence of ‘professional ideologies’ passed upon the ways the ‘text’ was represented and excluded the potential diversity of social accounts on what the ‘text’ actually means to different parts of the audience (Philo, 2007).

Nevertheless, the biggest strength of this thesis, apart from its contribution to knowledge and its partaking in the ‘vibrant’, developing academic field of Greek television, is the fact that, to my knowledge, it is the only study conducted by one individual to date, which has presented and analysed ‘in one place’ such a large number of scenes taken from Greek comedy series episodes. This makes me particularly happy as I had the chance to offer to non-Greek speakers as many glimpses as possible of this unique, unknown to the rest of the world television realm.

REFERENCES

- Aitaki, G. (2015) 'The Historicized 'Self' and the Hungry 'Other': Geopolitical Imaginations in Greek Television Comedy *Oi Aparadektoi/The Unacceptables*', *Filmicon: Journal of Greek Film Studies*, 3(1), pp. 32-48.
- Aitaki, G. (2017) 'Laughing with/at the national self: Greek television satire and the politics of self-disparagement', *Social Semiotics*, 29(1), pp. 68-82.
- Aitaki, G. (2018a) 'The academic study of Greek television: Mapping a scattered field', *Critical Studies in Television: The International Journal of Television Studies*, 13(2), pp. 244-253.
- Aitaki, G. (2018b) *The private life of a nation in crisis: A study on the politics in/of Greek television fiction*. PhD thesis. University of Gothenburg.
- Aitaki, G. (2018c) 'Domesticating pathogenies, evaluating change: The Eurozone crisis as a 'Hot Moment' in Greek television fiction', *Media, Culture & Society*, 40(7), pp. 957-972.
- Aitaki, G. (2020) 'Making television fiction in a commercial context: Commercialization, ideology and entertainment in a production study of Greek private television', *Journal of Greek Media & Culture*, 6(2), pp. 219-240.
- Aitaki, G. and Chairetis, S. (2019) 'Introduction to Greek Television Studies: (Re)Reading Greek Television Fiction since 1989', *Filmicon: Journal of Greek Film Studies*, 6, pp. 1-16.
- Aitaki, G. Papadimitriou, L. and Tzioumakis, Y. (2020) 'Greek Screen Industries: From Political Economy to Media Industry Studies', *Journal of Greek Media and Culture*, 6(2), pp. 155-178.
- Aitaki, G., Papadimitriou, L. and Tzioumakis, Y. (2021) 'Locating and localizing Media Industry Studies: The case of Greece' In McDonald, P. (ed) *The Routledge Companion to Media Industries*. New York: Routledge.
- Anderson, B. (1991) *Imagined communities: Reflections on the origin and spread of nationalism*. 2nd ed. London: Verso.
- Arnold, M. (1993) *Culture and Anarchy*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Barker, C. (2012) *Cultural Studies*. 4th edn. London: Sage.
- Barth, F. (1969) *Ethnic Groups and Boundaries*. London: Allen & Unwin.
- Betz, Hans-Georg (1994) *Radical Right-Wing Populism in Western Europe*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Botsiou, K. (2015) 'New Democracy and PASOK, 1974-1985: 'Europe' as politics and identity/N.Δ. και ΠΑΣΟΚ, 1974-1985: Η «Ευρώπη» ως πολιτική και ως ταυτότητα' In

- Avgeridis, M., Gazi, E. & Kornetis, K. (eds) *Regime Change: Greece at the crossroads of two centuries/Μεταπολίτευση: Η Ελλάδα στο μεταίχμιο δύο αιώνων*. Athens: Θεμέλιο.
- Brook, V. (2003) *Something Ain't Kosher Here: The rise of the 'Jewish' sitcom*. New York: Rutgers University Press.
- Bryman, A. (2012) *Social Research Methods*. 4th ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Carvalho, A. (2008) 'Media(ted) Discourse and Society', *Journalism Studies*, 9(2), pp. 161-177.
- Chairetis, S. (2020) *Queering the Greek Television 'Comedy': Popular Texts, Dissident Readings*. PhD thesis. University of Oxford.
- Chairetis, S. (2021) 'Tracing the ephemeral 'lesbian' characters in Greek television comedies', *VIEW Journal of European Television History and Culture*, 10(19), pp. 1-10.
- Chalari, A. (2015) 'Reorganising Everyday Greek Social Reality: Subjective Experiences of the Greek Crisis' In Karyotis, G. and Gerodimos, R. (eds) *The politics of extreme austerity: Greece in the eurozone crisis*. Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Chambers, D. (2001) *Representing the Family*. London: Sage.
- Chatzisavvas, G. V. (1990) 'The (non) bureaucracy. Idealtypus and Greek reality/Η (μη) γραφειοκρατία. Ιδεότυπος και ελληνική πραγματικότητα', *The Greek Review of Social Research*, 79, pp. 28-43.
- Christensen, T. and Haas, P. (2015) *Projecting politics: Political messages in American films*. London: Routledge.
- Croteau, D. and Hoynes, W. (2003) *Media Society: Industries, Images, and Audiences*. 3rd edn. London: Sage.
- Daniels, S. (1993) *Fields of Vision: landscape, imagery and national identity in England and the US*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Davidoff, L., Doolittle, M., Fink, J. and Holden, K. (1999) *The Family Story: Boon, Contract and Intimacy, 1830-1960*. Harlow: Addison Wesley Longman.
- Delli Carpini, M. (2012) 'Entertainment Media and the Political Engagement of Citizens' In Semetko, H. and Scammell, M. (eds) *The sage handbook of political communication*. London: Sage.
- Dow, B. (1996) *Prime-Time Feminism: Television, Media Culture, and the Women's Movement since 1970*. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Dyer, G. (1987) 'Introduction' In Baehr, H. and Dyer, G. (eds) *Boxed In: Women and Television*. London: Pandora.

- Eaton, M. (1978) 'Television Situation Comedy', *Screen*, 19(4), pp. 61-90.
- Economou, L. (2018) 'Sentiment, Memory, and Identity in Greek Laiko Music (1945–1967)' In Tragaki, D. (ed) *Made in Greece: Studies in Popular Music*. Routledge: New York.
- Edensor, T. (2002) *National Identity, popular culture and everyday life*. Oxford: Berg.
- Elasmar, M., Hasegawa, K. and Brain, M. (1999) 'The portrayal of women in U.S. prime time television', *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, 43(1), pp. 20-34.
- Elliot, F. R. (1996) *Gender, Family and Society*. Basingstoke: Macmillan Press.
- Entman, R. and Rojecki, A. (2001) *The black image in the white mind: Media and race in America*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Faustmann, H. (2010) 'Rusfeti and Political Patronage in the Republic of Cyprus', *The Cyprus Review*, 22(2), pp. 269-289.
- Fürsich, E. (2009) 'In defence of Textual Analysis', *Journalism Studies*, 10(2), pp. 238-252.
- Gauntlett, D. (2008) *Media, Gender and Identity: An introduction*. 2nd edn. New York: Routledge.
- Gazi, E. (2015) 'Transformations of Greek national ideology and identity after the Regime Change/Μεταπλάσεις της Ελληνικής εθνικής ιδεολογίας και ταυτότητας στη Μεταπολίτευση' In Avgeridis, M., Gazi, E. & Kornetis, K. (eds) *Regime Change: Greece at the crossroads of two centuries/Μεταπολίτευση: Η Ελλάδα στο μεταίχμιο δύο αιώνων*. Athens: Θεμέλιο.
- Georgiades, S. D. (2006) 'Favouritism as a Form of Injustice in Cyprus: Ubiquitous and Eternal?', *The Cyprus Review*, 18(2), pp. 105-127.
- Gianos, P. (1995) *Politics and politicians in American film*. Westport: Praeger.
- Giddens, A. (1990) *The consequences of modernity*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Gioltzidou, F. and Gioltzidou, G. (2023) 'Η αναπαράσταση της οικογένειας στις κωμικές τηλεοπτικές σειρές: Οι περιπτώσεις *Dolce Vita*, *Ευτυχισμένοι Μαζί*, *Το σόι σου*/The representation of family in television comedy series: The cases of *Dolce Vita*, *Happy Together (Eftihismenoi Mazi)*, *Your Kin (To Soi Sou)*' In Vamvakas, V. and Paschalidis, G. (eds) *Το Κουτί: Εικόνες της σύγχρονης Ελλάδας στην ιδιωτική τηλεόραση/The Box: Images of contemporary Greece in private television*. Athens: Brainfood.
- Gitlin, T. (1994) *Inside Prime Time*. London: Routledge.
- Goode, W. J. (1963) *World Revolution and Family Patterns*. New York: The Free Press.
- Gray, J., Jones, J. and Thompson, E. (2009) *Satire TV: Politics and comedy in the post-network era*. New York: NYU Press.
- Guibernau, M. (2007) *The identity of nations*. Cambridge: Polity Press.

- Günes-Ayata, A. (1994) 'Clientelism: Premodern, Modern, Postmodern' In Roniger, L. and Günes-Ayata, A. (eds) *Democracy, Clientelism and Civil Society*. London: Lynne Rienner.
- Gunter, B. (1995) *Television and Gender Representation*. London: John Libbey.
- Hall, S. (1975) 'Introduction' In Blackwell, T., Immirzi, E. and Smith, A. (eds) *Paper Voices: The Popular Press and Social Change 1935-1965*. London: Chatto & Windus.
- Hall, S. (1997) *Representation: Cultural representations and signifying practices*. London: Sage.
- Hallin, D. C. and Papathanassopoulos, S. (2002) 'Political clientelism and the media: southern Europe and Latin America in comparative perspective', *Media, Culture & Society*, 24(2), pp. 175-195.
- Hodkinson, P. (2011) *Media, culture and society: An introduction*. London: Sage.
- Holbert, L. (2005) 'A typology for the study of Entertainment Television and Politics', *American Behavioral Scientist*, 49(3), pp. 436-453.
- Holst-Warhaft, G. (2002) 'Politics and Popular Music in Modern Greece', *Journal of Political & Military Sociology*, 30(2), pp. 297-323.
- Inthorn, S., Street, J. and Scott, M. (2012) 'Popular culture as a resource for political engagement', *Cultural Sociology*, 7(3), pp. 336-351.
- Iosifides, T., Lavrentiadou, M., Petracou, E. and Kontis, A. (2007) 'Forms of Social Capital and the incorporation of Albanian immigrants in Greece', *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 33(8), pp. 1343-1361.
- Johnson, R. (1986-7) 'What Is Cultural Studies Anyway?', *Social Text*, 16, pp. 33-80.
- Jones, J. and Baym, G. (2010) 'A dialogue on satire news and the Crisis of Truth in postmodern political television', *Journal of Communication Inquiry*, 34(3), pp. 278-294.
- Kaklamanidou, B. (2017) 'Introduction to the Greek Sitcom: The Case of *I Tris Charites/The Three Graces*', *Filmicon: Journal of Greek Film Studies*, (4), pp. 138-154.
- Kallimopoulou, E. (2016) *Paradosiaká: Music, Meaning and Identity in Modern Greece*. Routledge: London.
- Karakasidis, G. (2023) 'Διακριτικές και αδιάκριτες αναπαραστάσεις των αλλοδαπών στις ελληνικές τηλεοπτικές σειρές (1989-2019)/Discreet and indiscreet representations of the foreigners in Greek television series (1989-2019)' In Vamvakas, V. and Paschalidis, G. (eds) *To Κουτί: Εικόνες της σύγχρονης Ελλάδας στην ιδιωτική τηλεόραση/The Box: Images of contemporary Greece in private television*. Athens: Brainfood.

- Kornetis, K. (2013) *Children of the Dictatorship: Student Resistance, Cultural Politics and the 'Long 1960s' in Greece*. New York: Berghahn Books.
- Koukoutsaki-Monnier, A. (2010) 'Greek television fiction: Diachronic development and production tendencies/Ελληνικά προγράμματα μυθοπλασίας: Διαχρονική εξέλιξη και τάσεις παραγωγής' In Vovou, I. (ed) *The World of Television: Theoretical approaches, analysis of programmes and Greek reality/Ο Κόσμος της Τηλεόρασης: Θεωρητικές προσεγγίσεις, ανάλυση προγραμμάτων και ελληνική πραγματικότητα*. Athens: Ηρόδοτος.
- Küechler, M. (1994) 'The German and the 'Others': Racism, Xenophobia, or Legitimate Conservatism?', *German Politics*, 3, pp. 47-74.
- Lauzen, M., Dozier, D. and Cleveland, E. (2006) 'Genre Matters: An Examination of Women Working Behind the Scenes and On-screen Portrayals in Reality and Scripted Prime-Time Programming', *Sex Roles*, 55(7-8), pp. 445-455.
- Linton, R. (1949) 'The Natural History of the Family' In Anshen, R. N. (ed) *The Family: Its Function and Destiny*. New York: Harper & Bros.
- Maratou-Alipranti, L. (1998) 'Single-parent Families: Contemporary trends and policy dilemmas: Comparative overview among the countries of the European Union/Μονογονεϊκές οικογένειες: Σύγχρονες τάσεις και διλήμματα πολιτικής: Συγκριτική επισκόπηση ανάμεσα στις χώρες της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης', *The Greek Review of Social Research*, 95, pp. 185-208.
- Margaroni, M. (2017) 'Social Representations of the Modern Greek Family in Popular Comic Television Series in Greece over the Last Two Decades', *Ethnologia Balkanica*, (20), pp. 233-258.
- Martens, E. and Póvoa, D. (2017) 'How to get away with colour: colour-blindness and the myth of a post-racial America in American television series', *Alphaville: Journal of Film and Screen Media*, (13), pp. 117-134.
- Mavromatidis, F. (2010) 'The role of the European Union in the name dispute between Greece and FYR Macedonia', *Journal of Contemporary European Studies*, 18(1), pp. 47-62.
- McKee, A. (2003) *Textual Analysis*. London: Sage Publications.
- McNeil, J. (1975) 'Feminism, femininity and the television series: A content analysis', *Journal of Broadcasting*, 19(3), pp. 259-269.
- Means Coleman, R. (1998) *African American Viewers and the Black Situation Comedy: Situating Racial Humour*. New York: Garland Publishing.
- Medhurst, J. (2006) 'Case study: A (very) brief history of television' In Creeber, G. (ed) *Televisions: an introduction to studying television*. London: British Film Institute.

- Meichanetsidis, V. Th. (2015) 'The Genocide of the Greeks of the Ottoman Empire, 1913-1923: A comprehensive overview', *Genocide Studies International*, 9(1), pp. 104-173.
- Mercer, K. (1990) 'Welcome to the jungle' In Rutherford, J. (ed) *Identity: Community, Culture, Difference*. London: Lawrence and Wishart.
- Michas, T. (2011) 'Putting politics above markets: Historical background to the Greek debt crisis', *Cato Institute Working Paper*, pp. 1-19.
- Michelis, L. (2011) 'The Greek Debt Crisis: Suggested Solutions and Reforms', *The Rimini Centre for Economic Analysis (RCEA)*, pp. 1-22.
- Morreale, J. (2003) *Critiquing the sitcom: A reader*. New York: Syracuse University Press.
- Nilsen, S. and Turner, S. (2014) *The Colourblind Screen: Television in post-racial America*. New York: New York University Press.
- Ordoulidis, N. (2011) 'The Greek Popular Modes', *British Postgraduate Musicology*, 11, pp. 1-17.
- Orfanos, S. (1999) 'The Creative Boldness of Mikis Theodorakis', *The Journal of Modern Hellenism*, 16, pp. 27-39.
- Papathanasopoulos, S. (1997) *The Power of Television: The logic of the medium and the market/Η Δύναμη της Τηλεόρασης: Η λογική του μέσου και η αγορά*. Athens: Εκδόσεις Καστανιώτη.
- Papathanasopoulos, S. (2000) *Η Τηλεόραση και το Κοινό της/The Television and its Audience*. Athens: Εκδόσεις Καστανιώτη.
- Paschalidis, G. (2018) 'The Lost Paradigm of Greek Television/Το Χαμένο Παράδειγμα της Ελληνικής Τηλεόρασης' In Vamvakas, V. and Paschalidis, G. (eds) *50 Years of Greek Television: Conference Proceedings/50 Χρόνια Ελληνική Τηλεόραση: Πρακτικά Συνεδρίου*. Thessaloniki: Επίκεντρο
- Paschalidis, G. and Vamvakas, V. (2018) *50 Χρόνια Ελληνική Τηλεόραση/50 Years Greek Television*. 1st ed. Thessaloniki: Επίκεντρο.
- Petridis, S. (2024) 'Writing Greek TV Comedy: Analysing the Structure of the Two Types of Greek Sitcoms', *Filmicon: Journal of Greek Film Studies*. Available at: <https://filmiconjournal.com/blog/post/90/writing-greek-tv-comedy>
- Philo, G. (2007) 'Can discourse analysis successfully explain the content of media and journalistic practice?' *Journalism Studies*, 8(2), pp. 175-196.
- Photiou, I., Charalambous, P. and Maniou, T. (2019) 'Battle of the Sexes' on Television: The Cases of the Greek-Cypriot and Greek Adaptations of *Un Gars, Une Fille*', *Filmicon: Journal of Greek Film Studies*, (6), pp. 90-111.

- Pickering, M. (2001) *Stereotyping: The politics of representation*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Prince, S. (1992) *Visions of Empire: Political Imagery in Contemporary American Film*. New York: Praeger.
- Racy, A. J. (2000) 'The Many Faces of Improvisation: The Arab Taqāsīm as a Musical Symbol', *Ethnomusicology*, 44(2), pp. 302-320.
- Robins, K (1991) 'Tradition and translation: national culture in its global context' In Harvey, S. (ed) *Enterprise and Heritage: crosscurrents of national culture*. London: Routledge.
- Robins, K (1997) 'What is the world's going on?' in du Gay, P. (ed) *Production of Culture/Cultures of Production*. London: Sage.
- Rovisco, M. (2008) 'Nation, Boundaries and Otherness in European 'Film of Voyage'' In Uricchio, W. (ed) *We Europeans?: Media, representations, identities*. Bristol: Intellect Books.
- Ryan, G. (2018) 'Introduction to positivism, interpretivism and critical theory', *Nurse Researcher*, 25(4), pp. 1-20.
- Said, E. (1978) *Orientalism*. London: Random House.
- Smith, A. (1991) *National Identity*. London: Penguin.
- Snape, D. and Spencer, L. (2003) 'The Foundations of Qualitative Research' In Ritchie, J. and Lewis, J. (eds) *Qualitative Research Practice*. London: Sage.
- Stacey, J. (1999) 'Virtual social science and the politics of family values in the United States' In Jagger, G. and Wright, C. (eds) *Changing Family Values*. London: Routledge.
- Stamatiadi, A. (2018) 'Crisis and Nostalgia in Private Television: The case of MEGA/Κρίση και νοσταλγία της ιδιωτικής τηλεόρασης: Η περίπτωση του Mega Channel' In Papadopoulos, A. (ed) *Sociology and its Public Role in the Era of the World's Transformation/Η Κοινωνιολογία και ο Δημόσιος Ρόλος της στην Εποχή της Μεταμόρφωσης του Κόσμου*. Athens: Ελληνική Κοινωνιολογική Εταιρεία.
- Stamou, A. (2018) 'Fictionalization of Germanness in the times of Greek Crisis: Deconstructing the 'Two Strangers' frame in TV sketch comedies', *Journal of Multicultural Discourses*, 13(4), pp. 377-397.
- Storey, J. (1993) *An Introductory Guide to Cultural Theory and Popular Culture*. Hemel Hempstead: Harvester Wheatsheaf.
- Taguieff, Pierre-André (1994) *Sur la Nouvelle droite: jalons d'une analyse critique/On the New Right: milestones of a critical analysis*. Paris: Descartes.

- Thwaites, T., Davis, L. and Mules, W. (2002) *Introducing Cultural and Media Studies: A Semiotic Approach*. Basingstoke: Palgrave.
- Tredy, D. (2013) 'Reflecting the changing face of American Society: How 1970's sitcoms and spin-offs helped redefine American identity', *TV/Series*, 4, pp. 9-34.
- Tsakalotos, E. (1998) 'The political economy of Social Democratic Economic Policies: The PASOK experiment in Greece', *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 14(1), pp. 114-138.
- Tuchman, G. (1978) 'Introduction: The Symbolic Annihilation of Women by the Mass Media' In Tuchman, G., Kaplan Daniels, A. and Benét, J. (eds) *Hearth and Home: Images of Women in the Mass Media*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Valoukos, S. (2018) *Ιστορία της ελληνικής τηλεόρασης (1960-2018)/History of Greek Television (1960-2018)*. Athens: Αιγόκερως.
- Vamvakas, V. (2019) 'Modernizing Tradition: Love, Friendship, Family and De-Urbanization in Greek TV Fiction (1993-2018)', *Filmicon: Journal of Greek Film Studies*, 6, pp. 17-39.
- Vande Berg, L., Wenner, L. and Gronbeck, B. (1998) *Critical Approaches to Television*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
- Βονου, Ι. (2010) 'Στοιχεία για μια μετα-ιστορία της ελληνικής τηλεόρασης: Το μέσο, η πολιτική και ο θεσμός/Elements for a meta-history of Greek television: the Medium, the Politics and the Institution' In Βονου, Ι. (ed) *Ο κόσμος της τηλεόρασης: Θεωρητικές προσεγγίσεις, ανάλυση προγραμμάτων και ελληνική πραγματικότητα/The World of Television: Theoretical Approaches, Analysis of Programmes and Greek Reality*. Athens: Ηρόδοτος.
- Weber, M., Henderson, A. and Parsons, T. (1947) *The Theory of Social and Economic Organization*. New York: Free Press.
- Woodward, K. (1997) *Identity and Difference*. London: Sage.